

STOCHASTIC GUARANTEES FOR STATISTICAL LEARNING METHODS

Ph.D. Thesis

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Abbreviations

Acronym	Meaning
a.e.	almost everywhere
AI	artificial intelligence
a.s.	almost surely
AR	autoregressive (system)
ARMAX	autoregressive moving average (system) with exogenous input
ARX	autoregressive (system) with exogenous input
CKME	conditional kernel mean embedding
CLT	central limit theorem
ERM	empirical risk minimization
HSIC	Hilbert–Schmidt independence criterion
i.i.d.	independent identically distributed
KME	kernel mean embedding
kNN	k-nearest neighbors
LS	least squares
ML	machine learning
MLE	maximum likelihood estimator
MoM	median-of-means
PAC	probably approximately correct
PET	point estimator based test
RKHS	reproducing kernel Hilbert space
RMM	resampled median-of-means
SPS	sign-perturbed sums
SLLN	strong law of large numbers
ULLN	uniform law of large numbers
UQ	uncertainty quantification
VC dimension	Vapnik–Chervonenkis dimension
VVKT	vector-valued kernel test

Notations

General Notations

\mathbb{N}	set of natural numbers
\mathbb{N}^+	set of positive natural numbers
\mathbb{Z}	set of integers
\mathbb{R}	set of real numbers
\mathbb{R}^+	set of positive real numbers
\mathbb{R}_+	set of nonnegative real numbers
\mathbb{R}^d	d dimensional Euclidean space
$\ \cdot\ $	2-norm on \mathbb{R}^d
$\mathbb{R}^{n \times m}$	set of matrices with n rows and m columns over \mathbb{R}
\mathbb{P}	probability measure
Ω	set of elementary events
\mathcal{A}	σ -algebra of events
\mathcal{P}	set of probability measures
$\mathcal{L}_p(\Omega, \mathcal{A}, \mathbb{P})$	\mathcal{L}_p space of real-valued functions on $(\Omega, \mathcal{A}, \mathbb{P})$
$L_p(\Omega, \mathcal{A}, \mathbb{P})$	L_p space of equivalent classes of functions on $(\Omega, \mathcal{A}, \mathbb{P})$
$L_p(\Omega, \mathcal{A}, \mathbb{P}; \mathcal{G})$	Bochner space of p -integrable \mathcal{G} -valued function classes
$[n]$	set $\{1, \dots, n\}$
$[n]_0$	set $\{0, 1, \dots, n\}$
X	random variable (or random vector)
$\sigma(X)$	σ -algebra generated by X
(X, Y)	random input-output pair
$Q_{X,Y}$ (or Q)	joint distribution of (X, Y)
Q_X	marginal distribution of X
Θ	parameter space
θ^*	“true” parameter
$\hat{\Theta}_n$	confidence region
$\mathbb{E}[X]$	expected value of X
$\mathbb{E}[X \mathcal{F}]$	conditional expectation of X w.r.t. σ -algebra \mathcal{F}
$D^2(X)$	variance of X
$B(x, \varepsilon)$	open ball around x with radius ε

Heavy-Tailed Mean Estimation

$\bar{\mu}_n$	empirical mean
$\hat{\sigma}_n^2$	unbiased estimator of the variance
$\text{med}(X)$	median of variable X
$\text{med}(\mathcal{D})$	median of sample \mathcal{D}
$\hat{\mu}$	median-of-means estimator
$\text{diam}(\cdot)$	diameter of a set
Y^i	i th coordinate of vector Y
$\text{var}(Y)$	covariance matrix of a random vector Y
$\lambda_{\max}(\Sigma)$	the greatest eigenvalue of Σ
$\text{Tr}(\Sigma)$	trace of Σ
$\mathbb{1}$	all one vector
\odot	Hadamard product

Confidence Sets for Binary Classification

\mathbb{X}	input space
\mathbb{Y}	output space
\mathcal{X}	σ -algebra on \mathbb{X}
$C_b(\mathbb{X})$	the space of bounded continuous functions on \mathbb{X}
$f^*(\cdot)$	regression function
$\eta^*(\cdot)$	conditional probability function for binary classification
$\ \cdot\ _Q$	L_2 -norm w.r.t. Q_x
U	uniform random variable on $[-1, 1]$
h^+	subgraph of function h
\mathcal{H}^+	set of subgraphs of the functions in \mathcal{H}
$V_{\mathcal{H}^+}$	VC-dimension of class \mathcal{H}^+ , pseudo-dimension of \mathcal{H}

Kernel Methods

$\mathcal{L}(\mathcal{G})$	bounded linear operators on RKHS \mathcal{G}
$\langle \cdot, \cdot \rangle_{\mathcal{G}}$	scalar product in a RKHS \mathcal{G}
$\ \cdot\ _{\mathcal{G}}$	norm in a RKHS \mathcal{G}
$\text{Id}_{\mathcal{G}}$	identity operator on \mathcal{G}
$\mathcal{M}_+(\mathbb{X}, \mathcal{X})$	set of probability measures on $(\mathbb{X}, \mathcal{X})$
μ_Y	kernel mean embedding of Q_Y
$\mu_{Y X}$	conditional kernel mean embedding of Y given X in an RKHS
$\mu^*(\cdot)$	conditional kernel mean map
$\Gamma^*(x_1, x_2)$	adjoint of $\Gamma(x_1, x_2)$
$k \otimes \ell$	product kernel of k and ℓ
$\ \cdot\ _{\otimes}$	norm of the product RKHS

Independence Tests for Stochastic Linear Systems

q^{-1}	backshift operator
$(U_t), (V_t)$	observable system inputs
$(Y_t), (Z_t)$	observable system outputs
$(E_t), (N_t)$	innovation sequences
$\text{HSIC}(E, N)$	Hilbert-Schmidt independence criterion of $Q_{E,N}$
$\text{HSIC}_n(\cdot)$	empirical Hilbert-Schmidt independence criterion estimator
S_n	symmetric group of permutations over $[n]$
$\ \cdot\ _{c(\infty)}$	Cesàro norm

Chapter 1

Introduction

In this dissertation we present stochastic guarantees for statistical learning methods that are at the core of several technological innovation. They provide a theoretical foundation for machine learning (ML), which is an essential component of artificial intelligence (AI). In real-world applications ML algorithms run in uncertain environments, thus they have to cope with uncertainty when modeling unknown systems and estimating parameters of unknown distributions based on random (possibly noisy) observations. Stochastic guarantees are presented in the form of novel algorithms for constructing confidence regions and hypothesis tests. We prove theorems that ensure both finite sample and asymptotic bounds for four fundamental statistical learning problems: heavy-tailed mean estimation, regression function estimation for binary classification, conditional kernel mean embedding (CKME) estimation and independence testing.

ML is a rapidly evolving field (Devroye et al., 2013; Györfi et al., 2002; Hastie et al., 2009; Vapnik, 1998) fundamentally grounded in mathematical statistics and computer science. Recent advances in this area have already made a huge socioeconomic impact by propelling AI and provide a potential driving force for future developments in science and technology (Samoli et al., 2020). The technological revolution of recent decades has not only “glorified” several statistical results, but also motivated new mathematical challenges. In this dissertation we focus on quantifying the uncertainty of ML methods with finite sample stochastic guarantees and proving asymptotic results in a data-driven, distribution-free framework that uses the information in the data efficiently and makes only mild distributional assumptions on the observations.

1.1 Uncertainty Quantification

Uncertainty quantification (UQ) is essential for robust and trustworthy AI, where we need to avoid unnecessary risks and meet strict safety, stability and quality criteria. Despite significant improvements, current ML solutions still fall short to these objectives in several cases (Jordan, 2019). Providing guarantee tags for ML algorithms is a possible solution for UQ. The main results of this dissertation infer stochastic guarantees in the form

of confidence regions, hypothesis tests, probably approximately correct (PAC) bounds and consistency theorems, which can quantify several error criteria, e.g., the probability of confidence, the probability of errors, the expected risk or the conditional distribution of a variable w.r.t. some observations.

1.2 Driven by Data

Over the past few decades, there has been an enormous increase in computing power and in the ability to gather, store and transfer data. This phenomena drove a vast amount of scientists and practitioners to use ML solutions to gain insights, predict and make decisions efficiently. However, collecting data can be really expensive, time-consuming, difficult or ethically constrained in several fields. Typical small sample application domains include clinical trials of new drugs, crash testing of vehicles, safety-critical forecasting from limited (possibly nonstationary) historical data, such as predicting floods or financial market collapses. Thus, the need for efficient non-asymptotically guaranteed, data-driven methods is immense. In this dissertation novel data-driven and hyperparameter-free algorithms are presented for UQ, which can be used for a wide range of applications under mild statistical assumptions, preferably for any finite sample size.

1.3 Algorithmic Learning

The field of ML emerged in the intersection of statistics and computer science ([Jordan and Mitchell, 2015](#)). Due to the different interests of these scientific fields, there is often a trade-off between statistical efficiency and algorithmic feasibility, when we apply ML algorithms. On the one hand statistically superior methods can be complex, e.g., may suffer from the “curse of dimensionality”, producing algorithms that require exponential time or space to run. On the other hand heuristic polynomial time algorithms do not always admit statistical benefits. In this dissertation our main goal is to present stochastic guarantees, therefore we focus on the statistical characteristics of the novel methods. Our algorithms construct confidence regions and hypothesis tests that are valid for any sample size and are proved to be consistent under mild statistical assumptions. In this dissertation the algorithmic complexity of the new methods plays only a secondary role. Nevertheless, we reveal the main algorithmic attributes of the presented approaches emphasizing the practical advantages and constraints.

Chapter 2

Preliminaries

2.1 Statistical Inference

In this dissertation we work on the statistical space $(\Omega, \mathcal{A}, \mathcal{P})$, where Ω is a sufficiently large set of elementary events, \mathcal{A} is the σ -algebra of events and \mathcal{P} is a set of probability measures. The main challenge in statistics is to infer some features of an unknown measure $\mathbb{P} \in \mathcal{P}$ based on measurable observations. More precisely let $(\mathbb{M}, \mathcal{M})$ be some measurable sample space and $\mathcal{D} : \Omega \rightarrow \mathbb{M}^n$ be a random element in \mathbb{M}^n , a.k.a. sample or data of size $n \in \mathbb{N}^+$, where \mathbb{N}^+ denotes the set of positive natural numbers. Let $Q_{\mathcal{D}}$ denote the distribution of \mathcal{D} , i.e., the push-forward measure of \mathbb{P} given \mathcal{D} defined by $Q_{\mathcal{D}}(B) = \mathbb{P}(\mathcal{D} \in B)$ for $B \in \otimes_{i=1}^n \mathcal{M}$, where $\otimes_{i=1}^n \mathcal{M}$ is the product of σ -algebras. In most cases we work directly with $(\mathbb{M}^n, \otimes_{i=1}^n \mathcal{M}, Q_{\mathcal{D}})$ and our main objective is to derive some properties of $Q_{\mathcal{D}}$ based on \mathcal{D} . In Chapter 3, Chapter 4 and Chapter 5 the observations are independent and identically distributed (i.i.d.), i.e., $\mathcal{D} = (Z_1, \dots, Z_n)$ for some i.i.d. $\{Z_i\}_{i=1}^n$ and $Q_{\mathcal{D}} = \otimes_{i=1}^n Q_{\mathbf{z}}$, where $Q_{\mathbf{z}}$ is the distribution of Z_1 . In Chapter 6 special synchronized linear systems are considered, where the components of the sample can be dependent.

2.1.1 Nonparametric Statistics

A fundamental building block of a statistical problem is the given class of probability measures. This set incorporates our prior distributional knowledge of the observations. Though, in theory \mathcal{P} can consist of all probability measures on \mathcal{A} , usually \mathcal{P} is given in an indexed form as $\mathcal{P} = \{\mathbb{P}_{\theta} : \theta \in \Theta\}$, where Θ is the set of indexes. If $\Theta \subseteq \mathbb{R}^p$ for some p -dimensional Euclidean space, for a fixed $p \in \mathbb{N}^+$, then we say that \mathcal{P} is a parametric family of probabilities. If Θ can not be included in a (finite dimensional) Euclidean space, then the family of probability measures and the corresponding statistical space are nonparametric. For simplicity we will call the elements of Θ parameters even if we deal with nonparametric problems. Nonparametric methods are needed if Θ is an abstract set, e.g., if it contains functions. In this work we mainly focus on nonparametric inference.

2.1.2 Distribution-Free Perspective

In statistics one of the main goals is to estimate unknown quantities given some random observations. These quantities are estimated from the data based on prior distributional information incorporated in \mathcal{P} . We aim to use very mild distributional assumptions, i.e., we would like \mathcal{P} to be as broad as possible. Most of our results are presented in the classical i.i.d. settings, for which we have $\mathcal{D} = (Z_1, \dots, Z_n)$ with i.i.d. elements $\{Z_i\}_{i=1}^n$. This nonparametric framework is called distribution-free, because in this model the distribution of the components is not restricted. Distribution-free methods offer reliable solutions for applications which deal with unknown observation generating mechanisms. We use the term distribution-free in a broader sense calling every result distribution-free, which makes mild nonparametric statistical assumptions on the data generating distribution (e.g., symmetry, exchangeability), uses only some moment information or requires other nonparametric properties of the sample distribution.

2.1.3 Data-Driven Methods

In the dissertation we do not only minimize the distributional assumptions that we make, but we also use the available information in the data as efficiently as possible, that is, we derive and analyze data-driven methods. Most of the presented algorithms are hyperparameter-free and do not use any moment information making it easily applicable in many real-world problems. We also prove distribution dependent (pointwise) performance bounds for the data-driven methods under stronger distributional assumptions to make the presented framework adaptive to stochastic environments.

2.1.4 A Note on Inferential Approaches

There is a philosophical debate regarding the “nature” of statistical parameters. Without diving into details we note that in this work we consider only Fisherian methods (Fisher, 1925, 1935), i.e., we assume a ground truth in the form of an unknown (non-random) parameter $\theta^* \in \Theta$. Though in the literature these methods are usually called frequentist, we do not use this terminology in this dissertation, because it refers also to a particular interpretation of probability, which can be misleading, especially when we deal with non-asymptotic properties of statistics.

Bayesian inference offers a fundamentally different approach to statistics by considering a random parameter which admits a prior distribution. For real world problems usually some expertise is incorporated in the prior distribution. In this work we assume as few domain specific knowledge as possible and make only mild assumptions on the data generating distribution, therefore we do not consider Bayesian approaches; rather we focus on aforementioned Fisherian methods.

2.2 Stochastic Guarantees

2.2.1 Beyond Point Estimation

Most statistical methods only provide a point estimator for the true parameter, however, a point estimate in an uncertain environment typically equals to the true parameter with probability zero for a finite set of sample. For several applications the uncertainty of the point estimator should be quantified; some guarantee tags are sought. Confidence regions are popular tools to quantify the uncertainty of an estimator by providing stochastic guarantees for covering the true parameter.

Confidence Regions

For a prescribed confidence level $\gamma \in (0, 1)$ a confidence region is a (random) set of parameters, $\hat{\Theta}_n \subseteq \Theta$, which contains the true parameter with probability at least γ , i.e.,

$$\mathbb{P}_{\theta^*}(\theta^* \in \hat{\Theta}_n) \geq \gamma. \quad (2.1)$$

Note that (2.1) must hold for every possible $\theta^* \in \Theta$. For the sake of simplicity we are not going to indicate the dependence of \mathbb{P} on θ^* . Observe that in (2.1) the true parameter is fixed and $\hat{\Theta}_n$ is the random object. Obviously $\{\theta^* \in \hat{\Theta}_n\} \in \mathcal{A}$ needs to be satisfied for (2.1) to make sense. For the presented novel methods this condition will automatically hold. The confidence level (a.k.a. coverage probability) can be chosen w.r.t. the area of use. Typical choices include 0.9, 0.95, 0.99. If (2.1) holds with equality for all $\theta^* \in \Theta$, then we say that $\hat{\Theta}_n$ is exact with confidence level γ . If (2.1) holds with strict inequality for some $\theta^* \in \Theta$, then we say that $\hat{\Theta}_n$ is conservative. The exclusion probability of θ^* in $\hat{\Theta}_n$ is called the significance level of $\hat{\Theta}_n$.

It is easy to construct noninformative exact confidence sets, e.g., one can take the whole parameter space with probability γ and the empty set with probability $1 - \gamma$ independently from the sample. The resulted region covers the true parameter with probability γ , however, the confidence set does not contain any information about θ^* . We want to avoid these degenerate constructions, therefore we quantify the “size” and “shape” of $\hat{\Theta}_n$.

Hypothesis Tests

Hypothesis testing provides an alternative for constructing confidence regions in several problems. These two approaches are often equivalent. Let $\varphi : \mathbb{Z}^n \times \Theta \rightarrow \{0, 1\}$ be a (possibly randomized) hypothesis test with significance level δ for the simple null hypothesis and its alternative for a given $\theta \in \Theta$:

$$H_0 : \theta^* = \theta \quad \text{vs} \quad H_1 : \theta^* \neq \theta. \quad (2.2)$$

If $\varphi(\mathcal{D}, \theta)$ is equal to 0, then H_0 is rejected, otherwise the null hypothesis is accepted. The significance level controls the probability of type I error, i.e., the probability of rejection

under the null hypothesis. Thus for a test φ with significance level δ we have

$$\mathbb{P}(\varphi(\mathcal{D}, \theta^*) = 0) \leq \delta. \quad (2.3)$$

A confidence set $\hat{\Theta}_n$ with confidence level $1 - \delta$ can be used to define a hypothesis test φ with significance level δ as

$$\varphi(\mathcal{D}, \theta) = \mathbb{I}(\theta \in \hat{\Theta}_n) \quad (2.4)$$

and vice versa a test φ defines a confidence region with confidence level $1 - \delta$ by

$$\hat{\Theta}_n = \{ \theta : \varphi(\mathcal{D}, \theta) = 1 \}. \quad (2.5)$$

In the dissertation we construct confidence regions based on hypothesis tests using (2.5), i.e., $\hat{\Theta}_n$ will include those parameters that are accepted by a hypothesis test φ .

2.2.2 Finite Sample Guarantees

Statistical methods need to use only a finite amount of data. For several applications, e.g., crash testing of cars, collecting data can be really expensive, time-consuming or extremely difficult. In these cases providing non-asymptotic guarantees to the statistical methods are often vital. In this dissertation we emphasize the finite sample aspect of the presented methods. We aim to prove non-asymptotic results, i.e., prove stochastic bounds that hold for every sample size. We achieve finite sample guarantees for the confidence level, that is, we construct confidence regions with confidence level γ such that

$$\mathbb{P}(\theta^* \in \hat{\Theta}_n) \geq \gamma \quad (2.6)$$

holds for every $n \in \mathbb{N}^+$. It is one of the main challenges in this dissertation that we assert compare to several popular constructions, e.g., central limit theorem (CLT) based methods, which provide only approximate guarantees for a fixed sample size. Our main tool to achieve these non-asymptotic guarantees is a resampling framework (Csáji et al., 2014), which was originally developed for linear regression in system identification. Similar ideas also show up in Monte Carlo testing (Zhu, 2006), bootstrapping (Efron and Tibshirani, 1994), jackknife estimation (Quenouille, 1956) and conformal learning methods (Vovk et al., 2005). These are reviewed in Section 2.4.

Additionally, we prove non-asymptotic probably approximately correct (PAC) bounds on the “shrinkage” of the confidence regions based on concentration inequalities (Boucheron et al., 2013). We consider several error criteria for $\hat{\Theta}_n$. First, the pointwise exclusion probability is quantified for any parameter $\theta \neq \theta^*$ w.r.t. the difference between θ and θ^* and the sample size. We note that this is equivalent to considering the power of the corresponding hypothesis test. Second, we determine the convergence rate of confidence intervals for the expected value w.r.t. the sample size and a confidence parameter under heavy-tailed distributional assumptions. Finally, we consider the inclusion probability of $\hat{\Theta}_n$ in $B(\theta^*, \varepsilon)$, the open ball around θ^* with radius ε , for some fixed $\varepsilon > 0$ given some

metric on Θ . These non-asymptotically valid bounds produce more reliable guarantees in practice than limit theorems.

2.2.3 Strong Consistency

Beside the finite sample guarantees we explore the asymptotic properties of the presented methods. Several consistency results are proved in the dissertation. Let ϱ be a metric on space Θ . A point estimator $(\hat{\theta}_n)$ is strongly consistent if as $n \rightarrow \infty$ we have

$$\hat{\theta}_n \xrightarrow{a.s.} \theta^*. \quad (2.7)$$

The convergence in (2.7) needs to hold for all possible $\theta^* \in \Theta$. Similarly, $(\hat{\theta}_n)$ is consistent if the convergence holds in probability. In particular let $(\mathbb{X}, \mathcal{X}, Q_X)$ be a measure space and $\theta^* = f^* \in L_2(\mathbb{X}, \mathcal{X}, Q_X)$. The strong consistency of an estimator (f_n) in this setup is

$$\int (f^* - f_n)^2 dQ_X \xrightarrow{a.s.} 0, \quad (2.8)$$

which is also called the strong L_2 -consistency of (f_n) . We say that (f_n) is weakly L_2 -consistent if the convergence holds in expectation, that is, as $n \rightarrow \infty$ we have

$$\mathbb{E} \left[\int (f^* - f_n)^2 dQ_X \right] \rightarrow 0. \quad (2.9)$$

Since stochastic convergence is strictly weaker than L_1 convergence, weak consistency is not equivalent to consistency.

A confidence region estimate $(\hat{\Theta}_n)$ is pointwise consistent if for all $\theta \neq \theta^*$ we have

$$\mathbb{P} \left(\limsup_{n \rightarrow \infty} \{\theta \in \hat{\Theta}_n\} \right) = \mathbb{P} \left(\bigcap_{n=1}^{\infty} \bigcup_{k=n}^{\infty} \{\theta \in \hat{\Theta}_k\} \right) = 0. \quad (2.10)$$

We note that (2.10) can hold without assuming any topology on Θ . Intuitively if $(\hat{\Theta}_n)$ is pointwise consistent, then θ is included infinitely many times in the confidence regions as $n \rightarrow \infty$ with probability 0 if $\theta \neq \theta^*$, or equivalently every “bad” parameter is included in $(\hat{\Theta}_n)$ at most finitely many times with probability 1. Strong uniform consistency in a metric space (Θ, ϱ) is a stronger type of consistency. We say that $(\hat{\Theta}_n)$ is strongly uniformly consistent if for all $\varepsilon > 0$ we have

$$\mathbb{P} \left(\liminf_{n \rightarrow \infty} \{\hat{\Theta}_n \subseteq B(\theta^*, \varepsilon)\} \right) = \mathbb{P} \left(\bigcup_{n=1}^{\infty} \bigcap_{k=n}^{\infty} \{\hat{\Theta}_k \subseteq B(\theta^*, \varepsilon)\} \right) = 1. \quad (2.11)$$

Intuitively, (2.11) says that $\hat{\Theta}_n$ is included in $B(\theta^*, \varepsilon)$ for all but finitely many $n \in \mathbb{N}^+$ with probability 1, hence in this case the “bad” parameters are excluded uniformly.

2.3 Statistical Learning Problems

In the dissertation we consider four classical statistical learning problems. First, we construct confidence intervals for the mean of an unknown distribution. Second, we examine binary classification and seek to build confidence regions for the regression function. Third, motivated by conditional distribution estimation, CKME estimation is tackled. Finally, we consider the problem of independence testing for synchronous, stochastic linear systems. In the sections that follow we present brief introductions for these problems and review some of the most important methods and corresponding results.

2.3.1 Confidence Intervals for the Mean

Let Y be a random variable in \mathbb{R} with finite mean μ and distribution Q_Y . Constructing confidence intervals for μ based on an i.i.d. sample $\mathcal{D} \doteq \{Y_i\}_{i=1}^n$ from Q_Y is one of the key problems in statistics and it serves as a backbone for countless methods in ML. Let $\delta \in (0, 1)$ denote the desired significance level. If $\sigma^2 \doteq D^2[Y_1] < \infty$, then classical theory supports the application of the well-known (unbiased) empirical mean and variance:

$$\bar{\mu}_n \doteq \frac{1}{n} \sum_{i=1}^n Y_i \quad \text{and} \quad \hat{\sigma}_n^2 = \frac{1}{n-1} \sum_{i=1}^n (Y_i - \bar{\mu}_n)^2 \quad \text{for } n \geq 2, \quad (2.12)$$

that is, confidence intervals can be constructed based on the CLT using

$$\mathbb{P}\left(\mu \in \left[\bar{\mu}_n - \frac{z_{1-\delta/2}\hat{\sigma}_n}{\sqrt{n}}, \bar{\mu}_n + \frac{z_{1-\delta/2}\hat{\sigma}_n}{\sqrt{n}}\right]\right) \approx 1 - \delta, \quad (2.13)$$

where $z_{1-\delta/2}$ is the $(1 - \delta/2)$ -quantile of the standard normal distribution. However, CLT only provides approximate guarantees for a finite sample size and the required moment assumption does not necessarily hold in practice. From another asymptotic viewpoint CLT yields a Gaussian tail bound

$$\lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} \mathbb{P}\left(\sqrt{n} |\bar{\mu}_n - \mu| > \sigma \sqrt{2 \log(2/\delta)}\right) \leq \delta. \quad (2.14)$$

Under additional assumptions the same tail bound holds for every finite sample size. If the distribution of Y is σ -subgaussian, i.e., there exists a $\sigma > 0$ such that

$$\mathbb{E}[\exp(\lambda(Y - \mu))] \leq \exp(\sigma^2 \lambda^2 / 2) \quad (2.15)$$

for all $\lambda \in \mathbb{R}$, then by Chernoff's bound one has

$$\mathbb{P}\left(\sqrt{n} |\bar{\mu}_n - \mu| > \sigma \sqrt{2 \log(2/\delta)}\right) \leq \delta. \quad (2.16)$$

Observe that (2.16) holds for every $n \in \mathbb{N}^+$, however, one needs to know σ to construct confidence intervals based on (2.16). Using a standard deviation estimator yields only a

heuristic solution and provides approximate guarantees. Our contribution to the mean estimation problem is twofold. We get rid of the variance estimation problem and construct confidence intervals for symmetric distributions that are exact for every sample size. Additionally, we prove that the diameters of the novel confidence intervals shrink at the same rate w.r.t. δ and n as (2.16) under milder conditions than subgaussianity.

2.3.2 Heavy-Tailed Mean Estimation

For many problems we need to cope with heavy-tailed distributions and handle outliers in the data. In these cases the empirical mean and standard CLT based confidence intervals can perform poorly calling for robust techniques (Hampel et al., 2011; Huber and Ronchetti, 2009). If the distribution of Y has a finite variance σ^2 but is not subgaussian, then Chebyshev's inequality yields

$$\mathbb{P}\left(|\bar{\mu}_n - \mu| \leq \sigma\sqrt{\frac{1}{n\delta}}\right) \geq 1 - \delta \quad (2.17)$$

for $\delta > 0$ and $n \in \mathbb{N}^+$. This is an exponentially weaker bound in δ than (2.16). Catoni (2012) proved that this bound is optimal, i.e., there exists a constant $c > 0$ such that for every $\delta > 0$ and $n \in \mathbb{N}^+$ there is a distribution with variance σ^2 for which we have

$$\mathbb{P}\left(|\bar{\mu}_n - \mu| \geq \sigma\sqrt{\frac{c}{\delta n}}\right) \geq \delta. \quad (2.18)$$

Somewhat surprisingly there are estimators that admit stronger tail bounds than the empirical mean for heavy-tailed distributions, hence the empirical mean is not the “best” in this sense. In general the empirical mean is computationally attractive and statistically efficient for σ -subgaussian distributions but sensitive for outliers which occur with high probability in case of heavy-tailed distributions.

In the dissertation we consider distributions which admit the so-called moment condition, i.e., let $\mu \doteq \mathbb{E}[Y]$ as above and we assume that

$$\mathbb{E}[|Y_1 - \mu|^{1+a}] = M \quad (2.19)$$

for some $a \in (0, 1]$ and $M > 0$. For $a = 1$ we can recover the variance in (2.19). Note that assuming the existence of the variance is much milder than assuming subgaussianity for some $\sigma > 0$. For $a < 1$, condition (2.19) is even less restrictive.

Let us consider the median-of-means (MoM) estimator (Alon et al., 1996; Huber and Ronchetti, 2009; Nemirovsky and Yudin, 1983), which admits a σ -subgaussian tail bounds under the finite variance assumption and is statistically efficient under milder moment conditions. Let $Y_{(1)} \leq Y_{(2)} \leq \dots \leq Y_{(n)}$ denote the ordered sample. Then for the sake of

simplicity, let the empirical median of sample Y_1, \dots, Y_n be

$$\text{med}(\mathcal{D}) = \text{med}(Y_1, \dots, Y_n) \doteq \begin{cases} Y_{(n/2)} & \text{if } n \text{ is even,} \\ Y_{(\lfloor n/2 \rfloor)} & \text{if } n \text{ is odd.} \end{cases} \quad (2.20)$$

Let k be an integer at most n . For the MoM estimator one needs to divide the dataset into k groups of almost the same size, i.e., let $\tilde{n} = \lfloor n/k \rfloor$ and for $\ell = 1, \dots, k$ if $\tilde{n}k + \ell \leq n$ let $B_\ell \doteq \{Y_\ell, \dots, Y_{\ell+\tilde{n}k}\}$, and $B_\ell \doteq \{Y_\ell, \dots, Y_{\ell+(\tilde{n}-1)k}\}$ otherwise. Partition B_1, \dots, B_k can be defined in many ways as long as $|B_\ell| \geq \tilde{n}$ holds for each $\ell \in [k] \doteq \{1, \dots, k\}$. Then

$$\hat{\mu}(\mathcal{D}_0) \doteq \text{med} \left(\frac{1}{|B_1|} \sum_{i \in B_1} Y_i, \dots, \frac{1}{|B_k|} \sum_{i \in B_k} Y_i \right) \quad (2.21)$$

is the MoM estimator. Its optimal finite sample performance is proved in (Bubeck et al., 2013; Devroye et al., 2016; Lugosi and Mendelson, 2019a):

Theorem 2.3.1. *Assume that $\{Y_1, \dots, Y_n\}$ is an i.i.d. sample, $\mathbb{E}[Y_1] = \mu$ and for $a \in (0, 1]$*

$$\mathbb{E}[|Y_1 - \mu|^{1+a}] = M. \quad (2.22)$$

Let $\delta > 0$, then the MoM estimator $\hat{\mu}$ with $k = \lceil 8 \log(2/\delta) \rceil$ satisfies

$$\mathbb{P} \left(|\hat{\mu} - \mu| \leq 8 \left(\frac{12M^{1/a} \log(1/\delta)}{n} \right)^{a/(1+a)} \right) > 1 - \delta. \quad (2.23)$$

Moreover, for any mean estimator μ_n , sample size $n \in \mathbb{N}^+$ and $\delta > 0$ there exists a distribution with mean μ and $(1+a)$ th central moment M such that

$$\mathbb{P} \left(|\mu_n - \mu| > \left(\frac{M^{1/a} \log(2/\delta)}{n} \right)^{a/(1+a)} \right) \geq \delta. \quad (2.24)$$

The second part of the theorem provides a lower bound for the rate w.r.t. δ and n , hence the MoM estimator achieves an optimal bound (up to a constant factor). If a and M are known, then confidence intervals can be built based on (2.23), however, these moment parameters needs to be estimated in practice. We build on this result and construct data-driven exact confidence intervals for μ under the symmetricity assumption without the knowledge of hyperparameters a and M . Furthermore, we prove that our novel confidence intervals shrink at the same rate w.r.t. δ and n as (2.23).

2.3.3 Binary Classification

Classification or pattern recognition is one of the fundamental problems in supervised learning (Vapnik, 1998). In this problem a sample consisting of i.i.d. random pairs $\{(X_i, Y_i)\}_{i=1}^n$ is given from an unknown joint distribution Q ($Q_{X,Y}$) in a measurable space

$(\mathbb{X} \times \mathbb{Y}, \mathcal{X} \otimes \mathcal{Y})$, where $X \in \mathbb{X}$ is a random element from the so-called input space and Y is the output variable from a finite (measurable) set \mathbb{Y} . In this dissertation we focus on binary classification in which case $\mathbb{Y} = \{-1, +1\}$. For some of the results we assume that \mathbb{X} is a Polish space, that is, \mathbb{X} is separable and completely metrizable, or that $\mathbb{X} \subseteq \mathbb{R}^d$.

Let us include some well-known results about binary classification from the seminal work of [Devroye et al. \(2013\)](#). A key observation is that for classification the joint distribution $Q_{X,Y}$ can be decomposed into a pair of (Q_X, η^*) , where Q_X is the distribution of X - the marginal distribution of $Q_{X,Y}$ - and η^* is the conditional probability function, i.e.,

$$Q_X(A) \doteq \mathbb{P}(X \in A) \text{ for } A \in \mathcal{X} \quad \text{and} \quad \eta^*(x) = \mathbb{P}(Y = 1 | X = x) \quad Q_X\text{-a.e.} \quad (2.25)$$

Proposition 2.3.2. *The (Q_X, η^*) pair determines the joint distribution of (X, Y) .*

A classifier is a measurable function $\phi : \mathbb{X} \rightarrow \{+1, -1\}$ that assigns a class for each input point. Let \mathbb{R}_+ denote the set of nonnegative numbers and $L : \mathbb{Y} \times \mathbb{Y} \rightarrow \mathbb{R}_+$ be a (measurable) loss function, which measures the error at a given output point. In the dissertation we use the 0/1-loss defined by $L(\hat{y}, y) \doteq \mathbb{I}(\hat{y} \neq y)$. Usually the goal of classification is to minimize the so-called a priori risk or Bayes risk, which is the expected loss, i.e., $R(\phi) \doteq \mathbb{E}[L(\phi(X), Y)]$. We say that ϕ^* is Bayes optimal (or optimal) if $\phi^* \in \arg \min_{\phi} R(\phi)$. From the definition we can see that the Bayes optimal classifier is not necessarily unique and the existence of at least one optimal classifier is also not obvious for every loss function. However, for the 0/1-loss, the Bayes risk equals to the misclassification probability, i.e.,

$$R(\phi) = \mathbb{E}[\mathbb{I}(\phi(X) \neq Y)] = \mathbb{P}(\phi(X) \neq Y). \quad (2.26)$$

Additionally, a Bayes optimal classifier can be determined with the help of the conditional expected value function $f^*(x) \doteq \mathbb{E}[Y | X = x]$, the so-called regression function.

Proposition 2.3.3. *Function $\phi^* : \mathbb{X} \rightarrow \{-1, +1\}$ defined by*

$$\phi^*(x) = \text{sign}(2\eta^*(x) - 1) = \text{sign}(f^*(x)) \quad (2.27)$$

is Bayes optimal in case of the 0/1-loss, where for the sake of simplicity let

$$\text{sign}(x) \doteq 2\mathbb{I}(x \geq 0) - 1. \quad (2.28)$$

Proposition 2.3.3 can be interpreted as follows. Variable Y conditioned on $X = x$ is a random binary variable taking $+1$ with probability $\eta^*(x)$ and -1 with probability $1 - \eta^*(x)$. The optimal classifier assigns the most probable outcome to each input. If both class probabilities are equal to $1/2$, then one can choose the output arbitrarily. In those cases our choice, ϕ^* , favors the $+1$ class. In Chapter 4 we construct exact confidence regions for the regression function, because f^* contains more information than the Bayes optimal classifier by quantifying the misclassification probabilities for every input.

2.3.4 Conditional Distribution Estimation

In supervised learning the object of interest is to predict some output variable Y based on some input variable X . In prediction we usually try to guess the value of Y , however, it is often not possible to determine Y exactly based on X , therefore the conditional expected value of Y w.r.t. X , the regression function, is estimated. In Chapter 5 we go further. We consider a harder problem: estimating the conditional distributions given the inputs. We note, that for binary classification this is equivalent to estimating the regression function, because in that case the distribution of Y conditioned on X is a translated Bernoulli distribution whose parameter depends on X via f^* .

In this section we review the problem of conditional distribution estimation, which is of high importance, especially for UQ. It is a very hard problem, where a probability measure-valued function needs to be estimated. As above let $\{(X_i, Y_i)\}_{i=1}^n$ be an i.i.d. sample in a measurable space $(\mathbb{X} \times \mathbb{Y}, \mathcal{X} \otimes \mathcal{Y})$ from distribution $Q_{X,Y}$, where $X \in \mathbb{X}$ is the random input in a Borel space. Let $\sigma(X)$ denote the σ -algebra generated by X and let Y be an output variable in a Polish space \mathbb{Y} . We aim to estimate the regular conditional distribution kernel given X , which satisfies

$$\nu_{Y|X}(B, x) = \mathbb{P}(Y \in B | X = x), \quad (2.29)$$

for each $B \in \mathcal{Y}$ and $x \in \mathbb{X}$, where $\nu_{Y|X}(\cdot, x)$ is a probability measure on $(\mathbb{Y}, \mathcal{Y})$ Q_x -a.e. and $\nu_{Y|X}(B, \cdot)$ is measurable for all $B \in \mathcal{Y}$. The conditional probability kernel exists by the Doob–Dynkin lemma (Kallenberg, 2002). Let ϱ be a metric on $\mathcal{M}_+(\mathbb{Y}, \mathcal{Y})$, where $\mathcal{M}_+(\mathbb{Y}, \mathcal{Y})$ denotes the set of probability measures on $(\mathbb{Y}, \mathcal{Y})$. Then the risk of a measure-valued function $\nu : \mathbb{X} \rightarrow \mathcal{M}_+(\mathbb{Y}, \mathcal{Y})$ is defined as $\mathbb{E}[\varrho(\nu(X), \nu_{Y|X}(\cdot, X))]$ assuming that $\varrho(\nu(x), \nu_{Y|X}(\cdot, x))$ is in $L_1(\mathbb{X}, \mathcal{X}, Q_x)$, thus metric ϱ plays the role of the loss function on probability measures. We say that an estimator $(\nu_n)_{n \in \mathbb{N}^+}$ is strongly consistent if

$$\int \varrho(\nu_n, \nu_{Y|X}) dQ_x \xrightarrow{a.s.} 0. \quad (2.30)$$

In Chapter 5 we show one solution to deal with this problem using CKMEs, which are popular tools in ML. Kernel mean embeddings (KMEs) map the distributions into a reproducing kernel Hilbert space (RKHS), where the inner product induced metric can be used. In Chapter 5 we present a point estimator for the conditional kernel mean map, which encodes some properties of the conditional distribution given the input, and prove strong consistency under mild statistical assumptions in an abstract framework.

2.4 Resampling Methods

Our new hypothesis tests and confidence regions are resampling methods. This class of algorithms makes statistical inference based on alternatively drawn samples. In the dissertation our aim is to verify the universality and demonstrate the flexibility of these

resampling approaches. Monte Carlo tests (Zhu, 2006), bootstrap (Efron and Tibshirani, 1994) and jackknife (Wu, 1986) are the most well-known examples of this area. Our algorithms differ from the original bootstrap and jackknife in the sense that we generate alternative samples from a hypothetical class of distributions, instead of sampling from the empirical one (or an approximate distribution). Another difference w.r.t. bootstrap is that we give finite sample guarantees instead of using the asymptotic distribution of the estimator. For the sake of completeness, we also include a brief introduction to conformal learning, which is another elegant distribution-free approach to UQ. It has already been used for jackknife methods to prove universal performance bounds (Barber et al., 2021).

2.4.1 Monte Carlo Tests

Monte Carlo tests generate samples from a test distribution and compare some statistics of the alternative datasets to that of the original sample. We apply this principle several times in the dissertation and present new Monte Carlo tests. Further, we emphasize the confidence region perspective of the defined tests and show how to reduce the cost of the alternative data generation to a constant and manage to test any candidate. For mean estimation we also give a compact representation of the confidence sets.

The main idea of Monte Carlo tests can be demonstrated on the goodness of fit test. Let $\mathcal{D}_0 = \{Y_1, \dots, Y_n\}$ be an i.i.d. sample in \mathbb{R} from a distribution $Q_Y \in \mathcal{Q}$. Let us consider the hypothesis testing problem for $Q \in \mathcal{Q}$:

$$H_0 : Q_Y = Q \quad \text{vs} \quad H_1 : Q_Y \neq Q. \quad (2.31)$$

A valid procedure for a rational significance level $\delta \in (0, 1)$ is as follows. Let $\delta = r/m$ for some integers r and m . Let $\mathcal{D}_j = \{Y_{i,j}\}_{i=1}^n$ be artificially generated samples from Q for $j \in [m-1]$. Then for any statistic $T_n : \mathbb{R}^n \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$ let us consider the reference variables

$$T_j = T_n(\mathcal{D}_j) \quad \text{for} \quad j \in [m-1]_0 \doteq \{0, \dots, m-1\}. \quad (2.32)$$

The goodness of fit Monte Carlo test rejects H_0 if and only if

$$\mathcal{R}(Q) = 1 + \sum_{j=1}^{m-1} \mathbb{I}(T_0 \succ_{\pi} T_j) > m - r, \quad (2.33)$$

that is, H_0 is accepted if T_0 is not very large compared to T_1, \dots, T_{m-1} . Function \mathcal{R} is called ranking function, its value is the rank and the corresponding test is a rank test. It can be proven that for every $n \in \mathbb{N}^+$ we have

$$\mathbb{P}(\mathcal{R}(Q_Y) > m - r) = \delta, \quad (2.34)$$

thus the significance level of the rank test is exactly δ . Moreover, the power of the test can be controlled by choosing the test statistic in a smart way. In the dissertation the

presented methods are built on the idea of resampling and ranking. Our contributions include several constructions for T_n and \mathcal{R} that produce consistent confidence sets.

2.4.2 Jackknife

Jackknife is a special resampling technique first introduced by [Quenouille \(1956\)](#) to reduce bias, then applied by [Tukey \(1958\)](#) to estimate the variance. The main idea of jackknife is to use leave-one-out estimators. Let $\mathcal{D} = \{Y_1, \dots, Y_n\}$ denote an i.i.d. sample in \mathbb{R} from an unknown distribution Q_Y . Let θ^* be some parameter of Q_Y and $T_n : \mathbb{R}^n \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$ be an estimator of θ^* . The bias of T_n with respect to θ^* is $\mathbb{E}[T_n] - \theta^*$. Let

$$T_{(i)} = T_{n-1}(\{Y_1, \dots, Y_{i-1}, Y_{i+1}, \dots, Y_n\}) \text{ for } i \in [n], \quad (2.35)$$

then the jackknife estimator is defined as

$$T_{jack} \doteq \frac{1}{n} \sum_{i=1}^n T_{(i)}. \quad (2.36)$$

The jackknife method can be used to estimate the bias and the variance of T_n by

$$\text{bias}(T_n)_{jack} = (n-1)(T_{jack} - T_n) \text{ and } \text{var}(T_n)_{jack} = \frac{n-1}{n} \sum_{i=1}^n (T_{(i)} - T_{jack})^2. \quad (2.37)$$

The jackknife estimates give some insights about the distribution of the estimator, however, finite sample guarantees are not gained immediately by this procedure. Jackknife is often used to build confidence regions as well, but these techniques usually make stringent distributional assumptions, e.g., use approximate gaussianity ([Simonoff and Tsai, 1986](#)).

2.4.3 Bootstrap

Bootstrap is a standard resampling tool to estimate the distribution of an estimator. It was studied in several works including ([Efron and Tibshirani, 1994](#); [Hall, 2013](#); [Lahiri, 2013](#)). We consider its simplest application. Let θ^* be some parameter of Q_Y and let $\mathcal{D} = \{Y_1, \dots, Y_n\}$ be an i.i.d. sample in \mathbb{R} from Q_Y . Let $T_n(\mathcal{D})$ be an estimate of θ^* as above. We are often interested in the distribution of T_n . Bootstrap takes artificial samples from the empirical distribution Q_n defined by

$$Q_n(A) = \frac{1}{n} \sum_{i=1}^n \mathbb{I}(Y_i \in A) \quad (2.38)$$

for any measurable set A . Let m be a user-chosen integer and $\mathcal{D}_j \doteq \{Y_{1,j}, \dots, Y_{n,j}\}$ i.i.d. samples from Q_n for $j \in [m]$. Then, the empirical distribution concentrated on $\{T_n(\mathcal{D}_1), \dots, T_n(\mathcal{D}_m)\}$ denoted by Q_* is called the (empirical) bootstrap distribution of T_n . Confidence intervals can be constructed based on the quantiles of Q_* . The bootstrap

distribution is biased in general, therefore most bootstrap-based confidence intervals admit only approximate coverage guarantees for a finite set of sample.

2.4.4 Conformal Learning

Conformal inference is an elegant distribution-free framework for UQ (Angelopoulos et al., 2023; Fontana et al., 2023; Gammerman et al., 1998; Vovk et al., 2005). This framework applies similar ideas as the main results of this dissertation. The key difference w.r.t. our results is that conformal learning was introduced to construct prediction regions instead of confidence sets. Prediction regions are used in supervised learning, where an i.i.d. sample of pairs, $\mathcal{D} = \{(X_i, Y_i)\}_{i=1}^n$, is given in $(\mathbb{X} \times \mathbb{Y})^n$. The target value of a prediction region is a random (output) variable. This is a key difference w.r.t. confidence regions. A prediction region with confidence level $\gamma \in (0, 1)$ is a random measurable subset $C(\mathcal{D}) \subseteq \mathbb{Y}$ such that $\mathbb{P}(Y_{n+1} \in C(\mathcal{D})) \geq \gamma$ holds for every $n \in \mathbb{N}^+$, where Y_{n+1} is identically distributed to Y_1 and independent of \mathcal{D} .

One of the simplest conformal learning algorithm for classification is considered, which produces distribution-free prediction regions under the i.i.d. assumption with the help of an arbitrary score function $s : \mathbb{X} \times \mathbb{Y} \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$. A prediction region is defined by

$$C(x) = \{y : s(x, y) \leq \hat{q}\}, \quad (2.39)$$

where \hat{q} is the $\lceil (n+1)\gamma \rceil / n$ quantile of $\{s(X_1, Y_1), \dots, s(X_n, Y_n)\}$. The main theoretical advantage of C is as follows. It can be proved that for any distribution of (X_1, Y_1) we have

$$\gamma \leq \mathbb{P}(Y_{n+1} \in C(X_{n+1})) \leq \gamma + \frac{1}{n+1}, \quad (2.40)$$

where (X_{n+1}, Y_{n+1}) is independent of \mathcal{D} and identically distributed to (X_1, Y_1) . Conformal inference provides finite sample guarantees, i.e., (2.40) holds for every $n \in \mathbb{N}^+$. There are several useful refinements of this method, e.g., prediction intervals for regression and adaptive inference can be produced based on this technique (Angelopoulos et al., 2023).

2.5 Kernel Methods

Kernel methods are popular nonparametric tools in ML (Schölkopf and Smola, 2002; Shawe-Taylor and Cristianini, 2004; Steinwart and Christmann, 2008). Their use for classification and regression is widespread, e.g., applications of support vector machines and kernel ridge regression became standard in several fields. In the dissertation kernel methods play an important role. We consider kernelized classification methods in Chapter 4, present a novel consistent estimator for the conditional kernel mean map in Chapter 5 and a kernel-based independence test in Chapter 7.

2.5.1 Reproducing Kernel Hilbert Spaces

The theory of RKHSs provide a neat mathematical framework for kernel methods. There are two common ways to introduce this concept. We follow an abstract path by first defining the notion of RKHSs, then recovering the (positive definite) reproducing kernel function. By the well-known Moore-Aronszajn theorem (Aronszajn, 1950), this definition is equivalent to first considering a positive definite function and then generating the Hilbert space with the reproducing property.

Let \mathbb{X} be a set. It is one of the main advantages of kernel methods that they can handle abstract sets by mapping their elements to an RKHS via the so-called feature map. Let us consider a positive definite function on $\mathbb{X} \times \mathbb{X}$ and a Hilbert space of functions.

Definition 2.5.1. *A bivariate function $k : \mathbb{X} \times \mathbb{X} \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$ is a (positive definite) kernel if k is symmetric, i.e., $k(x, y) = k(y, x)$ for all $x, y \in \mathbb{X}$ and positive definite, that is, for all $n \in \mathbb{N}^+$ and $x_1, \dots, x_n \in \mathbb{X}$ kernel matrix $K \in \mathbb{R}^{n \times n}$ (Gram matrix), defined elementwise as $K_{i,j} \doteq k(x_i, x_j)$ for $i, j \in [n]$, is positive semidefinite.*

Definition 2.5.2. *Given a Hilbert space \mathcal{H} of $\mathbb{X} \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$ type functions, with inner product $\langle \cdot, \cdot \rangle_{\mathcal{H}}$, we say that \mathcal{H} is a reproducing kernel Hilbert space if the point evaluation function $\delta_x : f \rightarrow f(x)$ is bounded (or equivalently continuous) on \mathcal{H} for all $x \in \mathbb{X}$.*

By the Riesz representation theorem for an RKHS \mathcal{H} there uniquely exists a bivariate function $k(\cdot, \cdot)$, such that for all $x \in \mathbb{X}$, $k(\cdot, x) \in \mathcal{H}$ and $f(x) = \langle f, k(\cdot, x) \rangle_{\mathcal{H}}$. This is called the reproducing property, and function $k : \mathbb{X} \times \mathbb{X} \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$ is called the reproducing kernel. Consequently $k(\cdot, x)$ is the representer of δ_x . In particular $\langle k(\cdot, x), k(\cdot, y) \rangle_{\mathcal{H}} = k(x, y)$, thus k is symmetric. The kernel function is often called a (signed) similarity measure. Function $k(\cdot, x)$ is the feature of x ; the feature of x is identified with the similarities of x with respect to the other elements. Some important results about RKHSs are presented (Aronszajn, 1950; Berlinet and Thomas-Agnan, 2004; Schölkopf and Smola, 2002; Wainwright, 2019).

Proposition 2.5.1. *For an RKHS \mathcal{H} there uniquely exists a reproducing kernel k , which is symmetric and positive semidefinite.*

Theorem 2.5.2 (Moore-Aronszajn). *For each symmetric, positive definite kernel k there uniquely exists an RKHS where k satisfies the reproducing property, i.e.,*

$$\langle f(\cdot), k(\cdot, x) \rangle_{\mathcal{H}} = f(x) \quad \forall f \in \mathcal{H}. \quad (2.41)$$

Standard examples for symmetric, positive definite functions include the Gaussian kernel, the Laplacian kernel and the polynomial kernel. These are included in Table 2.1 and widely used on $\mathbb{R}^d \times \mathbb{R}^d$. Universal kernels constitute an important class.

Definition 2.5.3. *Let \mathbb{X} be a metric space and $C_b(\mathbb{X})$ denote the space of bounded continuous functions on \mathbb{X} . For a compact metric space \mathbb{X} , kernel k is universal if $\text{span}\{k(\cdot, x) : x \in \mathbb{X}\} \subseteq \mathcal{H}$ is dense in $C_b(\mathbb{X})$: for all $f \in C_b(\mathbb{X})$ and $\varepsilon > 0$ there exist $l \in \mathbb{N}^+$, $\lambda_1, \dots, \lambda_l \in \mathbb{R}$ and $x_1, \dots, x_l \in \mathbb{X}$ such that $\sup_{u \in \mathbb{X}} |f(u) - \sum_{i=1}^l \lambda_i k(u, x_i)| < \varepsilon$.*

name	domain	function	parameters	U	C
Gaussian kernel	$\mathbb{R}^d \times \mathbb{R}^d$	$\exp\left(\frac{-\ x-y\ _2^2}{2\sigma^2}\right)$	$\sigma > 0$	✓	✓
Laplacian kernel	$\mathbb{R}^d \times \mathbb{R}^d$	$\exp\left(\frac{-\ x-y\ _1}{\sigma}\right)$	$\sigma > 0$	✓	✓
polynomial kernel	$\mathbb{R}^d \times \mathbb{R}^d$	$(x^T y + c)^p$	$c \geq 0, p \in \mathbb{N}^+$	✗	✗

Table 2.1: Various characterizations of three archetypal kernels. In columns U and C we indicate, whether the kernel is universal or characteristic.

In other words, with finite linear combinations of universal kernel functions any bounded continuous function on a compact metric space \mathbb{X} can be uniformly approximated arbitrarily well. It is well-known that the Gaussian kernel and the Laplacian kernel are universal restricted to any compact subset of \mathbb{R}^d (Muandet et al., 2017).

2.5.2 The Representer Theorem

Kernel methods can be used to model nonlinear phenomena in supervised learning tasks, therefore we often need to solve optimization problems over an infinite dimensional RKHS. Though it sounds computationally demanding, the representer theorem makes the RKHS attractive in many cases (Schölkopf et al., 2001).

Theorem 2.5.3. (*representer theorem*) *Given a set of elements $\{(x_i, y_i)\}_{i=1}^n$ in $(\mathbb{X} \times \mathbb{R})^n$ and a positive definite kernel $k(\cdot, \cdot)$, an associated RKHS \mathcal{H} with a norm $\|\cdot\|_{\mathcal{H}}$ induced by $\langle \cdot, \cdot \rangle_{\mathcal{H}}$, then, for any strictly monotonically increasing regularizer, $\kappa : [0, \infty) \rightarrow [0, \infty)$, and arbitrary loss function $L : (\mathbb{X} \times \mathbb{R}^2)^n \rightarrow \mathbb{R} \cup \{\infty\}$ each minimizer*

$$\hat{f} \in \arg \min_{f \in \mathcal{H}} L((x_1, y_1, f(x_1)), \dots, (x_n, y_n, f(x_n))) + \kappa(\|f\|_{\mathcal{H}}) \quad (2.42)$$

admits the following representation for some $\beta \in \mathbb{R}^n$:

$$\hat{f}(x) = \sum_{i=1}^n \beta_i k(x, x_i). \quad (2.43)$$

Theorem 2.5.3 is extremely powerful. It enables us to solve an optimization problem over an infinite dimensional Hilbert space. It is proved that the the solution of (2.42) admits a finite dimensional form in the linear space spanned by the features of the given (input) elements $\{x_i\}_{i=1}^n$. There are several other variants of the representer theorem, e.g., one can prove that for a differential/monotone regularizer there exists a minimizer admitting a finite dimensional representation (Argyriou et al., 2009). This theorem can be used to develop kernelized versions of linear methods in a high (possibly infinite) dimensional space without suffering from the “curse of dimensionality”.

2.5.3 Kernel Mean Embeddings

An important intuition behind the kernel function is the feature representation. Function $x \rightarrow k(\cdot, x)$ maps the inputs to a possibly higher dimensional RKHS admitting a neat geometrical structure. If $(\mathbb{X}, \mathcal{X})$ is a measurable space, then we can extend the feature map to the set of distributions on \mathbb{X} . This is the main idea of KMEs.

Definition 2.5.4. *Let $(\mathbb{X}, \mathcal{X})$ be a measurable space and let $M_+(\mathbb{X})$ denote the space of probability measures on $(\mathbb{X}, \mathcal{X})$. The kernel mean embeddings of probability measures into an RKHS \mathcal{H} endowed with a reproducing kernel $k : \mathbb{X} \times \mathbb{X} \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$ is defined by*

$$\begin{aligned} \mu &: M_+(\mathbb{X}) \rightarrow \mathcal{H}, \\ Q &\mapsto \int k(\cdot, x) dQ(x), \end{aligned} \tag{2.44}$$

where the integral is a Bochner integral.

For the sake of completeness we included an introductory material about Bochner integrals in Appendix C. [Smola et al. \(2007\)](#) characterized KMEs by:

Proposition 2.5.4. *Let X be a random element in $(\mathbb{X}, \mathcal{X})$ with distribution Q and $k : \mathbb{X} \times \mathbb{X} \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$ be a kernel. If $\mathbb{E}[\sqrt{k(X, X)}] < \infty$, then $\mu_Q \doteq \mu(Q) \in \mathcal{H}$ and*

$$\mathbb{E}[f(X)] = \langle f, \mu_Q \rangle_{\mathcal{H}} \text{ for all } f \in \mathcal{H}. \tag{2.45}$$

Proposition 2.5.4 is the consequence of the Riesz representation theorem. A kernel is called characteristic if the corresponding KME is injective. In this case the embedded element captures all information about the distribution, i.e., for $P, Q \in M_+(\mathbb{X})$, $\|\mu_P - \mu_Q\|_{\mathcal{H}} = 0$ if and only if $P = Q$. Thus, KMEs induce a metric on $M_+(\mathbb{X})$. [Gretton et al. \(2012\)](#) proved that if \mathbb{X} is a compact metric space and k is a universal kernel on \mathbb{X} , then k is also characteristic. Therefore the Gaussian kernel and the Laplacian kernels are characteristic on compact subsets of \mathbb{R}^d . KMEs have nice properties even if the kernel is not characteristic, e.g., for a polynomial kernel with degree p it holds that $\|\mu_P - \mu_Q\|_{\mathcal{H}} = 0$ if and only if the first d moments of P and Q are the same ([Muandet et al., 2017](#)).

Several fundamental operations can be performed in \mathcal{H} instead of dealing with distributions. Conditional distributions can be embedded and the conditional expected value can be expressed via an inner product similarly to Proposition 2.5.4. Consequently a wide range of tools, e.g., sum, product and Bayes rules, can be performed in \mathcal{H} ([Fukumizu et al., 2013](#); [Song et al., 2013, 2009](#)).

The underlying probability distribution of the sample is typically unknown, therefore, an estimator for the KME of a distribution is often sought. An important tool to prove the consistency of empirical estimators is the strong law of large numbers (SLLN) for random elements taking values in a separable Hilbert space ([Taylor, 1978](#)).

Theorem 2.5.5. *Let $(X_n)_{n \in \mathbb{N}^+}$ be a sequence of independent random elements taking values in a separable Hilbert space \mathcal{H} . If*

$$\sum_{n=1}^{\infty} \frac{D^2[X_n]}{n^2} < \infty \quad (2.46)$$

for $D^2[X] \doteq \mathbb{E}[\|X - \mathbb{E}[X]\|_{\mathcal{H}}^2]$, then

$$\left\| \frac{1}{n} \sum_{k=1}^n (X_k - \mathbb{E}[X_k]) \right\|_{\mathcal{H}} \xrightarrow{a.s.} 0 \quad \text{as } n \rightarrow \infty. \quad (2.47)$$

2.5.4 Conditional Kernel Mean Embeddings

Let (X, Y) be a random pair in $\mathbb{X} \times \mathbb{Y}$ with joint distribution $Q_{X,Y}$ and marginals Q_X and Q_Y . In addition, let $\ell : \mathbb{Y} \times \mathbb{Y} \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$ be a kernel function. If the KME of Q_Y exists, then for a given σ -algebra one can take the conditional expectation of $\ell(\cdot, Y)$. The CKME of Y given X in RKHS \mathcal{G} is a $\sigma(X)$ -measurable random element of \mathcal{G} defined by

$$\mu_{Y|X} \doteq \mathbb{E}[\ell(\cdot, Y) | X]. \quad (2.48)$$

More details about conditional expectations in a Banach space are included in Appendix C. This appendix is based on the seminal works of [Pisier \(2016\)](#) and [Hytönen et al. \(2016\)](#).

It is known that the conditional expectation is well-defined if $\mathbb{E}[\ell(\cdot, Y)]$ exists, therefore let us assume that $\mathbb{E}[\sqrt{\ell(Y, Y)}] < \infty$. Then, by ([Kallenberg, 2002](#), Lemma 1.13) there exists a measurable map $\mu^* : \mathbb{X} \rightarrow \mathcal{G}$ such that $\mu_{Y|X} = \mu^*(X)$ (a.s.). We use the pointwise form of μ^* defined Q_X -a.s. by $\mu^*(x) = \mathbb{E}[\ell(\cdot, Y) | X = x]$. This function plays a key role for CKMEs. We call μ^* the conditional kernel mean map. By equation (C.12)

$$\begin{aligned} \langle \mu_{Y|X}, g \rangle_{\mathcal{G}} &= \langle \mu^*(X), g \rangle_{\mathcal{G}} = \langle \mathbb{E}[\ell(\cdot, Y) | X], g \rangle_{\mathcal{G}} \\ &= \mathbb{E}[\langle \ell(\cdot, Y), g \rangle_{\mathcal{G}} | X] = \mathbb{E}[g(Y) | X] \end{aligned} \quad (2.49)$$

holds for all $g \in \mathcal{G}$. In addition by the law of total expectation we have $\mathbb{E}[\mu_{Y|X}] = \mu_Y$.

Recovering the regression function Let us consider the special case of $\mathbb{X} \doteq \mathbb{R}^d$, $\mathbb{Y} \doteq \mathbb{R}$ and $\ell(y_1, y_2) = y_1 \cdot y_2$. Then, the RKHS generated by ℓ can be identified with \mathbb{R} by mapping $\ell(y, a) = y \cdot a$ to a and the conditional kernel mean map takes the form of $\mu^*(X) = \mathbb{E}[Y \cdot y | X]$. By linearity, μ^* is equivalent to the regression function, i.e., $\mu^*(X)$ is the linear function determined by $\mathbb{E}[Y|X]$.

In Chapter 5 our main finding is a strongly L_2 -consistent estimator for the conditional kernel mean map μ^* , that is, we develop an estimator $(\mu_n)_{n \in \mathbb{N}^+}$ such that

$$\int \|\mu_n(x) - \mu(x)\|_{\mathcal{G}}^2 dQ_X(x) \xrightarrow{a.s.} 0 \quad (2.50)$$

holds under mild statistical assumption. We generalize the theorem of Stone (1977) to prove the convergence of a Hilbert space valued recursive local averaging estimator. If we use a characteristic kernel on \mathbb{Y} , then our point estimator provides a consistent solution for conditional distribution estimation under mild structural conditions.

2.5.5 Vector-Valued Reproducing Kernel Hilbert Spaces

RKHSs can be generalized for vector-valued functions (Micchelli and Pontil, 2005; Grünewälder et al., 2012), which are used for ML problems that involve functional output variables. They also offer a practical tool to estimate CKMEs.

Definition 2.5.5. *Let \mathcal{H} be a Hilbert space of $\mathbb{X} \rightarrow \mathcal{G}$ type functions with inner product $\langle \cdot, \cdot \rangle_{\mathcal{H}}$, where \mathcal{G} is a Hilbert space. \mathcal{H} is a vector-valued RKHS if for all $x \in \mathbb{X}$ and $g \in \mathcal{G}$ the linear functional (on \mathcal{H}) $h \mapsto \langle g, h(x) \rangle_{\mathcal{G}}$ is bounded.*

Then by the Riesz representation theorem, for all $(g, x) \in \mathcal{G} \times \mathbb{X}$ there exists a unique $\tilde{h} \in \mathcal{H}$ for which $\langle g, h(x) \rangle_{\mathcal{G}} = \langle \tilde{h}, h \rangle_{\mathcal{H}}$. Let Γ_x be a $\mathcal{G} \rightarrow \mathcal{H}$ operator defined as $\Gamma_x g = \tilde{h}$. The notation is justified because Γ_x is linear. Further, let $\mathcal{L}(\mathcal{G})$ denote the set of bounded linear operators on \mathcal{G} and let $\Gamma : \mathbb{X} \times \mathbb{X} \rightarrow \mathcal{L}(\mathcal{G})$ be defined as $\Gamma(x_1, x_2)g \doteq (\Gamma_{x_2}g)(x_1) \in \mathcal{G}$. Let us recall the properties that follow (Micchelli and Pontil, 2005, Proposition 2.1):

Proposition 2.5.6. *Operator Γ satisfies for all $x_1, x_2 \in \mathbb{X}$:*

1. $\forall g_1, g_2 \in \mathcal{G} : \langle g_1, \Gamma(x_1, x_2)g_2 \rangle_{\mathcal{G}} = \langle \Gamma_{x_1}g_1, \Gamma_{x_2}g_2 \rangle_{\mathcal{H}}$.
2. $\Gamma(x_1, x_2) \in \mathcal{L}(\mathcal{G})$, $\Gamma(x_1, x_2) = \Gamma^*(x_2, x_1)$, where $\Gamma^*(x_2, x_1)$ is the adjoint of $\Gamma(x_2, x_1)$.
3. For all $n \in \mathbb{N}^+$, $\{(x_i)\}_{i=1}^n \subseteq \mathbb{X}$ and $\{(g_j)\}_{j=1}^n \subseteq \mathcal{G}$, we have

$$\sum_{i,j=1}^n \langle g_i, \Gamma(x_i, x_j)g_j \rangle_{\mathcal{G}} \geq 0. \quad (2.51)$$

If 1–3. hold, we call Γ a vector-valued reproducing kernel. Similarly to the classical Moore-Aronszjan theorem, for any vector-valued kernel Γ , there uniquely exists (up to isometry) a vector-valued RKHS \mathcal{H} , such that Γ is a vector-valued reproducing kernel in \mathcal{H} (Micchelli and Pontil, 2005, Theorem 2.1).

2.5.6 Empirical Estimates of Conditional Kernel Mean Maps

In statistical learning, the underlying distributions are unknown. Therefore, the conditional kernel mean map needs to be estimated. Under the typical i.i.d. assumption, the empirical estimation of conditional kernel mean map $\mu^* : \mathbb{X} \rightarrow \mathcal{G}$ is challenging in general, because its dependence on $x \in \mathbb{X}$ can be arbitrary (e.g., nonlinear). The most widely used approach defines an estimator $\hat{\mu}$ as a regularized empirical risk minimizer in

a vector-valued RKHS (Grünewälder et al., 2012), which is equivalent to the originally proposed operator estimates of Song et al. (2009).

By (2.49) it is intuitive to estimate μ^* with a minimizer of the following objective over some space \mathcal{H} (Grünewälder et al., 2012, Equation 5):

$$\mathcal{E}(\mu) = \sup_{\|g\|_{\mathcal{G}} \leq 1} \mathbb{E} \left[\left| \mathbb{E}[g(Y) | X] - \langle g, \mu(X) \rangle_{\mathcal{G}} \right|^2 \right]. \quad (2.52)$$

Grünewälder et al. (2012) have introduced a surrogate loss by

$$\mathcal{E}_s(\mu) \doteq \mathbb{E} \left[\|\ell(\cdot, Y) - \mu(X)\|_{\mathcal{G}}^2 \right], \quad (2.53)$$

because $\mathbb{E}[g(Y) | X]$ is not observable. They showed that $\mathcal{E}(\mu) \leq \mathcal{E}_s(\mu)$ for all $\mu \in L_2(\mathbb{X}, Q_X; \mathcal{G})$, cf. Definition C.1.2, and proved that under mild statistical conditions the minimizer of \mathcal{E} Q_X -a.s. is equal to the minimizer of \mathcal{E}_s , so the surrogate version can be used. It is easy to empirically estimate \mathcal{E}_s by

$$\widehat{\mathcal{E}}_s(\mu) \doteq \frac{1}{n} \sum_{i=1}^n \|\ell(\cdot, Y_i) - \mu(X_i)\|_{\mathcal{G}}^2. \quad (2.54)$$

To make the problem tractable, a regularization term is added and (2.54) is minimized over a vector-valued RKHS, \mathcal{H} . One can choose the vector-valued RKHS arbitrarily. An intuitive approach is to use the space induced by kernel $\Gamma(x_1, x_2) \doteq k(x_1, x_2)\mathbf{Id}_{\mathcal{G}}$, where $x_1, x_2 \in \mathbb{X}$, k is a scalar-valued reproducing kernel and $\mathbf{Id}_{\mathcal{G}}$ is the identity map on \mathcal{G} . We will only focus on this kernel, as it leads to the same estimator as the one originally proposed by Song et al. (2009). The regularization term helps to prevent overfitting and to ensure well-posedness, hence, a conditional kernel mean map estimator is defined as

$$\widehat{\mu}_{n,\lambda} \doteq \arg \min_{\mu \in \mathcal{H}} \widehat{\mathcal{E}}_{\lambda}(\mu) \quad (2.55)$$

where $\widehat{\mathcal{E}}_{\lambda}(\mu) \doteq \left[\widehat{\mathcal{E}}_s(\mu) + \lambda/n \|\mu\|_{\mathcal{H}}^2 \right]$. The explicit form of $\widehat{\mu}$ is given by (Micchelli and Pontil, 2005, Theorem 4.1), cf. representer theorem:

Theorem 2.5.7. *If $\widehat{\mu}_{n,\lambda}$ minimizes \mathcal{E}_{λ} in \mathcal{H} , then it is unique and admits the form of $\widehat{\mu}_{n,\lambda} = \sum_{i=1}^n \Gamma_{X_i} c_i$, where $c_i \in \mathcal{G}$ are the unique solutions of*

$$\sum_{j=1}^n \left(\Gamma(X_i, X_j) + \lambda \mathbb{I}(i=j) \mathbf{Id}_{\mathcal{G}} \right) c_j = \ell(\cdot, Y_i) \quad \text{for } i \in [n].$$

By Theorem 2.5.7 we have: $c_i = \sum_{j=1}^n W_{i,j} \ell(\cdot, Y_j)$ for $i \in [n]$, with $W = (K + \lambda \mathbf{I})^{-1}$, where \mathbf{I} is the identity matrix and K is the Gram matrix of scalar-valued kernel k .

2.5.7 Hilbert-Schmidt Independence Criterion

In Chapter 7 we consider the problem of independence testing. Recall that two variables X and Y are independent of each other if $\sigma(X)$ and $\sigma(Y)$ are independent or equivalently if the joint distribution of (X, Y) factorizes to the product of marginals. We use a kernel based dependence measure, the Hilbert–Schmidt independence criterion (HSIC), to quantify the dependence between random variables.

Let (X, Y) be a random pair in $\mathbb{X} \times \mathbb{Y}$ with distribution $Q_{X,Y}$, where \mathbb{X} and \mathbb{Y} are arbitrary sets. Let k and ℓ be kernels on $\mathbb{X} \times \mathbb{X}$ and $\mathbb{Y} \times \mathbb{Y}$ respectively. It is known that if k and ℓ are positive definite, then the (tensor) product kernel

$$k \otimes \ell : (\mathbb{X} \times \mathbb{Y})^2 \rightarrow \mathbb{R} \\ ((x_1, x_2), (y_1, y_2)) \mapsto k(x_1, x_2) \cdot \ell(y_1, y_2) \quad (2.56)$$

is also positive definite. The (centered) cross-covariance operator is defined as

$$\mathbf{C}_{X,Y} \doteq \mathbb{E} \left[k \otimes \ell \left((\cdot, \cdot), (X, Y) \right) \right] - \mathbb{E}[k(\cdot, X)] \otimes \mathbb{E}[\ell(\cdot, Y)] \\ = \mu(Q_{X,Y}) - \mu(Q_X \otimes Q_Y). \quad (2.57)$$

Note that one can recover the standard cross-covariance matrix by applying linear kernels $k(x, y) = \ell(x, y) = x^T \cdot y$ for $x, y \in \mathbb{R}^d$ and $d \in \mathbb{N}^+$.

Let \mathcal{H}_k and \mathcal{H}_ℓ be the RKHSs of k and ℓ . The definition of Hilbert–Schmidt independence criterion ([Gretton et al., 2008](#)) is given by

$$\text{HSIC}(Q_{X,Y}, \mathcal{H}_k, \mathcal{H}_\ell) \doteq \|\mathbf{C}_{X,Y}\|_\otimes^2, \quad (2.58)$$

where $\|\cdot\|_\otimes$ denotes the norm of the product RKHS. For fixed kernel functions k and ℓ , we are going to simplify the notation to $\text{HSIC}(X, Y) \doteq \text{HSIC}(Q_{X,Y}, \mathcal{H}_k, \mathcal{H}_\ell)$. Additionally, by the reproducing property we obtain a more intuitive form:

$$\text{HSIC}(X, Y) = \mathbb{E}[k(X, X')\ell(Y, Y')] + \mathbb{E}[k(X, X')]\mathbb{E}[\ell(Y, Y')] \\ - 2\mathbb{E}[k(X, X')\ell(Y, Y'')], \quad (2.59)$$

where (X, Y) , (X', Y') and (X'', Y'') are i.i.d. copies from $Q_{X,Y}$. HSIC is called characteristic when $\text{HSIC}(X, Y) = 0$ if and only if X and Y are independent. Clearly, by (2.57) HSIC is characteristic if $k \otimes \ell$ is characteristic.

Given an i.i.d. sample $\mathcal{D} = \{(X_i, Y_i)_{i=1}^n\}$ from $Q_{X,Y}$, formula (2.59) motivates the empirical estimator of which consistency is proved by [Pfister et al. \(2018\)](#):

$$\text{HSIC}_n(\mathcal{D}) \doteq \frac{1}{n^2} \sum_{(i,j) \in [n]^2} k(X_i, X_j)\ell(Y_i, Y_j) + \frac{1}{n^4} \sum_{(i,j,r,s) \in [n]^4} k(X_i, X_j)\ell(Y_r, Y_s) \\ - \frac{2}{n^3} \sum_{(i,j,s) \in [n]^3} k(X_i, X_j)\ell(Y_i, Y_s). \quad (2.60)$$

2.6 Independence Tests for Linear Systems

In Chapter 7 we construct novel independence tests based on the method of [Pfister et al. \(2018\)](#) and [Rindt et al. \(2021\)](#), for synchronous, stochastic linear systems ([Ljung, 1999](#); [Söderström and Stoica, 1989](#)). Let \mathbb{Z} denote the set of integers. We consider two scalar (discrete-time, time-invariant) stochastic linear systems with general dynamics:

$$\begin{aligned} Y_t &= G_1(q^{-1}; \theta^*)U_t + H_1(q^{-1}; \theta^*)E_t, \\ Z_t &= G_2(q^{-1}; \varphi^*)V_t + H_2(q^{-1}; \varphi^*)N_t, \end{aligned} \tag{2.61}$$

for $t \in \mathbb{Z}$, where U_t and V_t are (exogenous) inputs; Y_t and Z_t are (observable) outputs; q^{-1} is the backshift operator defined by $q^{-1}X_t \doteq X_{t-1}$ for $t \in \mathbb{Z}$ for any time series (X_t) ; E_t and N_t are possibly dependent noise processes; G_1, H_1 , and G_2, H_2 are rational transfer functions on finite dimensional parameter spaces Θ and Φ , respectively. The unknown true parameters are θ^* and φ^* . We assume that H_1 and H_2 are invertible for all parameters $\theta \in \Theta$ and $\varphi \in \Phi$ and for simplicity the systems are initialized in zero, i.e., $Y_t = Z_t = U_t = V_t = E_t = N_t = 0$, for all $t \leq 0$. Our main structural assumption is that the systems are driven synchronously, i.e., the innovations $\{(E_t, N_t)\}_{t=1}^\infty$ are i.i.d. from the distribution of (E, N) and the inputs are independent of the driving noises. Autoregressive moving average systems with exogeneous inputs (ARMAX), e.g., can satisfy these conditions.

We present a new test for the null hypothesis that (Y_t) and (Z_t) are independent. For simplicity, we treat the inputs $(U_t), (V_t)$ as deterministic sequences. We provide finite sample guarantees for the confidence level. For this, we observe that if (Y_t) and (Z_t) are driven by a jointly i.i.d. noise (E, N) , with joint distribution $Q_{E,N}$ and marginals Q_E and Q_N , respectively, then the independence of (E_t) and (N_t) is equivalent to the conditional independence of (Y_t) and (Z_t) w.r.t. the inputs. Therefore, it is sufficient to test

$$H_0 : Q_{E,N} = Q_E \otimes Q_N \text{ vs } H_1 : Q_{E,N} \neq Q_E \otimes Q_N. \tag{2.62}$$

The main challenge in this problem is that the “true” parameters, θ^* and φ^* , are unknown, henceforth the innovations are not observable. In Chapter 7 we develop rank tests that use non-asymptotic confidence regions with HSIC estimates to obtain finite sample guarantees for the (rational, user-chosen) significance level. Finally, we prove that the presented hypothesis tests are consistent under mild statistical assumptions.

Chapter 3

Heavy-Tailed Mean Estimation

In this chapter we propose a new algorithm, the resampled median-of-means (RMM) method, to build non-asymptotically exact confidence intervals for the mean of a symmetric distribution based on an i.i.d. sample. The method combines resampling with MoM estimates to ensure optimal shrinkage rates for the sizes of the confidence intervals under mild, heavy-tailed moment conditions. The scheme is completely data-driven: the construction does not need any hyperparameters, yet it manages to build exact confidence regions which shrink at the optimal rate. We also show how to generalize the approach to higher dimensions and prove dimension-free, subgaussian PAC bounds for the exclusion probabilities of false candidates. We demonstrate the method and its properties for heavy-tailed distributions with numerical experiments.

The results of this chapter were published in (Tamás et al., 2024) and presented at the 27th Conference on Artificial Intelligence and Statistics, Valencia, Spain. The method was implemented in Python by my co-author and colleague, Szabolcs Szentpéteri. He carried out the numerical experiments and created the illustrations of this chapter including Figure 3.1, Figure 3.2, Figure A.1, Figure A.2 and Table A.1. The one-sided version of the RMM method to build upper confidence bounds and its application to stochastic multi-armed bandits have been developed by us in (Tamás et al., 2025).

3.1 Motivation

In statistical learning the accuracy-confidence trade-off is a key phenomenon (Györfi et al., 2002; Shalev-Shwartz and Ben-David, 2014; Vapnik, 1998). Classical methods offer a variety of PAC type bounds for the mean. The celebrated Hoeffding’s inequality provides exponential bounds for the mean of bounded variables (Hoeffding, 1963). Under the finite variance assumption tighter inequalities are proved in (Bennett, 1962; Bernstein, 1937). Nevertheless, we need to know the variance to construct confidence intervals based on these results. For bounded variables recently an adaptive martingale approach was developed in (Waudby-Smith and Ramdas, 2024) to derive time uniform concentration inequalities, which empirically outperform the classical methods. For the mean of heavy-

tailed distributions neat PAC bounds are presented in (Catoni, 2012; Lugosi and Mendelson, 2019a), however, these inequalities suffer from similar limitations as the bounds of (Bennett, 1962; Bernstein, 1937) assuming a priori knowledge of some hyperparameters. In this chapter, motivated by finite sample system identification methods, such as the sign-perturbed sums (SPS) method (Csáji et al., 2014; Szentpéteri and Csáji, 2023) and the leave-out sign-dominant correlation regions (Campi and Weyer, 2005), we introduce the RMM method for constructing exact confidence intervals for the mean of a symmetric variable based on an i.i.d. sample without making any other a priori assumption. We prove that the RMM method builds confidence intervals with optimal shrinkage rate w.r.t. the confidence parameter without using moment information. The main advantage of RMM w.r.t. the original SPS method lies in its robustness, i.e., we prove (subgaussian) PAC bounds for the RMM method under heavy-tailed distributional assumptions.

3.2 Exploiting Symmetry

Let Y be a random variable with a symmetric distribution Q_Y . We construct confidence intervals for the median of Q_Y with optimal shrinkage rate, cf. (2.23), based on a non-asymptotically exact hypothesis test, hence for a given $\theta \in \mathbb{R}$ let us consider

$$H_0 : \mu = \theta \quad \text{vs} \quad H_1 : \mu \neq \theta \tag{3.1}$$

under the assumptions that follow:

A1. Y_1, \dots, Y_n are i.i.d. with mutual distribution Q_Y .

A2. Q_Y is symmetric about μ .

We emphasise that the hypothesis test that we present is exact under these two very mild conditions. Assumption A1 can be weakened for some of our results. The key property that we need for proving the validity of the presented method is that each variable possesses the same pivot of symmetry. To quantify the type II error probabilities or the statistical power of the presented test we work with an additional assumption on the moment of the observed variables:

A3. $\mathbb{E}[|Y - \mathbb{E}[Y]|^{1+a}] = M < \infty$ for an $a \in (0, 1]$.

We also quantify the rate of shrinkage of the corresponding confidence regions under A1-A3. One can observe that from A2 and A3 it follows that $\mathbb{E}[Y] = \mu$ and in particular for $a = 1$ assumption A3 is equivalent to requiring $\sigma^2 < \infty$. We emphasise that the presented test does not use the knowledge of constants a and M , yet we can prove the optimality of the sizes of the corresponding confidence intervals that we build. This is one of the main advantages of our scheme compared to the methods that use hyperparameters.

Let δ be the desired (rational) significance level. We note that irrational significance levels can be achieved with additional randomization. Let us find integers r and m such

that $\delta = r/m$. In this chapter we propose a new resampling method to test the null hypothesis. Let $Y(\theta) \doteq \alpha(Y - \theta) + \theta$ be a parameterized random variable defined with a Rademacher variable α independent of Y . Clearly $\mathbb{E}[Y(\theta)] = \theta$ and $Y(\theta)$ is symmetric about θ . By Jensen's inequality we have

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbb{E}[|Y(\theta) - \mathbb{E}[Y(\theta)]|^{1+a}] &= \mathbb{E}[|\alpha|^{1+a}|Y - \theta|^{1+a}] \\ &\leq \mathbb{E}\left[\left(\frac{2|Y - \mu| + 2|\mu - \theta|}{2}\right)^{1+a}\right] \leq \mathbb{E}\left[\frac{1}{2}(2|Y - \mu|)^{1+a} + \frac{1}{2}(2|\mu - \theta|)^{1+a}\right] \\ &= 2^a\left(\mathbb{E}[|Y - \mu|^{1+a}] + d(\theta)^{1+a}\right) \leq 2(M + d(\theta)^{1+a}), \end{aligned} \quad (3.2)$$

where $d(\theta) \doteq |\theta - \mu|$. In particular for $a = 1$ we can compute the exact variance by

$$D^2[Y(\theta)] = \mathbb{E}[\alpha^2(Y - \theta)^2] = \mathbb{E}[(Y - \mu)^2] + \mathbb{E}[(\mu - \theta)^2] = \sigma^2 + d(\theta)^2. \quad (3.3)$$

For notational simplicity let $W \doteq Y - \mu$ be the centered version of Y and $\mathcal{W}_0 \doteq \{W_i\}_{i=1}^n$, where $W_i = Y_i - \mu$ for $i \in [n]$. Keep in mind, however, that $\{W_i\}_{i=1}^n$ are not observed. Note that $Y = \mu + W$ and $Y(\mu) = \mu + \alpha W$, where α is a Rademacher variable, have the same distribution, because W is symmetric about zero. Moreover, one can prove that Y and $Y(\mu)$ are conditionally i.i.d. given $|W|$, hence they are also exchangeable (Csáji et al., 2014). On the other hand if $\theta \neq \mu$, then the distribution of Y differs from the distribution of $Y(\theta)$, e.g., $Y(\theta)$ is symmetric about θ , whereas Y is symmetric about μ . We aim to detect this difference. For our test we generate alternative samples using H_0 and compare the new (resampled) datasets to the original one, i.e., for $i \in [n]$ and $j \in [m - 1]$ let $\{\alpha_{i,j}\}$ be i.i.d. random signs (Rademacher variables), for $j \in [m - 1]$ let

$$\mathcal{D}_j(\theta) \doteq \{\alpha_{1,j}(Y_1 - \theta) + \theta, \dots, \alpha_{n,j}(Y_n - \theta) + \theta\} \quad (3.4)$$

be parameter-dependent alternative samples and for $\theta \in \mathbb{R}$ let $\mathcal{D}_0(\theta) \doteq \mathcal{D}_0$. It is easy to see that $\mathcal{D}_j(\theta)$ is an i.i.d. sample from the distribution of $Y(\theta)$ for $j \neq 0$. We decide about H_0 by comparing $\mathcal{D}_0(\theta)$ to $\mathcal{D}_j(\theta)$ for $j \in [m - 1]$ with a ranking function.

Definition 3.2.1 (ranking function). *Let \mathbb{A} be a set, a function $\psi : \mathbb{A}^m \rightarrow [m]$ is called a ranking function if for all $(a_1, \dots, a_m) \in \mathbb{A}^m$ it satisfies P1 and P2.*

P1. *For all permutation τ on set $\{2, \dots, m\}$, we have*

$$\psi(a_1, a_2, \dots, a_m) = \psi(a_1, a_{\tau(2)}, \dots, a_{\tau(m)}),$$

that is, function ψ is invariant w.r.t. reordering the last $m - 1$ terms of its arguments.

P2. *For all $i, j \in [m]$, if $a_i \neq a_j$, then we have*

$$\psi(a_i, \{a_k\}_{k \neq i}) \neq \psi(a_j, \{a_k\}_{k \neq j}),$$

where the simplified notation is justified by P1.

The (possibly random) value of a ranking function is called the rank. If $\mathcal{D}_0(\theta)$ differs significantly from $\mathcal{D}_j(\theta)$, then we reject H_0 , otherwise we accept the null hypothesis. The comparison is carried out based on the rank. The main observation about the rank is given by the lemma that follows (Csáji and Tamás, 2019, Lemma 1):

Lemma 3.2.1. *Let ξ_1, \dots, ξ_m be almost surely pairwise different exchangeable random elements in a measurable space and let ψ be a ranking function, then $\psi(\xi_1, \dots, \xi_m)$ is uniformly distributed on $[m]$.*

The original sample and the alternative samples are random vectors in \mathbb{R}^n . We can observe that $\mathcal{D}_0(\theta)$ can be identical to $\mathcal{D}_j(\theta)$ for $j \in [m-1]$, e.g., if every sign $\{\alpha_{i,j}\}_{i=1}^n$ equals to +1. This poses a technical challenge in ranking. To resolve this problem we use a tiebreaking permutation, cf. (Csáji et al., 2014). Let π be a random permutation on $[m-1]_0$ generated uniformly from the permutation group on $[m-1]_0$, independently from \mathcal{D}_0 and $\{\alpha_{i,j}\}$. A.s. pairwise different extended samples are defined as $\mathcal{D}_j^\pi(\theta) \doteq (\mathcal{D}_j(\theta), \pi(j))$ for $j = 0, \dots, m-1$. It is easy to see that $\mathcal{D}_0^\pi(\mu), \dots, \mathcal{D}_{m-1}^\pi(\mu)$ are exchangeable, hence we obtain an exact hypothesis test if we reject H_0 if and only if

$$\psi(\mathcal{D}_0^\pi(\theta), \dots, \mathcal{D}_{m-1}^\pi(\theta)) > m - r. \quad (3.5)$$

Theorem 3.2.2. *For any ranking function ψ if A1 and A2 hold, then we have*

$$\mathbb{P}\left(\psi\left(\mathcal{D}_0^\pi(\mu), \dots, \mathcal{D}_{m-1}^\pi(\mu)\right) > m - r\right) = \frac{r}{m}. \quad (3.6)$$

We can observe that (3.6) provides the exact probability of type I error for every sample size $n \in \mathbb{N}^+$ and for every symmetric distribution Q_Y . Our conditions on ψ are also very mild. In fact at this point we allow degenerate rankings, e.g., rankings that only depend on the tiebreaking permutation. We would like to avoid these “pathological” choices and apply rankings that admit finite sample PAC bounds.

One of our main ideas is to compare the empirical estimates of the distances between parameter θ and the MoM estimate computed from each sample. If $\theta = \mu$, then each estimate has the same distribution, otherwise $\hat{\mu}(\mathcal{D}_0)$ is “farther” from θ than $\hat{\mu}(\mathcal{D}_j(\theta))$ with high probability for $j \in [m-1]$. Let us define reference variable functions as

$$S_j(\theta) \doteq |\hat{\mu}(\mathcal{D}_j(\theta)) - \theta| \quad \text{for } j = 0, \dots, m-1. \quad (3.7)$$

Because of the reasoning above $S_0(\theta)$ should be greater than $S_j(\theta)$ for $j \in [m-1]$ for those $\theta \in \mathbb{R}$ that are “far” from μ . However, $S_0(\theta)$ and $S_j(\theta)$ have the same distribution if $\theta = \mu$ and are exchangeable. Finally, we define the ranking function by

$$\mathcal{R}(\theta) = \psi(\mathcal{D}_0^\pi(\theta), \dots, \mathcal{D}_{m-1}^\pi(\theta)) \doteq 1 + \sum_{i=1}^{m-1} \mathbb{I}\left(S_0(\theta) \succ_{\pi} S_i(\theta)\right), \quad (3.8)$$

Algorithm 1 RMM Hypothesis Test (for $\mu = \theta$)

Inputs: i.i.d. sample \mathcal{D}_0 , rational significance level δ ,
 tiebreaking permutation π on $[m-1]_0$

- 1: Choose integers $1 \leq r < m$ such that $\delta = r/m$.
- 2: Generate $n(m-1)$ independent Rademacher signs $\{\alpha_{i,j}\}$ for $(i,j) \in [n] \times [m-1]_0$.
- 3: Construct $m-1$ alternative datasets for $j \in [m-1]$:

$$\mathcal{D}_j(\theta) \doteq \{\alpha_{1,j}(Y_1 - \theta) + \theta, \dots, \alpha_{n,j}(Y_n - \theta) + \theta\}$$

and let $\mathcal{D}_j^\pi \doteq (\mathcal{D}_j(\theta), \pi(j))$ for $j \in [m-1]_0$.

- 4: Compute the reference variables

$$S_j(\theta) \doteq |\hat{\mu}(\mathcal{D}_j(\theta)) - \theta| \quad \text{for } j = 0, \dots, m-1.$$

- 5: Compute the rank $\mathcal{R}(\theta)$ according to (3.8).
 - 6: Reject H_0 if and only if $\mathcal{R}(\theta) > m-r$.
-

where \prec_π is defined as the standard $<$ ordering with tiebreaking (Csáji et al., 2014), i.e.,

$$S_j(\theta) \prec_\pi S_k(\theta) \iff S_j(\theta) < S_k(\theta) \text{ or } (S_j(\theta) = S_k(\theta) \text{ and } \pi(j) < \pi(k)) \quad (3.9)$$

We reject θ if and only if $\mathcal{R}(\theta) > m-r$. The rank test is summarized in Algorithm 1.

Theorem 3.2.3. *Assume A1 and A2, then the defined hypothesis test is exact, i.e., for every $1 \leq r < m$ and for every sample size $n \in \mathbb{N}^+$ we have*

$$\mathbb{P}(\mathcal{R}(\mu) > m-r) = \frac{r}{m}. \quad (3.10)$$

Proof. This is a direct consequence of Lemma 3.2.1, because $\mathcal{D}_0, \mathcal{D}_1(\mu), \dots, \mathcal{D}_{m-1}(\mu)$ are exchangeable (Csáji and Tamás, 2019). \square

We prove a non-asymptotic pointwise bound for the type II error probability of the presented test. One can control the power of the test by parameter k of the MoM estimator.

Theorem 3.2.4. *Assume A1, A2 and A3. Let $\varrho > 0$, $k = \lceil 8 \log(2(m-r+1)/\varrho) \rceil$, $1 \leq r < m$ be user-chosen integers and \mathcal{R} be defined by (3.8). If*

$$8 \left(\frac{24(M + d(\theta)^{1+a})^{1/a} \log\left(\frac{m-r+1}{\varrho}\right)}{n} \right)^{\frac{\alpha}{1+a}} < \frac{d(\theta)}{2}, \quad (3.11)$$

holds for $d(\theta) = |\theta - \mu|$, then we have

$$\mathbb{P}(\mathcal{R}(\theta) \leq m-r) \leq \varrho. \quad (3.12)$$

We can observe that for fixed ϱ , m , r and θ , (3.11) holds for n large enough. In addition, for a given sample size we can find the smallest ϱ for which (3.11) holds. In this case

the smallest upper bound of (3.12) will be exponential with respect to the sample size. Moreover, if equation (3.11) is satisfied for a parameter θ with $D = |\mu - \theta|$, then it also holds for every $\tilde{\theta} \in \mathbb{R}$ such that $|\mu - \tilde{\theta}| \geq D$.

Proof. Let us fix $\theta \neq \mu$, integers $r < m$ and use notation $\hat{\mu}^j \doteq \hat{\mu}(\mathcal{D}_j(\theta))$ for $j \in [m-1]_0$ and $d = d(\theta)$. First, we observe that if $|\hat{\mu}^0 - \mu| < d/2$, then $|\hat{\mu}^0 - \theta| \geq d/2$, thus

$$\mathbb{P}(\mathcal{R}(\theta) > m - r) \geq \mathbb{P}\left(|\hat{\mu}^0 - \mu| < d/2 \text{ and } |\hat{\mu}^j - \theta| < d/2 \text{ for } j = 1, \dots, m - r\right). \quad (3.13)$$

Let us define m ancillary events by

$$B_0 \doteq \{|\hat{\mu}^0 - \mu| < d/2\}, \quad B_j \doteq \{|\hat{\mu}^j - \theta| < d/2\} \text{ for } j = 1, \dots, m - 1. \quad (3.14)$$

Then, by the union bound we have

$$\mathbb{P}\left(\bigcup_{j=0}^{m-r} \bar{B}_j\right) \leq \sum_{j=0}^{m-r} \mathbb{P}(\bar{B}_j) = \mathbb{P}\left(|\hat{\mu}^0 - \mu| \geq d/2\right) + \sum_{j=1}^{m-r} \mathbb{P}\left(|\hat{\mu}^j - \theta| \geq d/2\right). \quad (3.15)$$

Because of (3.11) the first term can be bounded as

$$\mathbb{P}\left(|\hat{\mu}^0 - \mu| \geq d/2\right) \leq \mathbb{P}\left(|\hat{\mu}^0 - \mu| > 8\left(\frac{12M^{1/a} \log(1/\tilde{\varrho})}{n}\right)^{\frac{a}{1+a}}\right) \leq \tilde{\varrho}, \quad (3.16)$$

where $\varrho = (m - r + 1)\tilde{\varrho}$. The other terms can be bounded similarly by

$$\mathbb{P}\left(|\hat{\mu}^j - \theta| \geq d/2\right) \leq \mathbb{P}\left(|\hat{\mu}^j - \theta| > 8\left(\frac{24(M + d^{1+a})^{1/a} \log(1/\tilde{\varrho})}{n}\right)^{\frac{a}{1+a}}\right) \leq \tilde{\varrho}. \quad (3.17)$$

In conclusion, under (3.11) we have

$$\mathbb{P}(\mathcal{R}(\theta) \leq m - r) \leq (m - r + 1)\tilde{\varrho} = \varrho, \quad (3.18)$$

which proves the desired bound. \square

For $a = 1$, the constants of Theorem 3.2.4 can be strengthened to obtain Theorem 3.2.5.

Theorem 3.2.5. *Assume A1, A2 and A3. Let $\varrho > 0$, $k = \lceil 8 \log((m-r+1)/\varrho) \rceil$, $1 \leq r < m$ be user-chosen integers and \mathcal{R} be defined by (3.8). If*

$$4(\sigma^2 + d(\theta)^2) \frac{32 \log((m-r+1)/\varrho)}{n} \leq d(\theta)^2 \quad (3.19)$$

holds for $d(\theta) = |\mu - \theta|$, then we have

$$\mathbb{P}(\mathcal{R}(\theta) \leq m - r) \leq \varrho. \quad (3.20)$$

The proof of Theorem 3.2.5 is included in Appendix A.

3.3 Confidence Intervals

In this section we apply the presented hypothesis test to define the RMM method to construct confidence regions for μ . We include those parameters in the confidence set that are accepted by Algorithm 1, i.e., we let

$$\Theta_n \doteq \{ \theta : \mathcal{R}(\theta) \leq m - r \}. \quad (3.21)$$

Note that we do not need to generate random signs for each θ , the same set of signs can be used. Moreover, as we will see, Θ_n is a (possibly degenerate) interval and its endpoints can be explicitly computed. Because of Theorem 3.2.3 the following holds:

Corollary 3.3.1. *Assume A1 and A2, then Θ_n is an exact confidence region for μ , i.e.,*

$$\mathbb{P}(\mu \in \Theta_n) = 1 - \frac{r}{m}. \quad (3.22)$$

In addition, Theorem 3.2.4 implies that the inclusion probability for any $\theta \neq \mu$ goes to zero with an exponential rate as the sample size tends to infinity. In this section we seek to give a PAC bound on the size of Θ_n under the finite moment condition, A3. Let

$$\text{diam}(\Theta_n) \doteq \sup_{\theta_1, \theta_2} \{ |\theta_1 - \theta_2| : \theta_1, \theta_2 \in \Theta_n \} \quad (3.23)$$

be the diameter of Θ_n . It can be shown that $\text{diam}(\Theta_n)$ is an extended random variable, which can be infinite. We prove optimal PAC bounds on the shrinkage of $\text{diam}(\Theta_n)$.

Theorem 3.3.1. *Assume A1, A2 and A3. Let $m = 2$, $\delta > 0$, $k = \lceil 8 \log(20/\delta) \rceil$, \mathcal{R} be defined by (3.8) and $\Theta_n \doteq \{ \theta : \mathcal{R}(\theta) \leq 1 \}$, then for $n \geq k(k + 8 \log(k))$ we have*

$$\mathbb{P} \left(\text{diam}(\Theta_n) > 8 \left(\frac{12M^{1/a} \log(10/\delta)}{n} \right)^{\frac{a}{1+a}} \right) \leq \delta. \quad (3.24)$$

Proof. The proof consists of several parts. Let us fix $\varepsilon > 0$ and bound the probability

$$\mathbb{P}(\text{diam}(\Theta_n) > \varepsilon) \quad (3.25)$$

from above with two terms. We handle the case when there are too many or too few $+1$ in a random sign vector realization separately, because the probability of these events is exponentially small. W.l.o.g. we assume that $n = \tilde{n}k$. Let

$$Z_\ell \doteq \frac{1}{2} \sum_{i=(\ell-1)\tilde{n}+1}^{\ell\tilde{n}} (1 - \alpha_i) \quad \text{for } \ell = 1, \dots, k. \quad (3.26)$$

We can see that $\{Z_\ell\}_{\ell=1}^k$ are independent binomial variables with parameters \tilde{n} and $1/2$,

and expected value $\tilde{n}/2$. Let us define the events that follow

$$\begin{aligned} A_\ell &\doteq \left\{ |Z_\ell - \mathbb{E}Z_\ell| \leq \tilde{n}/4 \right\} \text{ for } \ell = 1, \dots, k, \\ A &\doteq \bigcap_{\ell=1}^k A_\ell = \left\{ \max_{1 \leq \ell \leq k} |Z_\ell - \mathbb{E}Z_\ell| \leq \tilde{n}/4 \right\}. \end{aligned} \quad (3.27)$$

Then, by the law of total probability

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbb{P}(\text{diam}(\Theta_n) > \varepsilon) &= \mathbb{P}(\text{diam}(\Theta_n) > \varepsilon | A) \mathbb{P}(A) + \mathbb{P}(\text{diam}(\Theta_n) > \varepsilon | \bar{A}) \mathbb{P}(\bar{A}) \\ &\leq \mathbb{P}(\{\text{diam}(\Theta_n) > \varepsilon\} \cap A) + \mathbb{P}(\bar{A}). \end{aligned} \quad (3.28)$$

We bound the second term with the union bound and Hoeffding's inequality as

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbb{P}\left(\max_{1 \leq \ell \leq k} |Z_\ell - \mathbb{E}Z_\ell| > \tilde{n}/4\right) &= \mathbb{P}\left(\bigcup_{\ell=1}^k \bar{A}_\ell\right) \leq \sum_{\ell=1}^k \mathbb{P}(\bar{A}_\ell) = k \mathbb{P}(\bar{A}_1) \\ &\leq k \mathbb{P}(|Z_1 - \mathbb{E}Z_1| > \tilde{n}/4) \leq 2k \exp\left(-\frac{n}{8k}\right). \end{aligned} \quad (3.29)$$

In the next step we show that if A occurs, then Θ_n is a bounded interval. Reference variable function $S_0(\theta) = |\hat{\mu}(\mathcal{D}_0) - \theta|$ is the absolute value function of a linear function with slope -1 . Let us define the sub-sample alternative lines as

$$S_1^{(\ell)}(\theta) \doteq \frac{1}{\tilde{n}} \sum_{i=(\ell-1)\tilde{n}}^{\ell\tilde{n}} \alpha_{i,1}(Y_i - \theta) \text{ for } \ell = 1, \dots, k. \quad (3.30)$$

Then, the alternative reference function equals to

$$\begin{aligned} S_1(\theta) &= |\hat{\mu}(\mathcal{D}_1(\theta)) - \theta| = \left| \text{med}\left(S_1^{(1)}(\theta) + \theta, \dots, S_1^{(k)}(\theta) + \theta\right) - \theta \right| \\ &= \left| \text{med}\left(S_1^{(1)}(\theta), \dots, S_1^{(k)}(\theta)\right) \right|, \end{aligned} \quad (3.31)$$

which is the median of linear functions with slopes strictly between -1 and $+1$. Without taking the absolute value, the median of linear functions have exactly one intersection with $\hat{\mu}(\mathcal{D}_0) - \theta$, i.e., equation

$$\hat{\mu}(\mathcal{D}_0) - \theta = \text{med}\left(S_1^{(1)}(\theta), \dots, S_1^{(k)}(\theta)\right) \quad (3.32)$$

has exactly one solution. It can be shown that the solution of this equation equals to the median of the intersections of $\hat{\mu}(\mathcal{D}_0) - \theta$ with sub-sample lines $\{S_1^{(\ell)}(\theta)\}$. These intersec-

tions can be computed by

$$\begin{aligned}\nu_\ell^- &= \frac{\widehat{\mu}(\mathcal{D}_0) - \frac{1}{\tilde{n}} \sum_{i=(\ell-1)\tilde{n}}^{\ell\tilde{n}} \alpha_{i,1} Y_i}{1 - \frac{1}{\tilde{n}} \sum_{i=(\ell-1)\tilde{n}}^{\ell\tilde{n}} \alpha_{i,1}} = \mu + \frac{\widehat{\mu}(\mathcal{W}_0) - \frac{1}{\tilde{n}} \sum_{i=(\ell-1)\tilde{n}}^{\ell\tilde{n}} \alpha_{i,1} W_i}{\frac{1}{\tilde{n}} \sum_{i=(\ell-1)\tilde{n}}^{\ell\tilde{n}} (1 - \alpha_{i,1})} \\ &= \mu + \frac{\widehat{\mu}(\mathcal{W}_0) - \frac{1}{\tilde{n}} \sum_{i=(\ell-1)\tilde{n}}^{\ell\tilde{n}} \alpha_{i,1} W_i}{\frac{2}{\tilde{n}} Z_\ell}\end{aligned}\quad (3.33)$$

for $\ell = 1, \dots, k$. Hence, the median of intersections,

$$\begin{aligned}\nu^- &= \operatorname{med}_{\ell \in [k]} \nu_\ell^- \\ &= \mu + \operatorname{med}_{\ell \in [k]} \left(\frac{\widehat{\mu}(\mathcal{W}_0) - \frac{1}{\tilde{n}} \sum_{i=(\ell-1)\tilde{n}}^{\ell\tilde{n}} \alpha_{i,1} W_i}{\frac{2}{\tilde{n}} Z_\ell} \right) \\ &= \mu + V^-, \end{aligned}\quad (3.34)$$

is an intersection of $S_0(\theta)$ and $S_1(\theta)$, where

$$V^- \doteq \operatorname{med}_{\ell \in [k]} \left(\frac{\widehat{\mu}(\mathcal{W}_0) - \frac{1}{\tilde{n}} \sum_{i=(\ell-1)\tilde{n}}^{\ell\tilde{n}} \alpha_{i,1} W_i}{\frac{2}{\tilde{n}} Z_\ell} \right).\quad (3.35)$$

Similarly, another intersection of $S_0(\theta)$ and $S_1(\theta)$ occurs in

$$\nu^+ = \mu + V^+, \quad (3.36)$$

where

$$V^+ \doteq \operatorname{med}_{\ell \in [k]} \left(\frac{\widehat{\mu}(\mathcal{W}_0) + \frac{1}{\tilde{n}} \sum_{i=(\ell-1)\tilde{n}}^{\ell\tilde{n}} \alpha_{i,1} W_i}{\frac{2}{\tilde{n}} (\tilde{n} - Z_\ell)} \right).\quad (3.37)$$

Since $S_1(\theta)$ is “flatter” than $S_0(\theta)$, these are the only two intersections and

$$\Theta_n = \{ \theta : S_0(\theta) \prec_\pi S_1(\theta) \} = [\lambda, \tau]_\pi, \quad (3.38)$$

where $\lambda \doteq \min(\nu^-, \nu^+)$, $\tau \doteq \max(\nu^-, \nu^+)$ and $[\cdot, \cdot]_\pi$ denotes the interval of which endpoints are included if $\pi(0) < \pi(1)$. We can also observe that V^- and V^+ have the same symmetric distribution and both ν^- and ν^+ are well-defined, because $\tilde{n}/4 \leq Z_\ell \leq 3\tilde{n}/4$. Thus, the size of the confidence interval can be computed as

$$\operatorname{diam}(\Theta_n) = |\nu^+ - \nu^-| = |V^+ - V^-|. \quad (3.39)$$

We note that the formulas for ν^\pm remain valid if all $\{Z_\ell, \tilde{n} - Z_\ell\}_{\ell=1}^k$ are positive. Then, using symmetry and the application of the union bound yield

$$\begin{aligned}\mathbb{P}(\operatorname{diam}(\Theta_n) > \varepsilon | A) &\leq \mathbb{P}(|V^+| > \varepsilon/2 \text{ or } |V^-| > \varepsilon/2 | A) \\ &\leq \mathbb{P}(|V^+| > \varepsilon/2 | A) + \mathbb{P}(|V^-| > \varepsilon/2 | A)\end{aligned}$$

$$= 2 \cdot \mathbb{P}(|V^-| > \varepsilon/2 | A) \leq 4 \cdot \mathbb{P}(V^- > \varepsilon/2 | A). \quad (3.40)$$

Let us consider the events that follow

$$B = \{V^- > \varepsilon/2\}, \quad (3.41)$$

$$\tilde{B} = \left\{ \text{med}_{\ell \in [k]} \left(\frac{\hat{\mu}(\mathcal{W}_0) - \frac{1}{\tilde{n}} \sum_{i=(\ell-1)\tilde{n}}^{\ell\tilde{n}} \alpha_{i,1} W_i}{\frac{1}{2}} \right) > \varepsilon/2 \right\}.$$

Our key observation is that $B \cap A \subseteq \tilde{B} \cap A$, since if V^- is positive, then decreasing Z_ℓ in the denominator for every $\ell \in [k]$ down to $\tilde{n}/4$ increases the median in which case the median remains over $\varepsilon/2$. Consequently similarly as in (3.40)

$$\mathbb{P}(B \cap A) \leq \mathbb{P}(\tilde{B} \cap A) \leq 2 \cdot \mathbb{P}(\hat{\mu}(\mathcal{W}_0) > \varepsilon/8). \quad (3.42)$$

The details of this computation can be found in Appendix A. In conclusion, for $\tilde{\varrho} > 0$, $k = \lceil 8 \log(2/\tilde{\varrho}) \rceil$, $\varepsilon = 64 \left(\frac{12M^{1/a} \log(1/\tilde{\varrho})}{n} \right)^{\frac{a}{1+a}}$ and $n \geq k(8 \log(k) + k)$:

$$\mathbb{P} \left(\text{diam}(\Theta_n) > 8 \left(\frac{12M^{1/a} \log(1/\tilde{\varrho})}{n} \right)^{\frac{a}{1+a}} \right) \leq 2k \exp \left(-\frac{n}{8k} \right) + 8\tilde{\varrho} \leq 10\tilde{\varrho}, \quad (3.43)$$

from which the theorem follows. \square

We proved that $\Theta_n = [\lambda, \tau]_\pi$, where random permutation π “decides” about the endpoints, and Θ_n is bounded with high probability. In addition, $\hat{\mu}(\mathcal{D}_0)$ is always included in Θ_n if $\Theta_n \neq \emptyset$. The proof provided formulas in (3.33), (3.34), and (3.36) to construct the confidence interval for $m = 2$. The time complexity of the algorithm is in $O(n)$ and the space complexity is in $O(k)$, because one needs to compute the median of k elements.

We also show that $\Theta_n = [\lambda, \tau]_\pi$ for every $m \geq 2$ and present an explicit formula for the interval for all sign realizations $\{\alpha_{i,j}\}$ and $m \geq 2$ in Algorithm 2. In (3.46) we determine all intersections of the linear functions of $\hat{\mu}(\mathcal{D}_j(\theta)) - \theta$ and $\hat{\mu} - \theta$. With high probability these lines have only one intersections defined by the formula in (3.46). If these lines are parallel, then the intersection values are extended to $+\infty$ or $-\infty$ respectively. Index s is introduced to include the dependence of these extended values on the tiebreaking random variables respectively. We prove, as well, that Θ_n admits the special form of (3.44).

Theorem 3.3.2. *For $m \geq 2$ we have*

$$\Theta_n = \bigcup_{\substack{J \subseteq [m-1], j \in J \\ |J|=m-r}} \bigcap \left\{ \theta : S_0(\theta) \prec_\pi S_j(\theta) \right\}, \quad (3.44)$$

thus Θ_n is an interval that contains $\hat{\mu}(\mathcal{D}_0)$, if $\Theta_n \neq \emptyset$.

Our general result for $m \geq 2$ is as follows:

Algorithm 2 RMM Confidence Interval

Inputs: i.i.d. sample \mathcal{D}_0 , rational significance level δ ,
 tiebreaking permutation π on $[m-1]_0$,
 odd median-of-means parameter k

- 1: Choose integers $1 \leq r < m$ such that $\delta = r/m$.
- 2: Generate $n(m-1)$ independent Rademacher signs $\{\alpha_{i,j}\}$ for $(i,j) \in [n] \times [m-1]_0$.
- 3: For all $(\ell, j) \in [k] \times [m-1]$ and $s \in \{\pm 1\}$, compute the extended values

$$\nu_{\ell,j,s}^{\pm} = \frac{\hat{\mu}(\mathcal{D}_0) \pm \frac{1}{\bar{n}} \sum_{i=(\ell-1)\bar{n}}^{\ell\bar{n}} \alpha_{i,j} Y_i}{1 \pm \frac{1}{\bar{n}} \sum_{i=(\ell-1)\bar{n}}^{\ell\bar{n}} \alpha_{i,j}}, \quad (3.46)$$

where $\frac{\pm c}{0} = \pm\infty$ for all $c > 0$ and $\frac{0}{0} = s \cdot \infty$.

- 4: For all $(\ell, j) \in [k] \times [m-1]$ and $s \in \{\pm 1\}$, let

$$\nu_{j,s}^+ \doteq \text{med}_{\ell \in [k]} \nu_{\ell,j,s}^+, \quad \text{and} \quad \nu_{j,s}^- \doteq \text{med}_{\ell \in [k]} \nu_{\ell,j,s}^-. \quad (3.47)$$

- 5: For all $j \in [m-1]$, let $v^j \doteq [\nu_{j,-1}^+, \nu_{j,+1}^+, \nu_{j,-1}^-, \nu_{j,+1}^-]$.
- 6: For $j \in [m-1]$ if $\pi(j) > \pi(0)$, let $\lambda_j \doteq v_{(1)}^j$, $\tau_j \doteq v_{(4)}^j$ otherwise let $\lambda_j \doteq v_{(2)}^j$, $\tau_j \doteq v_{(3)}^j$, where $v_{(1)}^j, v_{(2)}^j, v_{(3)}^j, v_{(4)}^j$ are ordered.
- 7: Let $\lambda_{(1)}, \dots, \lambda_{(m-1)}$ and $\tau_{(1)}, \dots, \tau_{(m-1)}$ be ordered w.r.t. \prec_{π} and

$$\lambda \doteq \lambda_{(r)}, \quad \tau \doteq \tau_{(m-r)}. \quad (3.48)$$

- 8: Let $\eta_1, \eta_2 \in [m-1]$ be the original indices of $\lambda_{(r)}$ and $\tau_{(m-r)}$ before ordering. Return

$$[\lambda, \tau]_{\pi} \doteq (\lambda, \tau) \cup \{\lambda : \pi(0) < \pi(\eta_1)\} \cup \{\tau : \pi(0) < \pi(\eta_2)\}. \quad (3.49)$$

Theorem 3.3.3. *Assume A1, A2 and A3. Let $r < m$ be user-chosen positive integers, $\varrho > 0$, $k = \lceil 8 \log(20(m-r)/\varrho) \rceil$, then for $n \geq k(k + 8 \log(k))$ we have*

$$\mathbb{P} \left(\text{diam}(\Theta_n) > 8 \left(\frac{12M^{1/a} \log \left(\frac{10(m-r)}{\varrho} \right)}{n} \right)^{\frac{a}{1+a}} \right) \leq \varrho. \quad (3.45)$$

Proof. The proof follows from Theorem 3.3.1 and the union bound. A similar argument can be found in the proof of (Szentpéteri and Csáji, 2023, Theorem 3). \square

An illustrative example of the confidence interval for $m = 2$ and $k = 3$ is presented in Figure 3.1. In this example, the dashed lines are the sub-sample reference and alternative lines, while the solid lines are the reference variable functions for $j = 0$ and 1. The confidence region is given by the intersections of the reference variables for $\delta = 0.5$.

Figure 3.1: Confidence interval for $m = 2$ (50% confidence), $n = 30$ and $k = 3$.

3.4 Numerical Experiment

In this section we present a numerical experiment comparing our theoretical bounds on the sizes of RMM confidence regions, given by Theorem 3.3.3, with the theoretical confidence bound for the MoM estimator, proved in (Lugosi and Mendelson, 2019a, Theorem 3), and with the empirical sizes of the RMM and SPS regions which use the empirical mean instead of the MoM estimator. We consider a scalar mean estimation problem, where Y is sampled from a symmetrized Pareto distribution with scale parameter 1 and shape parameter 1.6. We consider 0.5-level confidence regions with $m = 2$ and $r = 1$ with sample sizes up to $n = 12900$. We simulated 10000 independent trajectories. In the experiments we let $\varrho = 0.1$, $a = 0.5$ and set k according to Theorem 3.3.3.

In Figure 3.2 the $(1 - \varrho)$ -quantiles of the empirical confidence interval sizes of the novel RMM method and the SPS algorithm are compared to the theoretical bounds of (3.45) and (Lugosi and Mendelson, 2019a, Theorem 3) for each sample size.

The theoretical bounds are conservative compared to the empirical sizes. We can observe that the difference between the theoretical bounds are negligible and our data-driven RMM algorithm has a better empirical performance than using Theorem 2.3.1. The experiments indicate that for heavy-tailed distributions the RMM method builds tighter confidence intervals than the original SPS method.

Figure 3.2: Comparison of confidence interval sizes.

3.5 Multivariate Hypothesis Test

In this section let Y be a p -dimensional random vector and $\{Y^i\}_{i=1}^n$ be an i.i.d. sample, cf. A1. Henceforth, we denote the coordinates of Y with lower indices. We present the multivariate generalization of the RMM method. Our assumptions are:

A4. $Y - \mu \stackrel{d}{=} \mu - Y$, for some vector $\mu \in \mathbb{R}^p$.

A5. $\Sigma \doteq \mathbb{E}[(Y - \mathbb{E}Y)(Y - \mathbb{E}Y)^\top]$ exists.

We note that the components of Y can be correlated, and A4 does not require symmetry w.r.t. each coordinate axis. It is easy to see that from A4 and A5 it follows that $\mu = \mathbb{E}[Y]$. Let λ^* denote the greatest eigenvalue of Σ . It is known that for a zero mean multivariate normal vector Z with $\text{var}(Z) = \Sigma$ we have

$$\mathbb{P}(\|Z\| - \mathbb{E}[\|Z\|] \geq t\sqrt{n}) \leq \exp\left(-\frac{nt^2}{2\lambda^*}\right) \quad (3.50)$$

for the Euclidean norm $\|\cdot\|$ (Cirel'son et al., 2006). Because of

$$\mathbb{E}[\|Z\|] \leq \sqrt{\mathbb{E}[\|Z\|^2]} = \sqrt{\text{Tr}(\Sigma)}, \quad (3.51)$$

if $\bar{\mu}_n$ denotes the empirical mean of a normally distributed i.i.d. sample $\{Z^i\}_{i=1}^n$, then for all $\varrho \in (0, 1)$ we have

$$\mathbb{P}\left(\|\bar{\mu}_n - \mu\| > \sqrt{\frac{\text{Tr}(\Sigma)}{n}} + \sqrt{\frac{2\lambda^* \log(1/\varrho)}{n}}\right) \leq \varrho. \quad (3.52)$$

In general, it is hard to reach this high probability bound for an unknown distribution with covariance matrix Σ , e.g., the coordinate-wise median-of-means

$$\tilde{\mu}_j \doteq \hat{\mu}(\{Y_j^i\}_{i=1}^n) \text{ for } j = 1, \dots, p, \quad (3.53)$$

admits a much weaker PAC bound; for all $\varrho \in (0, 1)$ if $k = \lceil 8 \log(1/\varrho) \rceil$ only a dimension dependent inequality can be proved (Lugosi and Mendelson, 2019a), where $\log(1/\varrho)$ is multiplied by the trace instead of the largest eigenvalue of Σ , i.e.,

$$\mathbb{P}\left(\|\tilde{\mu} - \mu\| \leq \sqrt{\frac{32 \operatorname{Tr}(\Sigma) \log(p/\varrho)}{n}}\right) \geq 1 - \varrho. \quad (3.54)$$

One may construct estimators with stronger guarantees. Geometrical median-of-means (Hsu and Sabato, 2016; Minsker, 2015) and median-of-means tournaments (Lugosi and Mendelson, 2019b) are analyzed in the survey of Lugosi and Mendelson (2019a). The median-of-means tournament estimator and also its polynomial time relaxation are proved to be in the subgaussian regime (Hopkins, 2020; Lugosi and Mendelson, 2019b).

Let us use any subgaussian estimator $\hat{\mu}$, such as the median-of-means tournament estimator, to define a meta test for the mean estimation problem in the multivariate case.

A6. *Let $\hat{\mu}$ be a multivariate subgaussian mean estimator, i.e., there exist positive constants c_1, c_2 and c_3 such that for every $\varrho > 0$ we have*

$$\mathbb{P}\left(\|\hat{\mu} - \mu\| > \sqrt{\frac{c_1 \operatorname{Tr}(\Sigma)}{n}} + \sqrt{\frac{c_2 \lambda^* \log(c_3/\varrho)}{n}}\right) \leq \varrho. \quad (3.55)$$

For $\theta \in \mathbb{R}^p$ we consider the null hypothesis $H_0 : \mu = \theta$ and alternative $H_1 : \mu \neq \theta$. The multivariate RMM method constructs alternative datasets of vectors for $j \in [m-1]$ by

$$\mathcal{D}_j(\theta) \doteq \{\alpha_{1,j} \mathbb{1} \odot (Y_1 - \theta) + \theta, \dots, \alpha_{n,j} \mathbb{1} \odot (Y_n - \theta) + \theta\},$$

where $\mathbb{1}$ is the all one vector and \odot denotes the Hadamard (element-wise) product. Let us use $\mathcal{D}_j^\pi(\theta) \doteq (\mathcal{D}_j(\theta), \pi(j))$ for $j \in [m-1]_0$, and define the reference variables as

$$S_j(\theta) \doteq \left\| \hat{\mu}(\mathcal{D}_j(\theta)) - \theta \right\| \quad (3.56)$$

for $j = 0, \dots, m-1$. The null hypothesis is rejected as in Algorithm 1, i.e., if and only if $\mathcal{R}(\theta) > m-r$, where $\mathcal{R}(\theta)$ is defined as in (3.8). A detailed description of the multivariate method is presented in Algorithm 3. The exact confidence level of this test is proved in:

Theorem 3.5.1. *Assume A1 and A4, then the multivariate RMM test is exact, i.e., for every integers $1 \leq r < m$ and for every sample size $n \in \mathbb{N}^+$ we have*

$$\mathbb{P}(\mathcal{R}(\mu) > m-r) = \frac{r}{m}. \quad (3.60)$$

Algorithm 3 Multivariate RMM Test

Inputs: i.i.d. sample \mathcal{D}_0 , rational significance level δ ,
 tiebreaking permutation π on $[m-1]_0$,
 subgaussian estimator $\hat{\mu}$

- 1: Choose integers $1 \leq r < m$ such that $\delta = r/m$.
- 2: Generate $n(m-1)$ independent random signs $\{\alpha_{i,j}\}$ for $(i,j) \in [n] \times [m-1]$.
- 3: Construct $m-1$ alternative datasets for $j \in [m-1]$:

$$\mathcal{D}_j(\theta) \doteq \{\alpha_{1,j}\mathbb{1} \odot (Y_1 - \theta) + \theta, \dots, \alpha_{n,j}\mathbb{1} \odot (Y_n - \theta) + \theta\} \quad (3.57)$$

and let $\mathcal{D}_j^\pi \doteq (\mathcal{D}_j(\theta), \pi(j))$ for $j \in [m-1]_0$, where $\mathcal{D}_0(\theta) \doteq \mathcal{D}_0$ for all $\theta \in \Theta$.

- 4: Compute the reference variables

$$S_j(\theta) \doteq \left\| \hat{\mu}(\mathcal{D}_j(\theta)) - \theta \right\| \quad \text{for } j = 0, \dots, m-1.$$

- 5: Compute the rank

$$\mathcal{R}(\theta) = 1 + \sum_{j=1}^{m-1} \mathbb{I} \left(S_0(\theta) \succ_{\pi} S_j(\theta) \right). \quad (3.58)$$

- 6: Reject H_0 if and only if

$$\mathcal{R}(\theta) > m - r. \quad (3.59)$$

Pointwise finite sample guarantees are presented for the type II error probability in Theorem 3.5.2. The complete proofs can be found in Appendix A, which includes additional numerical experiments as well.

Theorem 3.5.2. *Assume A1, A4, A5 and A6. Let $\varrho > 0$ and $1 \leq r < m$ be user-chosen integers. For $\theta \neq \mu$ if*

$$\sqrt{\frac{c_1(\text{Tr}(\Sigma) + \Delta(\theta)^2)}{n}} + \sqrt{\frac{c_2(\lambda^* + \Delta(\theta)^2) \log\left(\frac{c_3(m-r)}{e}\right)}{n}} < \frac{\Delta(\theta)}{2}, \quad (3.61)$$

holds, where $\Delta(\theta) = \|\theta - \mu\|$, then we have

$$\mathbb{P}(\mathcal{R}(\theta) \leq m - r) \leq \varrho. \quad (3.62)$$

3.6 Discussion

Constructing confidence intervals for the mean of an unknown distribution is an essential and well-studied problem in statistics. However, standard approaches either build on asymptotic results or on the knowledge of some distributional information, that might be harder to estimate than the mean, e.g., moments. In this chapter the problem of building confidence intervals for the mean of a symmetric, heavy-tailed distribution from an i.i.d.

sample was addressed, and the RMM method was introduced. RMM is completely data-driven, it does not require a priori distributional knowledge, e.g., information on moments. First the RMM based hypothesis test was presented, then the corresponding RMM confidence interval was constructed. We showed that RMM confidence intervals have exact confidence levels for any finite sample size. Moreover, optimal PAC bounds were proved for the shrinkage of the RMM intervals. Finally, the construction was extended to the multivariate case and RMM was also evaluated empirically.

Chapter 4

Confidence Sets for the Regression Function of Binary Classification

Classification or pattern recognition is one of the fundamental problems of statistical learning theory (Vapnik, 1998), and it is widely studied in several fields, such as ML, signal processing (especially in image processing), system identification and information theory. An intrinsic goal of classification is to construct estimates for the regression function, because the regression function not only determines a Bayes optimal classifier, but also encodes the conditional misclassification probability given the input.

In this chapter we presented a resampling framework to construct distribution-free and non-asymptotically exact confidence regions for the true regression function for any (rational) user-chosen confidence level. Then, four specific algorithms are suggested and analyzed to demonstrate the framework: an empirical risk minimization (ERM) based method, a k-nearest neighbors (kNN) based method and two variants of a CKME based method. We prove that the ERM-based confidence regions are strongly uniformly consistent and the remaining three methods achieve pointwise consistency. The convergence rates are quantified with PAC type bounds. Finally, the algorithms are validated with numerical experiments, and the methods are compared to approximate asymptotic confidence ellipsoids around the maximum likelihood estimator (MLE).

In this chapter we introduce the resampling framework of (Csáji and Tamás, 2019) and the methods of (Tamás and Csáji, 2020, 2022; Tamás, 2023) with the corresponding stochastic guarantees. Additionally, several results of the submitted paper (Tamás and Csáji, 2025) are also presented.

4.1 Scientific Background

There are several methods to construct region estimates, e.g., confidence intervals and ellipsoids, but most of these approaches suffer from theoretical limitations. In the area of parametric statistics, under strong assumptions on the observations, the distribution of the estimate can be derived. For example, confidence intervals for the expected value of

a normal distribution can be constructed based on the sample mean and variance.

In statistical learning the distribution of the sample is typically unknown, therefore, distribution-free methods are sought. The asymptotic theory of distribution-free regression function estimation is rich (Györfi et al., 2002). Many well-known estimators, for example, the kNN method and Nadaraya-Watson type kernel estimators, are proved to be strongly universally L_2 consistent (Devroye et al., 1994; Walk, 2002), however, the convergence rates of these methods can be arbitrarily slow (Cover, 1968) and for nonparametric families of distributions the rates are usually way too conservative (for example, minimax) to be useful in practice. With an asymptotic approach, the distribution of the scaled estimation error can be approximated with its limiting distribution, which can often be characterized by the CLT. However, asymptotic methods can perform poorly for small samples, because their guarantees are only approximate for finite datasets.

Distribution-free binary classification was studied by Barber (2020) in the popular framework of conformal inference (Vovk et al., 2005). Barber (2020) proves an explicit lower bound on the expected width of distribution-free confidence intervals for the conditional class probability in case of binary outputs and constructs a procedure that achieves this length approximately. In this chapter we prove the strong consistency of our confidence regions in an L_2 space, under no assumptions on the marginal distribution of the inputs. This seemingly contradicts the results of (Barber, 2020), however, our scheme does not necessarily construct confidence intervals with vanishing expected width for regression function values in general, but tests the functions themselves instead.

Our main objective is to build data-driven, nonparametric, non-asymptotically exact confidence regions for the regression function of binary classification and prove exponential PAC bounds as well as strong consistency results under very mild statistical assumptions. Our new approach was motivated by the SPS method (Csáji et al., 2014; Csáji and Weyer, 2015). SPS was modified in several ways to construct confidence sets for binary classification. We needed to refine the resampling mechanism and the ranking function to obtain finite sample guarantees for the regression function.

We present resampling hypothesis tests, i.e., we make statistical inference based on alternatively (artificially) drawn samples. We verify that resampling methods can provide universal, adaptive stochastic guarantees for binary classification. The newly presented methods are Monte Carlo tests, however, we emphasize the confidence region perspective of the defined tests and show how to reduce the cost of the alternative data generation to a constant and still be able to test any candidate.

We develop four algorithms for classification. We present strong uniform asymptotic results for an ERM based ranking function for a model class with finite pseudo-dimension and inverse Lipschitz parameterization and we also provide PAC bounds on the \mathcal{L}_2 size of the confidence set. Additionally, we infer pointwise bounds for a kNN based method. These algorithms are illustrated on a logistic model class and compared to asymptotic ellipsoids with numerical simulations. Finally, we introduce two consistent CKME based rank tests which motivate the main problem of Chapter 5.

4.2 Binary Classification

Let us recall the notations of binary classification, cf. Section 2.3.3. Let $(\mathbb{X}, \mathcal{X})$ be a measurable input space and let the binary output space be $\mathbb{Y} = \{+1, -1\}$. Let $\mathcal{D}_0 = \{(X_i, Y_i)\}_{i=1}^n$ denote an i.i.d. sample from the unknown joint distribution, $Q_{X,Y}$ (simply Q), of the input-output pair (X, Y) , where $X_i \in \mathbb{X}$ and $Y_i \in \mathbb{Y}$, for $i \in [n]$.

The main goal of classification is to minimize the expected loss (a.k.a. Bayes risk) over the set of classifiers. In case of the zero-one loss, the Bayes risk equals to the probability of misclassification, however, since the joint distribution of (X, Y) is unknown, we do not have a direct access to this quantity, due to which the minimization is challenging.

It is known that, assuming binary outputs, the joint distribution, Q , is determined by the marginal distribution of the inputs, Q_x , and the regression function, f^* . Furthermore, we saw that for the zero-one loss, a Bayes (optimal) classifier takes the form of $\phi^*(x) \doteq \text{sign}(f^*(x))$. The regression function does not only determine an optimal classifier, but it also encodes the misclassification probabilities for every inputs. That is why f^* is a key object for classification, henceforth in this chapter we build confidence regions for f^* .

4.3 Resampling for Classification

In this section we present a resampling framework to build distribution-free, non-asymptotic confidence regions, which contain the regression function of binary classification with a prescribed (rational) confidence level. Later, we consider four specific algorithms to build exact confidence sets for the regression function under mild statistical assumptions. The core assumptions of the framework are as follows:

B1. *The given sample, $\mathcal{D}_0 = \{(X_i, Y_i)\}_{i=1}^n$, is i.i.d. from distribution Q .*

B2. *A class of candidate regression functions is available, indexed by an arbitrary set of “parameters”, which contains f^* , that is, $f^* \in \mathcal{F}_0 \doteq \{f_\theta : \mathbb{X} \rightarrow [-1, +1] \mid \theta \in \Theta\}$.*

B3. *The parameterization is injective in the $\mathcal{L}_2(Q_x)$ sense, i.e., for all $\theta_1 \neq \theta_2 \in \Theta$:*

$$\|f_{\theta_1} - f_{\theta_2}\|_Q^2 \doteq \int_{\mathbb{X}} (f_{\theta_1}(x) - f_{\theta_2}(x))^2 dQ_x(x) \neq 0. \quad (4.1)$$

Let θ^* denote the parameter which corresponds to the true regression function, that is, $f_{\theta^*} = f^*$. The true parameter is well-defined, because of B3. Our method can be applied without this assumption and our theorems can be generalized for equivalent classes, however, B3 simplifies the analysis. Although we refer to Θ as “parameter space”, it can be almost any abstract set (a metric structure will be assumed for the uniform consistency results), e.g., Θ can be an infinite dimensional vector space. Moreover, the functions themselves can be the “parameters”. A confidence region is a random subset of Θ which covers θ^* with a user-chosen probability. In the section that follows abstract region estimators are defined as the accepted parameters of a rank test.

Algorithm 4 Initialization

Input: rational coverage probability γ

1: Select integers $1 \leq q_1 < q_2 \leq m$ such that

$$\gamma = \frac{q_2 - q_1 + 1}{m}. \quad (4.3)$$

2: Generate i.i.d. random variables, $\mathcal{U} \doteq \{U_{i,j}\}$ for $i \in [n]$ and $j \in [m - 1]$ with

$$U_{i,j} \sim \text{Uniform}(-1, 1). \quad (4.4)$$

3: Generate a random permutation π uniformly from the symmetric group over $[m - 1]_0$.

One of the main observations needed for our approach is that a regression function candidate determines the conditional distribution of the outputs given the inputs, that is,

$$\mathbb{P}(Y(\theta) = \pm 1 \mid X = x) = (1 \pm f_\theta(x))/2, \quad (4.2)$$

for all $\theta \in \Theta$. Notice that Y has the same distribution as $Y(\theta^*)$. Our idea is to generate alternative outputs for a given candidate model, then compare the alternative datasets to the original sample with a similarity measure to test the candidate's suitability. The comparison is performed via rank statistics, cf. Definition 3.2.1.

Lemma 3.2.1, which is an important observation about the rank of exchangeable random elements, will be our main tool to prove that the (user-chosen, rational) confidence level of the constructed confidence region is exact for every finite sample size. We emphasize that Lemma 3.2.1 is distribution-free, i.e., the marginal distribution of the given random elements, $\{\xi_j\}_{j=1}^m$, can be arbitrary. We note that the random elements that we compare do not need to be fully independent, only their exchangeability is required, which is more general than the i.i.d. assumption.

We use a ranking function ψ on resampled datasets. The given sample, \mathcal{D}_0 , is included in $(\mathbb{X} \times \mathbb{Y})^n$. Our framework generates $m - 1$ alternative random elements from this space for any candidate model, i.e., $\mathcal{D}_j(\theta) \doteq \{(X_i, Y_{i,j}(\theta))\}_{i=1}^n$, where $Y_{i,j}(\theta) = \text{sign}(f_\theta(X_i) + U_{i,j})$ with i.i.d. uniform variables $\{U_{i,j}\}$ on interval $[-1, 1]$ for $i \in [n]$ and $j \in [m - 1]$. That is, the conditional distribution of $Y_{i,j}(\theta)$ w.r.t. X_i is given by f_θ . Hence, we consider m elements in $(\mathbb{X} \times \mathbb{Y})^n$. To ensure pairwise difference, which is a technical assumption in Lemma 3.2.1, as in Chapter 3, we extend the datasets with the elements of a uniformly sampled random permutation π on set $[m - 1]_0$, i.e., we let $\mathcal{D}_j^\pi(\theta) \doteq (\mathcal{D}_j(\theta), \pi(j))$ for $j \in [m - 1]_0$. Thus, we construct $\psi : ((\mathbb{X} \times \mathbb{Y})^n \times [m])^m \rightarrow [m]$ type ranking functions.

The confidence region construction for an arbitrary ranking function ψ consists of two parts. First, in the initialization process, in Algorithm 4, the integer hyperparameters (q_1 , q_2 and m) are selected and a stem sample is generated. Then, in Algorithm 5 we define rank statistics on the parameter set with the help of the ranking function. Finally, we

Algorithm 5 Rank Statistic

Inputs: candidate parameter θ , original sample \mathcal{D}_0 , set of uniform variables \mathcal{U} , ranking function ψ , integer m , permutation π

- 1: Let $Y_{i,j}(\theta) \doteq \text{sign}(f_\theta(X_i) + U_{i,j})$ for $i \in [n]$ and $j \in [m-1]$ be the alternative outputs for model f_θ . For simplicity let $Y_{i,0}(\theta) = Y_i$ for $i \in [n]$.
- 2: Let $\mathcal{D}_j(\theta) \doteq \{(X_i, Y_{i,j}(\theta))\}_{i=1}^n$ be alternative samples for $j \in [m-1]_0$.
- 3: Let $\mathcal{D}_j^\pi(\theta) \doteq (\mathcal{D}_j(\theta), \pi(j))$ be the extended alternative sample for $j \in [m-1]_0$.
- 4: Return the rank statistic of parameter θ , that is, return

$$\psi(\mathcal{D}_0^\pi(\theta), \{\mathcal{D}_j^\pi(\theta)\}_{j=1}^{m-1}). \quad (4.6)$$

construct the confidence region based on the ranks by

$$\Theta_n^\psi \doteq \left\{ \theta \in \Theta \mid q_1 \leq \psi(\mathcal{D}_0^\pi(\theta), \{\mathcal{D}_j^\pi(\theta)\}_{j \neq 0}) \leq q_2 \right\}. \quad (4.5)$$

We show that Θ_n^ψ is an exact confidence region for θ^* with confidence level γ . Let us fix an index $i \in [n]$ and take the observations that follow. First, we note that

$$\mathbb{P}(Y_{i,j}(\theta) = \pm 1 \mid X_i) = \frac{1 \pm f_\theta(X_i)}{2} \quad (4.7)$$

and consequently $Y_{i,j}(\theta)$ is generated from the conditional distribution with respect to X_i determined by candidate regression function f_θ for all $j \in [m-1]$. Second, clearly $Y_{i,0}$ has the same conditional distribution with respect to X_i as $Y_{i,j}(\theta^*)$. In addition $\{Y_{i,j}(\theta^*)\}_{j=0}^{m-1}$ are all conditionally i.i.d. with respect to X_i , because $\{U_{i,j}\}_{j=1}^{m-1}$ are independent of each other and $Y_{i,0}$. We conclude that $\mathcal{D}_0, \mathcal{D}_1(\theta^*), \dots, \mathcal{D}_{m-1}(\theta^*)$ are conditionally i.i.d. with respect to $\{X_i\}_{i=1}^n$, thus they are also exchangeable. Hence, the application of Lemma 3.2.1 yields the theorem that follows, which is one of the main results of this chapter:

Theorem 4.3.1. *Assume that B1, B2 and B3 hold. Then, for any ranking function ψ , integers $1 \leq q_1 \leq q_2 \leq m$ and sample size $n \in \mathbb{N}^+$ we have*

$$\mathbb{P}(\theta^* \in \Theta_n^\psi) = \frac{q_2 - q_1 + 1}{m}. \quad (4.8)$$

Note that Theorem 4.3.1 holds for any finite dataset. If interpreted as a hypothesis test, Theorem 4.3.1 quantifies exactly the probability of type I error. Any rational coverage level can be exactly attained by choosing appropriate hyperparameters. If needed, irrational coverage levels could also be achieved by using additional randomization. We allow parameterizing the regression function, while the distribution of the inputs can be arbitrary, hence our approach can be applied in a semi-parametric setting, too. On the other hand, our method provides exact confidence sets on a distribution-free fashion, e.g., if we consider the model class of all possible regression functions.

The application of the proposed framework requires an appropriate ranking function. We develop rankings that produce consistent confidence regions. We aim at sorting datasets $\{\mathcal{D}_j^\pi(\theta)\}_{j=0}^{m-1}$ with the help of ψ . The extended datasets are from a high-dimensional space, where a total order is not given in general. For this purpose we introduce real-valued reference variables of the form

$$Z_n^{(j)}(\theta) \doteq T(\mathcal{D}_j(\theta), \theta), \quad (4.9)$$

for $j = 0, \dots, m-1$, where $T : (\mathbb{X} \times \mathbb{Y})^n \times \Theta \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$ is a real-valued map (measurable for all $\theta \in \Theta$). In order to sort $\{Z_n^{(j)}(\theta)\}_{j=0}^{m-1}$ we use the total order \prec_π defined by (3.9). With these notations let the ranking function be

$$\psi \left(\mathcal{D}_0^\pi(\theta), \{\mathcal{D}_j^\pi(\theta)\}_{j=1}^{m-1} \right) \doteq 1 + \sum_{j=1}^{m-1} \mathbb{I}(Z_n^{(0)}(\theta) \succ_\pi Z_n^{(j)}(\theta)). \quad (4.10)$$

Clearly, ψ satisfies P1 and P2. In the sections that follow we design real-valued statistics and reference variables that guarantee consistency for the constructed confidence regions beside the exact coverage probability. Note that T can depend on the model class, however, in this chapter \mathcal{F}_0 is fixed, therefore we do not indicate this dependence in the notation.

4.4 Point Estimator Based Constructions

In this section we present a general approach to define reference variables. Our idea is to estimate the regression function candidate from all available datasets, both from the original one and the resampled ones, and compare their empirical errors w.r.t. the candidate function. Any estimator of the regression function can be used. We focus on two specific choices: an ERM based and a kNN based technique. Both approaches construct exact confidence regions for any user-chosen confidence level and we prove that they also have strong asymptotic guarantees. Sufficient conditions are presented for strong uniform consistency of the ERM-based construction and strong pointwise consistency is proved for the kNN-based method. We make the additional assumption that follows:

B4. (*Euclidean input space condition*) $\mathbb{X} \subseteq \mathbb{R}^d$

4.4.1 Empirical Risk Minimization

It is well-known that the regression function is a risk minimizer (Györfi et al., 2002); f^* minimizes the true expected squared loss among all measurable functions, that is,

$$f^* = \arg \min_f \mathbb{E}[(f(X) - Y)^2]. \quad (4.11)$$

This observation motivates the application of the ERM principle, which, given a model class \mathcal{F} and a sample $\{(X_i, Y_i)\}_{i=1}^n$, estimates the regression function by choosing

$$f_n \doteq \arg \min_{f \in \mathcal{F}} \frac{1}{n} \sum_{i=1}^n (f(X_i) - Y_i)^2, \quad (4.12)$$

where the quantity in the right hand side is called the empirical risk. Note that we assume the existence and the measurability of f_n throughout the dissertation, however, we do not require the uniqueness of the estimate.

When f^* is included in a model class \mathcal{F} , the consistency of ERM estimates can be proved with the uniform convergence of the empirical risk to the true risk, i.e., with

$$\sup_{f \in \mathcal{F}} \left| \frac{1}{n} \sum_{i=1}^n (f(X_i) - Y_i)^2 - \mathbb{E}[(f(X) - Y)^2] \right| \xrightarrow{a.s.} 0. \quad (4.13)$$

These type of convergences are called the (strong) uniform laws of large numbers (ULLN) and are at the core of statistical learning theory (Vapnik, 1998; Györfi et al., 2002). The measurability of the supremum in (4.13) needs to be verified for the model class as it may contain uncountably many elements. For simplicity and to avoid digressions, we always assume the measurability of the arising supremums without further notice.

Classical approaches define a complexity measure to quantify the capacity of the model class and prove ULLN by posing bounds on the complexity. We use the concept of pseudo-dimension to restrict the expressivity of \mathcal{F}_0 . This notion is based on the celebrated Vapnik-Chervonenkis dimension (VC dimension), whose definition is recalled in Appendix B.

Definition 4.4.1 (pseudo-dimension). *Given a model class \mathcal{H} let \mathcal{H}^+ contain the sub-graphs of the functions in \mathcal{H} , that is,*

$$\mathcal{H}^+ = \{h^+ \mid h \in \mathcal{H}\}, \text{ where } h^+ \doteq \{(x, t) \in \mathbb{R}^d \times \mathbb{R} \mid t \leq h(x)\}, \quad (4.14)$$

then, the VC dimension of \mathcal{H}^+ , denoted by $V_{\mathcal{H}^+}$, is called the pseudo-dimension of \mathcal{H} .

It is known that the ULLN holds if $V_{\mathcal{H}^+} < \infty$ and the convex envelope of \mathcal{H} is Q_X -integrable (Györfi et al., 2002, Theorem 9.6).

4.4.2 Empirical Risk Minimization Based Ranking

For a given parameter θ , let us consider the ERM estimate for all datasets, i.e., let

$$f_{\theta, n}^{(j)} \doteq \arg \min_{f \in \mathcal{F}_0} \frac{1}{n} \sum_{i=1}^n (f(X_i) - Y_{i,j}(\theta))^2, \quad (4.15)$$

for $j = 0, \dots, m - 1$. With these models let the reference variables be defined as

$$Z_n^{(j)}(\theta) \doteq \frac{1}{n} \sum_{i=1}^n (f_{\theta}(X_i) - f_{\theta, n}^{(j)}(X_i))^2, \quad (4.16)$$

for $j = 0, \dots, m - 1$, that is, as the empirical error terms w.r.t. candidate function f_θ we are currently testing. Finally, let us use the ranking function defined in (4.10).

Notice that $f_{\theta,n}^{(0)}$ does not depend on parameter θ because it corresponds to the original dataset \mathcal{D}_0 ; therefore let us denote it by $f_{*,n}^{(0)}$. Then, on the one hand, $f_{*,n}^{(0)}$ should converge to f^* for all $\theta \in \Theta$, because it only uses the original sample, but on the other hand, $f_{\theta,n}^{(j)}$ should tend to f_θ for all $j \in [m - 1]$, for the reason that they estimate the regression function based on samples generated from the conditional distribution determined by f_θ . Because of these observations, our intuition is that for $\theta \neq \theta^*$ for n large enough $Z_n^{(0)}(\theta)$ tends to be the greatest. Therefore, we choose $q_1 = 1$ and $q_2 = q$ leading to

$$\Theta_n^{(1)} \doteq \left\{ \theta \in \Theta \mid \psi\left(\mathcal{D}_0^\pi, \{\mathcal{D}_j^\pi(\theta)\}_{j \neq 0}\right) \leq q \right\}. \quad (4.17)$$

For proving strong uniform consistency we make two additional assumptions:

B5. (*inverse Lipschitz condition*) Let (Θ, Δ) be a metric space and let the parameterization be inverse Lipschitz continuous, i.e., there exists a constant real number $L > 0$ such that for all $\theta_1, \theta_2 \in \Theta$ we have $\Delta(\theta_1, \theta_2) \leq L \cdot \|f_{\theta_1} - f_{\theta_2}\|_Q$.

B6. (*finite pseudo-dimension*) $V_{\mathcal{F}_0^+} < \infty$.

Theorem 4.4.1. Assume B1-B6, then for all sample size $n \in \mathbb{N}^+$ and integers $1 \leq q \leq m$

$$\mathbb{P}\left(\theta^* \in \Theta_n^{(1)}\right) = \frac{q}{m}, \quad (4.18)$$

In addition, if $q < m$, then $(\Theta_n^{(1)})_{n \in \mathbb{N}^+}$ is strongly uniformly consistent.

Observe that Theorem 4.4.1 provides uniform stochastic guarantees, i.e., for every $\varepsilon > 0$ with probability 1 the confidence regions are included in $B(\theta^*, \varepsilon)$ with at most finitely many exceptions. We made only very mild statistical and structural assumptions. The function class can be rich, e.g., it can be a subset of an infinite dimensional vector space; only the pseudo-dimension of the model class needs to be bounded, therefore the distribution of the sample is mildly restricted. The inverse Lipschitz condition is required intuitively to ensure that parameters, whose models are similar in the $\mathcal{L}_2(Q_x)$ sense, need to be close to each other in the parameter space. An important observation is that the confidence region is built around the ERM estimator, because $f_{\hat{\theta}} = f_{\hat{\theta},n}^{(0)}$ and $Z_n^{(0)}(\hat{\theta}) = 0$, henceforth the rank equals to 1 for $\hat{\theta}$ with high probability. A quantitative version of Theorem 4.4.1 is also formulated to provide PAC guarantees. The proofs, including the constants involved, are presented in Appendix B.2.

Theorem 4.4.2. Assume B1-B6 and $1 \leq q < m$. For all $\varepsilon > 0$ there exists N_0 such that for $n \geq N_0$ we have

$$\mathbb{P}\left(\Theta_n^{(1)} \subseteq B(\theta^*, \varepsilon)\right) \geq 1 - C_1 e^{-n\lambda_1}, \quad (4.19)$$

where C_1 depends only on ε and $V_{\mathcal{F}_0^+}$, and λ_1 depends only on ε and the Lipschitz constant.

4.4.3 Example: Perceptron and Generalized Linear Models

An important ERM estimator is the perceptron (Rosenblatt, 1958), which is closely related to generalized linear models in statistics (Hastie and Pregibon, 2017). They apply an activation function on an affine transformation of the input vectors, i.e., $f_{(\theta,b)}(x) \doteq \sigma(\theta^\top x + b)$ for $\theta, x \in \mathbb{R}^d$ and $b \in \mathbb{R}$. They can also be interpreted as simple neural networks with a single artificial neuron. The approach of Rosenblatt applies the sign function as activation and its iterative learning-rate-free perceptron algorithm terminates in finite steps, for linearly separable data (Shalev-Shwartz and Ben-David, 2014).

For potentially non-linearly separable data and general activation functions, one can apply a least squares (LS) type approach. This however, typically leads to non-convex optimization problems. Approximate solutions can be achieved by stochastic gradient descent methods, e.g., by the celebrated backpropagation algorithm (LeCun, 1988).

We use the perceptron with activation function $\sigma(z) \doteq 2/(1 + e^{-z}) - 1$ to estimate the regression function of binary classification, in case of $\{-1, 1\}$ valued classes. Let us consider \mathcal{F}_0 , the model class of $\{f_{(\theta,b)}\}$ functions with $(\theta^\top, b)^\top \in \mathbb{R}^{d+1}$. Anthony and Bartlett (2009) showed that the pseudo-dimension of neural networks with fixed structure is finite, thus, as a special case, $V_{\mathcal{F}_0^+} < \infty$, implying that, by Theorem 4.4.3, our method constructs non-asymptotically exact confidence regions in \mathcal{F}_0 , which are strongly uniformly consistent in $\mathcal{L}_2(Q_x)$.

The perceptron with the logistic type activation function above differs from the logistic regression estimator in the used error criterion only. The perceptron typically uses the ERM estimator, whereas for logistic regression one needs to maximize the conditional likelihood function. In Section 4.5 we present numerical experiments to compare the corresponding confidence regions based on the presented resampling framework.

In Appendix B additional model classes, namely linear models, feed-forward neural networks and radial basis function networks, are considered as demonstrative examples. In these use cases the ERM-based method constructs exact confidence regions for the regression function for every sample size, all of which are strongly uniformly consistent.

4.4.4 The kNN Estimator

In some cases determining the ERM estimator is computationally intensive or infeasible. The flexibility of our resampling framework allows us to use any other feasible regression function estimator in these challenging cases.

In this section we apply the kNN estimator to construct strongly pointwise consistent confidence regions for a wide range of distributions of (X, Y) . We note that it is easy to extend our construction algorithm to local averaging kernel estimates (Nadaraya-Watson estimates) or partitioning estimates.

Let $\mathbb{X} \subseteq \mathbb{R}^d$ as above with the Euclidean metric. Given an i.i.d. sample $\{(X_i, Y_i)\}_{i=1}^n$, the kNN estimate is defined by

$$f_n(x) \doteq \frac{1}{k_n} \sum_{i=1}^n Y_i \mathbb{I}(X_i \in N(x, k_n)), \quad (4.20)$$

where $N(x, k_n)$ denotes the set of k_n closest points in $\{X_i\}_{i=1}^n$ to x . We assume that $\|X - X'\| = \|X - X''\|$ holds with probability zero for $i \neq j \in [n]$, where $\{X, X', X''\}$ are i.i.d. copies. This assumption is needed to define the k_n closest neighbors in $\{X_i\}_{i=1}^n$ Q_X -almost surely. Note that this assumption can be eliminated by using random tiebreaking for those $x \in \mathbb{X}$ and $\{X_i, X_j\}$ for which we have $\|X_i - x\| = \|X_j - x\|$. By (Györfi et al., 2002, Theorem 23.7) if $k_n/n \rightarrow 0$ and $k_n \rightarrow \infty$ as $n \rightarrow \infty$, then

$$\int \left(f_n(x) - f^*(x) \right)^2 dQ_X(x) \xrightarrow{a.s.} 0. \quad (4.21)$$

4.4.5 Neighbor-Based Ranking

We follow the procedure of Section 4.4.2 to generate alternative samples for a given model candidate. Then, we consider the kNN estimates for every dataset, i.e., let

$$f_{\theta,n}^{(j)}(x) \doteq \frac{1}{k_n} \sum_{i=1}^n Y_{i,j}(\theta) \mathbb{I}(X_i \in N(x, k_n)), \quad (4.22)$$

for all $j = 0, \dots, m-1$. Finally, we define the reference variables as in (4.16), the ranking function as in (4.10) and the confidence region for parameters q and m by

$$\Theta_n^{(2)} \doteq \left\{ \theta \in \Theta \mid \psi \left(\mathcal{D}_0^\pi, \{\mathcal{D}_j^\pi(\theta)\}_{j \neq 0} \right) \leq q \right\}. \quad (4.23)$$

The guarantees of the construction are summarized as:

Theorem 4.4.3. *Assume B1-B4, then for all $n \in \mathbb{N}^+$ and integers $1 \leq q \leq m$ we have*

$$\mathbb{P} \left(\theta^* \in \Theta_{q,n}^{(2)} \right) = \frac{q}{m}, \quad (4.24)$$

Further, if $q < m$, $k_n/n \rightarrow 0$, and there exists $\delta > 0$ such that $k_n^2/n^{(1+\delta)} \rightarrow \infty$ as $n \rightarrow \infty$, then $(\Theta_n^{(2)})_{n \in \mathbb{N}^+}$ is strongly pointwise consistent for every distribution of (X, Y) such that

$$\mathbb{P} \left(\|X - X'\|_2 \neq \|X - X''\|_2 \right) = 1, \quad (4.25)$$

where X' and X'' are independent copies of X .

The proof of this theorem can be found in (Tamás and Csáji, 2025). The result is distribution-free, because \mathcal{F}_0 may contain all possible regression functions and ties can be resolved by a random permutation. As before, the exact confidence of the coverage is non-asymptotically guaranteed and easily adjustable. The confidence regions shrink around the true parameter under mild statistical assumptions. The conditions on k_n can be satisfied, e.g., $k_n = \lfloor n^\beta \rfloor$ for $\beta \in (1/2, 1)$ are appropriate choices.

Similarly as before, we formulate the quantitative version of Theorem 4.4.1. In this case, we give an exponential bound on the exclusion probability for any $\theta \neq \theta^*$.

Theorem 4.4.4. *Assume that B1-B4 and $1 \leq q < m$ hold. In addition, $k_n/n \rightarrow 0$, and there exists $\delta > 0$ such that $k_n^2/n^{(1+\delta)} \rightarrow \infty$ as $n \rightarrow \infty$. For every distribution of (X, Y) such that $\mathbb{P}(\|X - X'\|_2 \neq \|X - X''\|_2) = 1$, where X' and X'' are independent copies of X , for a given $\theta \in \Theta$, $\theta \neq \theta^*$ there exists N_0 such that for $n \geq N_0$ we have*

$$\mathbb{P}(\theta \notin \Theta_n^{(2)}) \geq 1 - C_2 e^{-k_n^2 \lambda_2 / n}, \quad (4.26)$$

where C_2 depends only on m , the number of datasets, and λ_2 depends on $\kappa \doteq \|f_\theta - f^*\|_{\mathcal{Q}}$.

The proof of Theorem 4.4.4 is in (Tamás and Csáji, 2025). The required size of the dataset is not quantified for the exponential bounds. One can prove that n needs to be large enough to reduce the expected loss of the kNN estimator below $\kappa/8$, which is ensured by its weak consistency (Györfi et al., 2002, Theorem 6.1). However, this consistency can be arbitrarily slow, therefore determining a sufficient sample size for (4.26) comes at a price. A possible bound on the minimum sample size can be found via rate of convergence results, which restrict the model class (e.g., by requiring Lipschitzness) and make distributional assumptions (e.g., bounded support). For these results we refer to (Biau and Devroye, 2015, Theorem 14.5) and (Döring et al., 2017, Theorem 6).

4.5 Numerical Experiments

We carried out numerical experiments on synthetic datasets to demonstrate the suggested algorithms. In this example we considered a logistic model class defined as

$$\mathcal{F}_0 \doteq \left\{ f_{(a,b)}(x) \doteq 2/(1 + e^{-(b \cdot x + a)}) - 1 \mid a, b \in \mathbb{R} \right\} \quad (4.27)$$

and compared the perceptron-based (ERM-based) and the kNN-based method to the asymptotic normal confidence ellipsoids around the MLE, whose formulation is included in Appendix B.4. Output variable Y took values -1 and 1 with probability $1/2$ each. The conditional distribution of X on Y was Gaussian with mean Y and variance 1 , in which case $f^*(x) = 2/(1 + e^{-2x}) - 1$ and $[a_*, b_*] = [0, 2]$, thus the true parameter (vector) was included in \mathcal{F}_0 . The sample size was set to 500 and we used $m = 40$ for the resampling parameter. We tested the model parameters on a fine grid and plotted their relative ranks, which indicate the rejection probabilities of the test, see the color bar in Figure 4.1b. The results of the perceptron-based construction and the kNN-based construction are presented in Figure 4.1a and Figure 4.1b. The asymptotic confidence ellipsoids centered around the MLE are shown in Figure 4.1c.

Recall that our resampling framework can use any regression function estimator. Therefore, we tested an MLE-based algorithm which defines the reference variables, (4.16),

Figure 4.1: Families of confidence regions for the perceptron-based, the kNN-based and the MLE-based resampling methods are presented along with the asymptotic confidence ellipsoids based on an i.i.d. sample with $n = 500$ observations. The distribution of the output variables were discrete uniform and the conditional distribution of an input given the output was Gaussian with different mean values, $\mu_{-1} = -1$ and $\mu_{+1} = 1$. We tested a class of logistic functions parameterized by a and b , cf. (4.27). The true vector of model parameters was $[a_*, b_*] = [0, 2]$. The relative ranks are indicated with the colors for each parameter pair on a fine grid.

with the help of the MLE for all parameters. Figure 4.1d shows the results for this MLE-based resampling method. By Theorem 4.3.1 this variant constructs exact confidence regions for every finite sample similarly to the kNN-based and ERM-based versions.

The plots illustrate that our resampling framework produces comparable region estimates to asymptotic ellipsoids. Clearly, those methods which use a priori knowledge about the regression function’s parametric structure construct tighter bounds, if the prior information is correct. We also plotted the point estimates and the true parameters on the figures. Note that the kNN estimate was not included in \mathcal{F}_0 , therefore it is not marked.

We estimated the coverage probability of the regions with theoretical value 95% based

Table 4.1: Empirical coverage probabilities (estimated confidence levels) for $n = 20, 50$ and 100 observations based on $30\,000$ Monte Carlo trials for the perceptron-based, the kNN-based and the MLE-based resampling construction and the asymptotic confidence ellipsoids. The underlying conditional marginal distribution of X given Y was normal with mean Y and variance 1 .

n	Perceptron	kNN	MLE	Ellipsoid
20	95.19 %	95.21 %	95.10 %	96.50 %
50	94.90 %	94.84 %	95.07 %	96.22 %
100	94.83 %	95.01 %	94.88 %	95.86 %

Table 4.2: Empirical coverage probabilities (estimated confidence levels) for $n = 20, 50$ and 100 observations based on $30\,000$ Monte Carlo trials for the perceptron-based, the kNN-based and the MLE-based resampling construction and the asymptotic confidence ellipsoids. The underlying marginal distribution was uniform on $[-1, 1]$, using the same true regression function as in Table 4.1.

n	Perceptron	kNN	MLE	Ellipsoid
20	95.09 %	94.92 %	95.01 %	97.49 %
50	94.69 %	94.99 %	94.90 %	96.63 %
100	94.94 %	94.72 %	94.89 %	95.63 %

on $30\,000$ Monte Carlo experiments, which is by Hoeffding’s inequality sufficient to reach a 1% precision with probability at least 99%. We tested if the true parameter was included in the confidence region with hyperparameters $m = 20$ and $q = 1$, and estimated the confidence level by the frequency of inclusions. The kNN-based, the MLE-based and the perceptron-based constructions were all applied. Similarly, we tested if the true parameter was included in the asymptotic confidence ellipsoid with approximate confidence level 95% and computed the frequency of inclusions. We carried out tests for $n = 20, 50$ and 100 observations. We can see in Table 4.1 that the confidence levels of the asymptotic regions are conservative and higher than 96% for $n = 20$ and $n = 50$ instead of the desired 95%, while our exact methods are close to the theoretical value for every sample size.

We carried out another experiment, where the marginal distribution of the input was uniform on $[-1, 1]$, but the regression function and the model class remained the same. These results, shown in Table 4.2, validate that our resampling framework provides exact guarantees for any sample size, for all variants, as before. On the other hand, the coverage levels of the asymptotic confidence sets (column “Ellipsoid”) are inaccurate for small sample sizes, though they tend to the theoretical value (95%) as the sample size increases. We conclude that our non-asymptotically exact guarantee is preferable to the asymptotic one, since the latter is conservative for small samples, even if its prior assumptions hold.

4.6 CKME-Based Construction

Finally, we propose a CKME based method for which the main idea is to compute the empirical estimates of the conditional kernel mean map for all available samples, both the original and the alternatively generated ones, and compare these to the theoretical one determined by the regression function candidate. Again, the estimates based on the alternatively generated samples should converge to the theoretical conditional kernel mean map, which can be deduced from candidate function f_θ , while the estimate based on the original sample, \mathcal{D}_0 , converges to the theoretical one only if $f_\theta = f^*$. We assume that:

B7. Kernel ℓ is the naïve kernel, that is, $\ell(y_1, y_2) = \mathbb{I}(y_1 = y_2)$ for $y_1, y_2 \in \mathbb{Y}$ and \mathcal{G} is the corresponding (scalar-valued) RKHS.

B8. Kernel k is real-valued, measurable, bounded by C_k and $\Gamma = k \mathbf{Id}_{\mathcal{G}}$.

Assumption B8 is satisfied for most of the standard kernel functions, e.g., for the Gaussian and Laplacian kernel, if $\mathbb{X} \subseteq \mathbb{R}^d$.

We can observe that if the regression function candidate is given in binary classification, then the exact CKME for any parameter candidate θ takes the form that follows:

$$\begin{aligned} \mu_{Y(\theta)|X} &= (1 - \eta_{\theta}(X))\ell(\cdot, -1) + \eta_{\theta}(X)\ell(\cdot, 1) \quad \text{and} \\ \mu_{\theta}(x) &= (1 - \eta_{\theta}(x))\ell(\cdot, -1) + \eta_{\theta}(x)\ell(\cdot, 1) \quad Q_X\text{-a.s.}, \end{aligned} \tag{4.28}$$

where $\eta_{\theta}(x) = 1/2 \cdot (f_{\theta}(x) + 1)$, because by the reproducing property for all $g \in \mathcal{G}$ we have

$$\begin{aligned} &\langle (1 - \eta_{\theta}\ell(\cdot, -1) + \eta_{\theta}(X)\ell(\cdot, 1), g \rangle_{\mathcal{G}} \\ &= (1 - \eta_{\theta}(X))g(-1) + \eta_{\theta}(X)g(1) = \mathbb{E}[g(Y(\theta)) | X]. \end{aligned} \tag{4.29}$$

In particular $\mu^*(x) = (1 - \eta^*(x))\ell(\cdot, -1) + \eta^*(x)\ell(\cdot, 1)$. We use two methods to empirically estimate μ^* . First, the vector-valued kernelized regularized risk minimizer of Theorem 2.5.7 is used with $\lambda > 0$ to define

$$\hat{\mu}_j^{(1)}(\theta) \doteq \hat{\mu}_{n,\lambda}(\mathcal{D}_j(\theta)) \quad \text{for } j = 0, \dots, m-1. \tag{4.30}$$

Second, we rely on the intuitive form of (4.28) and estimate the conditional probability function η^* directly by any standard method (e.g., k -nearest neighbors) and let

$$\hat{\mu}_j^{(2)}(\theta) \doteq (1 - \hat{\eta}_j(\theta))\ell(\cdot, -1) + \hat{\eta}_j(\theta)\ell(\cdot, 1), \tag{4.31}$$

for $j = 0, \dots, m-1$, where $\hat{\eta}_j(\theta) = \hat{\eta}(\mathcal{D}_j(\theta))$ and $\hat{\eta}$ denotes an (arbitrary) estimator of η^* . The first approach follows our motivation by using a vector-valued RKHS and the user-chosen kernel Γ lets us adaptively control the possibly high-dimensional scalar product. The second technique relies on the used conditional probability function estimator, hence we can make use of a broad range of point estimators available for this problem. For brevity, we call the first approach vector-valued kernel test (VVKT) and the second approach point estimation based test (PET).

Let us define the ranking functions with the help of reference variables, which are estimates of the deviations between $\hat{\mu}_j^{(r)}$ and μ_{θ} in some norm for $r = 1, 2$ and $j = 0, \dots, m-1$. An intuitive norm to apply is the expected loss in $\|\cdot\|_{\mathcal{G}}$, i.e., for $\mu_{\theta}, \hat{\mu} \in L_2(\mathbb{X}, Q_X; \mathcal{G})$, ideally, we would want to consider the expected loss

$$\int_{\mathbb{X}} \|\mu_{\theta}(x) - \hat{\mu}(x)\|_{\mathcal{G}}^2 \, dQ_X(x). \tag{4.32}$$

The usage of this “metric” is justified by (Park and Muandet, 2022, Lemma 2.1). They

proved that for any estimator $\hat{\mu}$ and conditional kernel mean map μ_θ , we have

$$\int_{\mathbb{X}} \|\mu_\theta(x) - \hat{\mu}(x)\|_{\mathcal{G}}^2 dQ_x(x) = \mathcal{E}_s(\hat{\mu}) - \mathcal{E}_s(\mu_\theta), \quad (4.33)$$

where the right hand side is the excess risk of $\hat{\mu}$, cf. equation (2.53). The distribution of X is unknown, therefore the norm in (4.32) needs to be estimated, thus the reference variables and the ranking functions are constructed as

$$\begin{aligned} Z_j^{(r)}(\theta) &\doteq \frac{1}{n} \sum_{i=1}^n \|\mu_\theta(X_i) - \hat{\mu}_j^{(r)}(X_i)\|_{\mathcal{G}}^2, \\ \mathcal{R}_n^{(r)}(\theta) &\doteq 1 + \sum_{j=1}^{m-1} \mathbb{I} \left(Z_j^{(r)}(\theta) \prec_\pi Z_0^{(r)}(\theta) \right) \end{aligned} \quad (4.34)$$

for $j = 0, \dots, m-1$ and $r \in \{1, 2\}$, where r refers to the conditional kernel mean map estimators, (4.30) and (4.31). The confidence sets of the proposed tests are defined by

$$\Theta_n^{(2+r)} \doteq \left\{ \theta \in \Theta \mid \mathcal{R}_n^{(r)}(\theta) \leq q \right\} \text{ for } r = 1, 2. \quad (4.35)$$

Similarly as before, we reject θ if $Z_0^{(r)}(\theta)$ is too high in which case our original estimate is far from μ_θ . The main advantages of these confidence sets are summarized in the theorems that follow. We provide asymptotic guarantees for the first test based on:

B9. For $\hat{\mu}_{n,\lambda}$ we have for all $\theta \in \Theta$ that

$$\frac{1}{n} \sum_{i=1}^n \|\mu_\theta(X_i) - \hat{\mu}_{n,\lambda}(\mathcal{D}_n; X_i)\|_{\mathcal{G}}^2 \xrightarrow[n \rightarrow \infty]{a.s.} 0, \quad (4.36)$$

where $\mathcal{D}_n = \{(X_i, Y_i(\theta))\}_{i=1}^n$ is an i.i.d. sample with regression function f_θ .

That is, we assume that the used regularized risk minimizer is consistent in the above sense. Condition B9, although nontrivial, is however key in proving that a hypothesis test can preserve the favorable asymptotic behaviour of the point estimator while also non-asymptotically guaranteeing a user-chosen type I error probability. Proving that assumption B9 can hold is one of the main challenges of Chapter 5.

Theorem 4.6.1. Assume that B1-B3, B7 and B8 hold, then for all $n \in \mathbb{N}^+$ we have

$$\mathbb{P}(\theta^* \in \Theta_n^{(3)}) = \frac{q}{m}. \quad (4.37)$$

If B1-B3, B7-B9 and $1 \leq q < m$ hold, then for all $\theta \neq \theta^*$ we have

$$\mathbb{P} \left(\bigcap_{N=1}^{\infty} \bigcup_{n=N}^{\infty} \{\theta \in \Theta_n^{(3)}\} \right) = 0. \quad (4.38)$$

In other words, the theorem states that the confidence level of $\Theta_n^{(3)}$ and the confidence level of the corresponding hypothesis test are exactly γ . Moreover, if $\theta \neq \theta_*$, then a “false” regression function is (a.s.) accepted at most finitely many times. Consequently the pointwise convergence of the type II error probabilities to zero (as $n \rightarrow \infty$) follows from (B.54). The proof of Theorem 4.6.1 can be found in Appendix B.5.

A similar result holds for the second approach, for which we assume the consistency of $\hat{\eta}$ in the following sense:

B10. For all $\theta \in \Theta$ for conditional probability function estimator $\hat{\eta}$ we have

$$\frac{1}{n} \sum_{i=1}^n (\eta_\theta(X_i) - \hat{\eta}(\mathcal{D}_n; X_i))^2 \xrightarrow[n \rightarrow \infty]{a.s.} 0, \quad (4.39)$$

where $\mathcal{D}_n = \{(X_i, Y_i(\theta))\}_{i=1}^n$ is an i.i.d. sample with conditional probability function η_θ .

Condition B10 holds for a broad range of conditional probability estimators (e.g., kNN, various kernel estimates), however most of these techniques make stronger assumptions on the data generating distribution than we do. As in Theorem 4.6.1 the presented stochastic guarantee for the type I error is non-asymptotic, while for the type II error it is asymptotic. The proof of this theorem can be found in (Tamás and Csáji, 2022).

Theorem 4.6.2. Assume that B1-B3, B7 and B8 hold, then for all $n \in \mathbb{N}^+$ we have

$$\mathbb{P}(\theta^* \in \Theta_n^{(4)}) = \frac{q}{m}. \quad (4.40)$$

If B1-B3, B7, B8, B10 and $1 \leq q < m$ hold, then for all $\theta \neq \theta^*$ we have

$$\mathbb{P}\left(\bigcap_{N=1}^{\infty} \bigcup_{n=N}^{\infty} \{\theta \in \Theta_n^{(4)}\}\right) = 0. \quad (4.41)$$

4.7 Numerical Experiments

The CKME-based methods are illustrated with numerical experiments on a synthetic dataset. The one-dimensional inputs were uniformly distributed on the $[-1, 1]$ interval and the true regression function was

$$f_*(x) \doteq \frac{p_* \cdot e^{-(x-\mu_1)^2/\lambda_*} - (1-p_*)e^{-(x-\mu_2)^2/\lambda_*}}{p_* \cdot e^{-(x-\mu_1)^2/\lambda_*} + (1-p_*)e^{-(x-\mu_2)^2/\lambda_*}}, \quad (4.42)$$

where $p_* = 0.5$, $\lambda_* = 1$, $\mu_1 = 1$ and $\mu_2 = -1$. This form of the regression function is the reparametrization of a logistic regression model, which is an archetypal approach for binary classification. The same formula holds for the regression function if two Gaussian classes are mixed together. The translation parameters (μ_1, μ_2) were considered to be

Figure 4.2: The normalized ranks of VVKTs and PETs are indicated with the darkness of points on a grid based on a sample of size $n = 50$ and resampling parameter $m = 40$.

Figure 4.3: The ranks of the reference variables are shown as functions of the sample size for two arbitrarily chosen “false” candidate functions.

known, therefore we could illustrate the confidence sets on two-dimensional plots. Sample size n was set to 50 and resampling parameter m was 40. We tested parameter pairs of (p, λ) on a fine grid on $[0.2, 0.8] \times [0.5, 1.5]$ with stepsize 0.01. The confidence sets are illustrated with the generated rank statistics for every test parameter on Figures 4.2a and 4.2b. These normalized values are indicated with the colors of the points. Kernel k was a Gaussian with parameter $\sigma = 1/2$ for the VVKTs and we used kNN-estimates for PETs with $k = \lfloor \sqrt{n} \rfloor$ neighbors. We illustrated the consistency of our algorithms by plotting the ranks of the reference variables for parameters $(0.3, 1.3)$ and $(0.4, 1.2)$ for various sample

sizes in Figures 4.3a and 4.3b. We took the average rank over several experiments for each dataset size. Clearly, the reference variable corresponding to the original sample tends to be the greatest, though the rate of convergence depends on the particular “false” candidate.

4.8 Discussion

In this chapter we assessed the uncertainty of regression function estimators for binary classification. The regression function is one of the key objects in this area, because it is not only sufficient to derive an optimal classifier (using the zero-one risk), but can also be used to determine the probability of misclassification for any given input point. The uncertainty of regression function estimators is quantified with confidence regions. We present a universal resampling framework, which provides exact stochastic guarantees for finding the true underlying regression function under the i.i.d. assumption. One of the key ideas was to test each candidate by generating alternative samples and comparing those to the original dataset. There are several strengths of the proposed framework. Most importantly, our method provides finite-sample guarantees for the coverage probability of the true regression function. Additionally, the attained stochastic bounds are distribution-free, i.e., only the i.i.d. assumption is used to produce a confidence region for the true regression function in a model class \mathcal{F}_0 which is broad enough. The distribution of the inputs can be arbitrary and if \mathcal{F}_0 contains every possible regression function, then the joint distribution of the sample is not restricted. Furthermore, the presented algorithm can reach any (rational) confidence level. If a priori knowledge is available, e.g., we have information about the shape of the regression function, then we can adopt the ranking function to the problem specific conditions by choosing an efficient point estimator. Finally, the framework can be applied for hypothesis testing, in which case the probability of the type I error is explicitly determined for any finite sample. These can make our framework a promising choice for many real-world UQ problems.

Beside the finite sample guarantees, we investigated the asymptotic properties of the constructed regions. Strong pointwise consistency and strong uniform consistency were studied under mild statistical assumptions. We suggested four specific ranking functions with stochastically guaranteed asymptotic properties.

The first two methods were based on regression function estimation. One of the main ideas was to test each parameter θ , by estimating the regression function from the available datasets. Since the alternative samples are generated with the help of θ , the corresponding estimates should tend to the regression function candidate, f_θ , while the original sample-based estimate should converge to f^* . Our rank tests statistically detect this difference. We introduced two main approaches, however, we emphasize that our scheme can be combined with any point estimator.

The first method was based on ERM and VC theory. We used LS estimates in the algorithm and proved that if the model class has finite pseudo-dimension and the parameterization is inverse Lipschitz, then the constructed regions are strongly uniformly

consistent. Additionally, we proved an exponential PAC bound, to quantify the probability of inclusion in a given ball around the true parameter. For illustration, the perceptron was revisited as an LS estimator.

The condition regarding the model class was weakened for the second method. We allowed \mathcal{F}_0 to contain all measurable functions bounded in $[-1, 1]$ by using the kNN estimator. Strong pointwise consistency was proved for this variant of our algorithm, which implies that any “bad” parameter is eventually excluded from the confidence regions as the sample size tends to infinity. We quantified the probability of exclusion for a fixed parameter other than θ^* with an exponential PAC bound. One of the main strengths of this latter approach is that no prior knowledge is assumed regarding the model class, hence the second approach is completely distribution-free.

We presented numerical experiments to illustrate our new algorithms. The results showed that our framework provides comparable regions to asymptotic ellipsoids. It was demonstrated that the theoretical guarantees are tighter in the resampling framework than in the asymptotic setup, i.e., the confidence level is exact in case of the newly proposed methods, whereas the asymptotic theory usually provides conservative estimates.

Additionally, we introduced two CKME based rank tests for which we proved pointwise consistency under mild statistical assumptions. The first method used a vector-valued regularized risk minimizer to estimate the conditional kernel mean map, while the second approach relied on a conditional probability function estimator. The CKME-based confidence regions were illustrated with numerical experiments.

Chapter 5

Conditional Kernel Mean Embeddings Estimation

In this chapter we present the results of (Tamás and Csáji, 2024). First, we develop a recursive scheme, which is proved to be strongly consistent for (unconditional) KMEs. Then, we introduce a recursive estimator of the conditional kernel mean map. Our algorithm is formulated in a flexible offline manner in such a way that the online algorithm is also covered. We prove the weak L_2 consistency of a general local averaging method in locally compact Polish spaces under mild statistical assumptions. The general result is applied to prove the strong consistency of local averaging kernel estimates with a (measurable) nonnegative, bounded and symmetric smoother sequence. In the final theorem only a structural condition on the probability of small balls is posed. Finally, we apply our results for three archetypal cases. We deduce universal consistency for Euclidean input spaces, Riemannian manifolds and special locally compact subsets of Hilbert spaces.

5.1 Theoretical Background

In statistical learning we work with probability distributions on (possibly high-dimensional or nonlinear) measurable sample spaces. KMEs offer a neat representation for dealing with distributions by mapping them into an RKHS. These embeddings were introduced in (Berlinet and Thomas-Agnan, 2004; Smola et al., 2007). In ML the conditional distribution of an output w.r.t. some input plays a key role. In these problems the concept of CKME is more adequate. The notion of CKME was first recognized in (Song et al., 2009), then a refined definition was given in (Song et al., 2013). Its rigorous measure theoretic background was presented in (Klebanov et al., 2020; Park and Muandet, 2020). These concepts build on the notion of Bochner integrals and conditional expectation in Banach spaces. We included a brief introductory material about these topics in Appendix C based on the seminal works of Pisier (2016); Hytönen et al. (2016).

In this chapter, we follow the general distribution-free framework of Györfi et al. (2002). It is recognized that estimating the conditional kernel mean map is a particular

vector-valued regression problem, which was already studied in (Ramsay and Silverman, 2005; Bosq and Delecroix, 1985; Dabo-Niang and Rhomari, 2009; Forzani et al., 2012; Brogat-Motte et al., 2022). However, it is still challenging to provide sufficient conditions for strong L_2 (mean square) consistency that can be applied in practice. We also build on the theory of stochastic approximation (Kushner and Yin, 2003; Ljung et al., 2012). Our core algorithm uses a stochastic update in each iteration. The presented method was motivated by the celebrated stochastic gradient descent algorithm, cf. (Bertsekas and Tsitsiklis, 1996, Proposition 4.2). The update term of our recursive algorithm is a modified gradient of an empirical surrogate loss function.

Our main contribution is a weakly and strongly consistent recursive algorithm for estimating the conditional kernel mean map under general structural assumptions. We present and prove a generalized version of Stone’s theorem (Stone, 1977), motivated by the recursive form in (Györfi et al., 2002, Theorem 25.1). Our generalization is twofold. We deal with general locally compact Polish input spaces and allow the output space to be Hilbertian. Our main assumption is that the measure of metric balls goes to zero slowly w.r.t. the radius. In (Forzani et al., 2012) a similar consistency result is proved, however the authors of that paper do not deal with functional outputs and also require the so-called Besicovitch condition to hold on the regression function. In (Dabo-Niang and Rhomari, 2009) sufficient conditions for L_2 consistency are given for vector-valued regression, however, in this paper a differentiation condition is required for the regression function and also the shrinkage rate of the small ball probabilities is bounded from below.

We highlight some potential application domains of the ideas. Based on the theory of KMEs and CKMEs, a rich variety of applications were introduced. KMEs are efficiently used, for example, in graphical models (Song et al., 2013), Bayesian inference (Fukumizu et al., 2013), dynamical systems (Song et al., 2009), reinforcement learning (Grünewälder et al., 2012), causal inference (Schölkopf et al., 2015) hypothesis testing for independence (Gretton et al., 2008; Gretton and Györfi, 2008; Gretton et al., 2012) and conditional independence (Fukumizu et al., 2007; Zhang et al., 2011). In Chapter 4 CKMEs were used to construct confidence regions for the regression function of binary classification, cf. (Csáji and Tamás, 2019) and (Tamás and Csáji, 2022).

5.2 Kernel Mean Embeddings of Distributions

Kernel methods offer an elegant approach to deal with abstract sample spaces. One only needs to specify a similarity measure on the space via the kernel function to provide a geometrical structure for the learning problem. In fact, every symmetric, positive definite function, a.k.a. kernel, defines an RKHS, cf. Theorem 2.5.2. The user-chosen kernel function also determines a natural projection from the sample space into the RKHS. The projected values of sample points are called feature vectors, or features. This projection can be easily extended to (probability) measures to define KMEs, cf. Definition 2.5.4.

5.2.1 Statistical Framework

Let us consider a metric space \mathbb{X} and let \mathcal{X} denote its Borel σ -algebra. Let $(\mathbb{Y}, \mathcal{Y})$ be a (nonempty) measurable space. We consider a random pair (X, Y) in the product space $\mathbb{X} \times \mathbb{Y}$ endowed with the product σ -algebra $\mathcal{X} \otimes \mathcal{Y}$. We denote the joint distribution of (X, Y) by Q (or $Q_{X,Y}$) and the corresponding marginal distributions by Q_X and Q_Y . In practice, distribution Q is usually unknown, however, similarly as before we assume:

C1. *Given an i.i.d. sample $\{(X_i, Y_i)\}_{i=1}^n$ from Q .*

We have already defined the KMEs of probability distributions in Definition 2.5.4. With a somewhat imprecise terminology, we also talk about the KME of a random variable into an RKHS, by which we mean taking the KME of its distribution. We consider a kernel ℓ defined for values of output variable Y . Explanatory variable X will only be used for the conditional variant of KME to generate the conditioning σ -algebra, consequently, for the unconditional KME, only the output variable is used.

In the subsequent sections we focus on CKMEs. Recall, that the CKME of Y with respect to X into an RKHS \mathcal{G} is the conditional expectation of the random feature defined by the kernel and variable Y with respect to the σ -algebra generated by X , i.e., a CKME is a random feature vector in \mathcal{G} measurable to some explanatory variable. The main object for CKME is the conditional kernel mean map, μ^* , which maps the explanatory points into RKHS \mathcal{G} . This function maps almost every input point to the KME of the conditional distribution given that input. For a linear kernel one can recover the regression function as a particular conditional kernel mean map. When X and Y are independent, μ^* is a constant function mapping every input into the unconditional KME of Y . The main result of this chapter is a strongly consistent recursive estimator of μ^* .

5.2.2 Kernel Mean Embeddings of Marginal Distributions

Let ℓ be a (real-valued, symmetric, positive definite) kernel on $\mathbb{Y} \times \mathbb{Y}$. Let \mathcal{G} denote the corresponding (unique) RKHS. Recall that we have $\ell(\cdot, y) \in \mathcal{G}$ for all $y \in \mathbb{Y}$ and the reproducing property holds, i.e., for all $g \in \mathcal{G}$ and $y \in \mathbb{Y}$ we have

$$\langle g, \ell(\cdot, y) \rangle_{\mathcal{G}} = g(y). \tag{5.1}$$

We consider only separable RKHSs. One can observe that if \mathbb{Y} is a separable topological space and kernel ℓ is continuous, then the separability of \mathcal{G} follows immediately ([Steinwart and Christmann, 2008](#), Lemma 4.33). Specifically, we assume

C2'. *Kernel ℓ is measurable, $\mathbb{E}[\sqrt{\ell(Y, Y)}] < \infty$, and RKHS \mathcal{G} is separable.*

In this case, by the theorem of Pettis ([Hytönen et al., 2016](#), Theorem 1.1.20), $\ell(\cdot, Y) : \Omega \rightarrow \mathcal{G}$ is also measurable. Then, we can embed distribution Q_Y into RKHS \mathcal{G} by

$$\mu_Y \doteq \mathbb{E}[\ell(\cdot, Y)], \tag{5.2}$$

where the expectation is a Bochner integral. Recall that if C2' holds, then by the Riesz representation theorem $\mu_Y \in \mathcal{G}$ and for all $g \in \mathcal{G}$, we have

$$\langle \mu_Y, g \rangle_{\mathcal{G}} = \mathbb{E}[g(Y)], \quad (5.3)$$

that is, μ_Y is the representer of the expectation functional on \mathcal{G} (Smola et al., 2007).

From an i.i.d. sample $\{Y_i\}_{i=1}^n$, having distribution Q_Y , we can estimate the KME of Q_Y with the empirical mean estimator, that is,

$$\bar{\mu}_n \doteq \frac{1}{n} \sum_{i=1}^n \ell(\cdot, Y_i). \quad (5.4)$$

By the strong law of large numbers, $\bar{\mu}_n \rightarrow \mu_Y$ almost surely (Taylor, 1978). We refer to (Tolstikhin et al., 2017, Proposition A.1.) to quantify the convergence rate of this estimate:

Theorem 5.2.1. *Let $\{Y_i\}_{i=1}^n$ be an i.i.d. sample from distribution Q_Y on a separable topological space \mathbb{Y} . Assume that $\ell(\cdot, y)$ is continuous and there exists $C_\ell > 0$ such that $\ell(y, y) \leq C_\ell$ for all $y \in \mathbb{Y}$. Then, for all $\delta \in (0, 1)$ with probability at least $1 - \delta$, we have*

$$\|\mu_Y - \bar{\mu}_n\|_{\mathcal{G}} \leq \sqrt{\frac{C_\ell}{n}} + \sqrt{\frac{2 C_\ell \log(1/\delta)}{n}}. \quad (5.5)$$

It is also proved that this rate is minimax for a broad class of distributions. Note that only the measurability of $\ell(\cdot, y)$ is used in the proof of Tolstikhin et al. (2017).

5.2.3 Recursive Estimation of Kernel Mean Embeddings

As in the scalar case, these empirical estimates can be computed recursively by

$$\bar{\mu}_0 \doteq 0, \quad \bar{\mu}_n \doteq \frac{n-1}{n} \bar{\mu}_{n-1} + \frac{1}{n} \ell(\cdot, Y_n) = \bar{\mu}_{n-1} + \frac{1}{n} (\ell(\cdot, Y_n) - \hat{\mu}_{n-1}) \quad (5.6)$$

for $n \in \mathbb{N}^+$. More generally, we can use some possibly random stepsize (or learning-rate) sequence (a_n) , taking values in $(0, 1)$, and apply the refined recursion defined by

$$\hat{\mu}_0 \doteq 0 \text{ and } \hat{\mu}_n \doteq \hat{\mu}_{n-1} - a_n (\hat{\mu}_{n-1} - \ell(\cdot, Y_n)), \quad (5.7)$$

for $n \in \mathbb{N}^+$. In (Tamás and Csáji, 2024) we prove the strong consistency of $(\hat{\mu}_n)$ by applying Theorem 1.9 of (Ljung et al., 2012):

Theorem 5.2.2. *Let Y_1, Y_2, \dots be an i.i.d. sequence, $C_\ell > 0$ be a constant such that $\ell(y, y) \leq C_\ell$, for all $y \in \mathbb{Y}$, and assume C2'. Let $(\hat{\mu}_n)$ be the estimate sequence defined in (5.7). If $a_n \geq 0$, $\sum_n a_n^2 < \infty$ and $\sum_n a_n = \infty$ (a.s.), then $\hat{\mu}_n \rightarrow \mu_Y$, as $n \rightarrow \infty$, a.s.*

5.3 Conditional Kernel Mean Embeddings

If the KME of Q_Y exists, then for a given σ -algebra one can take the conditional expectation of $\ell(\cdot, Y)$. We recall that the CKME of Y given X in RKHS \mathcal{G} is a $\sigma(X)$ measurable random element in \mathcal{G} defined by

$$\mu_{Y|X} \doteq \mathbb{E}[\ell(\cdot, Y) | X]. \quad (5.8)$$

It is known that the conditional expectation uniquely exists under C2' and there is a Q_X -a.s. well-defined measurable map $\mu^* : \mathbb{X} \rightarrow \mathcal{G}$ such that $\mu_{Y|X} = \mu^*(X)$ (a.s.).

5.3.1 Universal Consistency

The main challenge addressed in this chapter is to construct an estimator of μ^* with strong stochastic guarantees. Since the probability distribution of the given sample is unknown, in general our estimate will not be equal to μ^* in finite steps. In order to measure the loss of an estimate sequence, one may choose from several error criteria. We use the vector-valued L_2 risk with respect to Q_X to quantify our performance. The main reason leading to this choice of L_2 criterion is that conditional expectation is a projection in an L_2 space. We strengthen our assumption to ensure that the examined functions are included in the appropriate Bochner space, cf. Definition C.1.2.

C2. Kernel ℓ is measurable, $\mathbb{E}[\ell(Y, Y)] < \infty$, and RKHS \mathcal{G} is separable.

Lemma 5.3.1. *If C2 holds, then $\mu^* \in L_2(\mathbb{X}, Q_X; \mathcal{G})$.*

Proof. We can see that from C2 it follows immediately that $\ell(\cdot, Y) \in L_2(\Omega, \mathbb{P}; \mathcal{G})$ because

$$\int_{\Omega} \|\ell(\cdot, Y)\|_{\mathcal{G}}^2 d\mathbb{P} = \mathbb{E}[\ell(Y, Y)] < \infty. \quad (5.9)$$

Moreover, by (C.11), (Hytönen et al., 2016, Prop. 2.6.31.), we have that

$$\begin{aligned} \int_{\mathbb{X}} \|\mu^*(x)\|_{\mathcal{G}}^2 dQ_X(x) &= \mathbb{E}[\|\mu^*(X)\|_{\mathcal{G}}^2] = \mathbb{E}[\|\mathbb{E}[\ell(\cdot, Y) | X]\|_{\mathcal{G}}^2] \\ &\leq \mathbb{E}[\mathbb{E}[\|\ell(\cdot, Y)\|_{\mathcal{G}}^2 | X]] = \mathbb{E}[\ell(Y, Y)] < \infty, \end{aligned} \quad (5.10)$$

hence $\mu^* \in L_2(\mathbb{X}, Q_X; \mathcal{G})$. □

For scalar-valued regression, if $\mathbb{E}[Y^2] < \infty$ holds, then it is known that the conditional expectation is an orthogonal projection to $L_2(\Omega, \sigma(X), \mathbb{P}|_{\sigma(X)})$, where $\sigma(X)$ is the σ -algebra generated by X and $\mathbb{P}|_{\sigma(X)}$ is the restriction of \mathbb{P} to $\sigma(X)$. Similarly, Park and Muandet (2020, Theorem 4.2) proved that:

Lemma 5.3.2. *Under C2, conditional kernel mean embedding $\mu^*(X)$ is an orthogonal projection of $\ell(\cdot, Y)$ to $L_2(\Omega, \sigma(X), \mathbb{P}|_{\sigma(X)}; \mathcal{G})$.*

Proof. For any $\mu \in L_2(\mathbb{X}, Q_X; \mathcal{G})$ by (Park and Muandet, 2020, Theorem 4.2) it holds that

$$\begin{aligned}
 \mathcal{E}_s(\mu) &\doteq \mathbb{E} \left[\|\ell(\cdot, Y) - \mu(X)\|_{\mathcal{G}}^2 \right] = \mathbb{E} \left[\|\ell(\cdot, Y) - \mu^*(X) + \mu^*(X) - \mu(X)\|_{\mathcal{G}}^2 \right] \\
 &= \mathbb{E} \left[\|\ell(\cdot, Y) - \mu^*(X)\|_{\mathcal{G}}^2 \right] + \mathbb{E} \left[\|\mu^*(X) - \mu(X)\|_{\mathcal{G}}^2 \right] \\
 &\quad + 2 \mathbb{E} \left[\mathbb{E} \left[\langle \ell(\cdot, Y) - \mu^*(X), \mu^*(X) - \mu(X) \rangle_{\mathcal{G}} \mid X \right] \right] \\
 &= \mathbb{E} \left[\|\ell(\cdot, Y) - \mu^*(X)\|_{\mathcal{G}}^2 \right] + \mathbb{E} \left[\|\mu^*(X) - \mu(X)\|_{\mathcal{G}}^2 \right] \\
 &\quad + 2 \mathbb{E} \left[\langle \mathbb{E}[\ell(\cdot, Y) \mid X] - \mu^*(X), \mu^*(X) - \mu(X) \rangle_{\mathcal{G}} \right] \\
 &= \mathbb{E} \left[\|\ell(\cdot, Y) - \mu^*(X)\|_{\mathcal{G}}^2 \right] + \mathbb{E} \left[\|\mu^*(X) - \mu(X)\|_{\mathcal{G}}^2 \right].
 \end{aligned} \tag{5.11}$$

Thus, μ^* minimizes \mathcal{E}_s in $L_2(\mathbb{X}, Q_X; \mathcal{G})$. \square

Consequently, $\mathbb{E}[\|\ell(\cdot, Y) - \mu^*(X)\|_{\mathcal{G}}^2]$ is independent of μ , thus it is reasonable to apply $\mathbb{E}[\|\mu^*(X) - \mu(X)\|_{\mathcal{G}}^2]$ as an error criterion. This argument motivates the following notions of $L_2(\mathbb{X}, Q_X; \mathcal{G})$ consistency. Recall that Q_X is the marginal distribution of Q w.r.t. X .

Definition 5.3.1. Let $(\mu_n)_{n \in \mathbb{N}}$ be a (random) estimate sequence for μ^* . The (random) L_2 error (or more precisely $L_2(\mathbb{X}, Q_X; \mathcal{G})$ error) of μ_n is defined by

$$\int_{\mathbb{X}} \|\mu^*(x) - \mu_n(x)\|_{\mathcal{G}}^2 dQ_X(x). \tag{5.12}$$

We say that $(\mu_n)_{n \in \mathbb{N}}$ is weakly consistent for the distribution of (X, Y) , if as $n \rightarrow \infty$,

$$\mathbb{E} \left[\int_{\mathbb{X}} \|\mu^*(x) - \mu_n(x)\|_{\mathcal{G}}^2 dQ_X(x) \right] \longrightarrow 0. \tag{5.13}$$

We say that $(\mu_n)_{n \in \mathbb{N}}$ is strongly consistent for the distribution of (X, Y) , if as $n \rightarrow \infty$,

$$\int_{\mathbb{X}} \|\mu^*(x) - \mu_n(x)\|_{\mathcal{G}}^2 dQ_X(x) \xrightarrow{a.s.} 0. \tag{5.14}$$

One can see that strong consistency does not necessarily imply weak consistency, indeed neither of these two consistency notions imply the other. Nevertheless, knowing that an estimator is weakly consistent is of great help to also prove its strong consistency.

Note that it can happen that an estimate sequence is consistent for some distributions and inconsistent for other distributions of (X, Y) . We say that (μ_n) is universally weakly (strongly) consistent if it is weakly (strongly) consistent for all possible distributions of (X, Y) . It is a somewhat surprising fact that there exist such estimators for $\mathbb{R}^d \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$ type regression functions (Stone, 1977), for example, local averaging adaptive methods such as kNN, several kernel-based methods and various partitioning rules are proved to be universally consistent (Györfi et al., 2002).

Recently, Hanneke et al. (2020) proved that there exists a universally strongly consistent classifier called OptiNet for any separable metric space and Györfi and Weiss (2021)

constructed a universally consistent classification rule called proto-nearest neighbor for multiclass classification in metric spaces whenever the space admits a universally consistent estimator. For Banach space valued regression in semi-metric spaces [Dabo-Niang and Rhomari \(2009\)](#) constructed estimates with asymptotic bounds under some differentiation condition on the conditional expectation function and [Forzani et al. \(2012\)](#) proved consistency under the Besicovitch condition. Nevertheless, it is still an open question whether there exist universally consistent estimators under more general conditions (e.g., for Hilbert space valued regression).

5.3.2 Generalization of Stone’s Theorem

In this section, we present a generalization of Stone’s theorem ([Stone, 1977](#)) for conditional kernel mean map estimates on locally compact Polish spaces¹. This theorem will be our main theoretical tool to prove consistency results for our new recursive kernel algorithm. We consider local averaging methods of the general form

$$\mu_n(x) \doteq \sum_{i=1}^n W_{n,i}(x) \ell(\cdot, Y_i), \quad (5.15)$$

for $\mathbb{E}[\ell(\cdot, Y) | X = x]$, on a locally compact Polish space (\mathbb{X}, ϱ) . A Polish space gives a convenient setup for probability theory and locally compactness is required because of Lemma D.1.4. We use the fact that the set of compactly supported continuous functions is dense in $L_2(\mathbb{X}, Q_x)$ for every probability measure Q_x when \mathbb{X} is locally compact, see Theorem D.1.1. We deal with data-dependent probability weight functions $W_{n,i}(x)$ for $n \in \mathbb{N}^+$ and $i \in [n]$, i.e., we assume that for all $n \in \mathbb{N}^+$, weight $W_{n,i}(x)$ is nonnegative for all $i \in [n]$ and $\sum_{i=1}^n W_{n,i}(x) = 1$ for all $x \in \mathbb{X}$. These are somewhat stronger conditions compared to the original theorem of Stone, however, in practice they are usually satisfied and they simplify the proof. For several well-known methods (e.g. kNN, partitioning rules, Nadaraya–Watson estimates) these assumptions hold immediately.

Theorem 5.3.3. *Let (\mathbb{X}, ϱ) be a locally compact Polish space and let \mathcal{X} be the Borel σ -algebra on \mathbb{X} . Assume C1 and C2. Let $\mu^*(x) \doteq \mathbb{E}[\ell(\cdot, Y) | X = x]$ and*

$$\mu_n(x) \doteq \sum_{i=1}^n W_{n,i}(x) \ell(\cdot, Y_i). \quad (5.16)$$

Assume that:

(i) *For all $n \in \mathbb{N}^+$, $i \in [n]$ and $x \in \mathbb{X}$, we have*

$$0 \leq W_{n,i}(x) \leq 1, \quad \text{and} \quad \sum_{i=1}^n W_{n,i}(x) = 1. \quad (5.17)$$

¹A Polish space is a separable, completely metrizable topological space; as the specific choice of the metric is unimportant for the problems studied in this work, we fix an arbitrary metric ϱ which is compatible with the topology of our space.

(ii) There exists $c > 0$ such that for all $f : \mathbb{X} \rightarrow \mathbb{R}_+$ with $\mathbb{E}[f(X)] < \infty$, where \mathbb{R}_+ denotes the set of nonnegative real numbers, we have

$$\mathbb{E} \left[\sum_{i=1}^n W_{n,i}(X) f(X_i) \right] \leq c \mathbb{E}[f(X)]. \quad (5.18)$$

(iii) For all $\delta > 0$, we have

$$\lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} \mathbb{E} \left[\sum_{i=1}^n W_{n,i}(X) \mathbb{I}(\varrho(X_i, X) > \delta) \right] = 0. \quad (5.19)$$

(iv) The convergence that follows holds for the weight functions:

$$\lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} \mathbb{E} \left[\sum_{i=1}^n W_{n,i}^2(X) \right] = 0. \quad (5.20)$$

Then, estimate sequence (μ_n) is weakly consistent, that is,

$$\lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} \mathbb{E} \int_{\mathbb{X}} \|\mu_n(x) - \mu^*(x)\|_{\mathcal{G}}^2 dQ_X(x) = 0. \quad (5.21)$$

Condition (i) ensures that $\{W_{n,i}\}_{i=1}^n$ are probability weights for all $n \in \mathbb{N}^+$. Assumption (ii) intuitively says that the L_1 norm of the local averaging estimate is at most some positive constant times the L_1 norm of the estimated function whenever there is no noise on the observations, i.e., when $Y_i = f(X_i)$. Condition (iii) guarantees that asymptotically only those inputs affect the estimate at a point x that are close to x . Condition (iv) ensures that the individual weights vanish as the sample size goes to infinity.

Proof. The proof is based on the proof of Stone (1977) presented in (Györfi et al., 2002). By first using $(a + b)^2 \leq 2a^2 + 2b^2$, we have

$$\begin{aligned} & \mathbb{E} \left[\|\mu_n(X) - \mu^*(X)\|_{\mathcal{G}}^2 \right] \\ & \leq 2 \mathbb{E} \left[\left\| \sum_{i=1}^n W_{n,i}(X) (\ell(\cdot, Y_i) - \mu^*(X_i)) \right\|_{\mathcal{G}}^2 \right] + 2 \mathbb{E} \left[\left\| \sum_{i=1}^n W_{n,i}(X) (\mu^*(X_i) - \mu^*(X)) \right\|_{\mathcal{G}}^2 \right]. \end{aligned} \quad (5.22)$$

Then, the application of Lemma 5.3.4 and Lemma 5.3.5 completes the proof. \square

Lemma 5.3.4. Under the conditions of Theorem 5.3.3, we have

$$\mathbb{E} \left[\left\| \sum_{i=1}^n W_{n,i}(X) (\mu^*(X_i) - \mu^*(X)) \right\|_{\mathcal{G}}^2 \right] \xrightarrow{n \rightarrow \infty} 0. \quad (5.23)$$

Proof. Let us use the following notation

$$J_n \doteq \mathbb{E} \left[\left\| \sum_{i=1}^n W_{n,i}(X) (\mu^*(X_i) - \mu^*(X)) \right\|_{\mathcal{G}}^2 \right]. \quad (5.24)$$

By Theorem D.1.1 there exists a function $\tilde{\mu}^*$ which is bounded and continuous and

$$\mathbb{E} \left[\|\mu^*(X) - \tilde{\mu}^*(X)\|_{\mathcal{G}}^2 \right] < \varepsilon. \quad (5.25)$$

Recall that by the theorem of Heine and Cantor, Theorem D.1.5, a continuous function with compact support is always uniformly continuous. Using the convexity of $\|\cdot\|_{\mathcal{G}}$ and also the elementary fact that $(a + b + c)^2 \leq 3a^2 + 3b^2 + 3c^2$ for every triplet in \mathbb{R}^3 yield

$$\begin{aligned} J_n &= \mathbb{E} \left[\left\| \sum_{i=1}^n W_{n,i}(X) (\mu^*(X_i) - \mu^*(X)) \right\|_{\mathcal{G}}^2 \right] \\ &\leq \mathbb{E} \left[\left(\sum_{i=1}^n W_{n,i}(X) \|\mu^*(X_i) - \mu^*(X)\|_{\mathcal{G}} \right)^2 \right] \\ &\leq \mathbb{E} \left[\sum_{i=1}^n W_{n,i}(X) \|\mu^*(X_i) - \mu^*(X)\|_{\mathcal{G}}^2 \right] \\ &\leq 3\mathbb{E} \left[\sum_{i=1}^n W_{n,i}(X) \|\mu^*(X_i) - \tilde{\mu}^*(X_i)\|_{\mathcal{G}}^2 \right] \\ &\quad + 3\mathbb{E} \left[\sum_{i=1}^n W_{n,i}(X) \|\tilde{\mu}^*(X_i) - \tilde{\mu}^*(X)\|_{\mathcal{G}}^2 \right] \\ &\quad + 3\mathbb{E} \left[\sum_{i=1}^n W_{n,i}(X) \|\tilde{\mu}^*(X) - \mu^*(X)\|_{\mathcal{G}}^2 \right] \\ &\doteq 3J_n^{(1)} + 3J_n^{(2)} + 3J_n^{(3)}. \end{aligned} \quad (5.26)$$

We bound these three terms separately. For any $\delta > 0$ one can see that

$$\begin{aligned} J_n^{(2)} &= \mathbb{E} \left[\sum_{i=1}^n W_{n,i}(X) \|\tilde{\mu}^*(X_i) - \tilde{\mu}^*(X)\|_{\mathcal{G}}^2 \mathbb{I}(\varrho(X_i, X) > \delta) \right] \\ &\quad + \mathbb{E} \left[\sum_{i=1}^n W_{n,i}(X) \|\tilde{\mu}^*(X_i) - \tilde{\mu}^*(X)\|_{\mathcal{G}}^2 \mathbb{I}(\varrho(X_i, X) \leq \delta) \right] \\ &\leq \mathbb{E} \left[\sum_{i=1}^n W_{n,i}(X) 2 \left(\|\tilde{\mu}^*(X_i)\|_{\mathcal{G}}^2 + \|\tilde{\mu}^*(X)\|_{\mathcal{G}}^2 \right) \mathbb{I}(\varrho(X_i, X) > \delta) \right] \\ &\quad + \mathbb{E} \left[\sum_{i=1}^n W_{n,i}(X) \|\tilde{\mu}^*(X_i) - \tilde{\mu}^*(X)\|_{\mathcal{G}}^2 \mathbb{I}(\varrho(X_i, X) \leq \delta) \right] \end{aligned} \quad (5.27)$$

$$\begin{aligned} &\leq 4 \sup_{u \in \mathbb{X}} \|\tilde{\mu}(u)\|_{\mathcal{G}}^2 \mathbb{E} \left[\sum_{i=1}^n W_{n,i}(X) \mathbb{I}(\varrho(X_i, X) > \delta) \right] \\ &\quad + \sup_{u, v \in \mathbb{X}: \varrho(u, v) \leq \delta} \|\tilde{\mu}^*(u) - \tilde{\mu}^*(v)\|_{\mathcal{G}}^2. \end{aligned}$$

holds. We know that function $\tilde{\mu}^*$ is uniformly continuous, hence for any $\varepsilon > 0$ one can choose $\delta > 0$ such that

$$\sup_{u, v \in \mathbb{X}: \varrho(u, v) \leq \delta} \|\tilde{\mu}^*(u) - \tilde{\mu}^*(v)\|_{\mathcal{G}}^2 < \frac{\varepsilon}{2}, \quad (5.28)$$

hence the second term is less than $\varepsilon/2$. In addition, by condition (iii), for a given δ if n is large enough, then the first term is also less than $\varepsilon/2$. In conclusion, $J_n^{(2)}$ converges to 0.

For the third term we have that

$$\begin{aligned} |J_n^{(3)}| &= \mathbb{E} \left[\sum_{i=1}^n W_{n,i}(X) \|\tilde{\mu}^*(X) - \mu^*(X)\|_{\mathcal{G}}^2 \right] \\ &= \mathbb{E} \left[\|\tilde{\mu}^*(X) - \mu^*(X)\|_{\mathcal{G}}^2 \right] < \varepsilon. \end{aligned} \quad (5.29)$$

For $J_n^{(1)}$ the application of condition (ii) to function $f(x) \doteq \|\mu^*(x) - \tilde{\mu}^*(x)\|_{\mathcal{G}}^2$ yields

$$\begin{aligned} J_n^{(1)} &= \mathbb{E} \left[\sum_{i=1}^n W_{n,i}(X) \|\mu^*(X_i) - \tilde{\mu}^*(X_i)\|_{\mathcal{G}}^2 \right] \\ &\leq c \mathbb{E} \left[\|\mu^*(X) - \tilde{\mu}^*(X)\|_{\mathcal{G}}^2 \right] = c\varepsilon. \end{aligned} \quad (5.30)$$

Therefore, we can conclude that J_n tends to 0, as $n \rightarrow \infty$. \square

Lemma 5.3.5. *Under the conditions of Theorem 5.3.3, we have that*

$$\mathbb{E} \left[\left\| \sum_{i=1}^n W_{n,i}(X) (\ell(\cdot, Y_i) - \mu^*(X_i)) \right\|_{\mathcal{G}}^2 \right] \xrightarrow{n \rightarrow \infty} 0. \quad (5.31)$$

Proof. For simplicity let

$$\begin{aligned} I_n &\doteq \mathbb{E} \left[\left\| \sum_{i=1}^n W_{n,i}(X) (\ell(\cdot, Y_i) - \mu^*(X_i)) \right\|_{\mathcal{G}}^2 \right] \\ &= \mathbb{E} \left[\sum_{i=1}^n \sum_{j=1}^n W_{n,i}(X) W_{n,j}(X) \langle \ell(\cdot, Y_i) - \mu^*(X_i), \ell(\cdot, Y_j) - \mu^*(X_j) \rangle_{\mathcal{G}} \right]. \end{aligned} \quad (5.32)$$

For $i \neq j$ we have that

$$\begin{aligned} &\mathbb{E} \left[W_{n,i}(X) W_{n,j}(X) \langle \ell(\cdot, Y_i) - \mu^*(X_i), \ell(\cdot, Y_j) - \mu^*(X_j) \rangle_{\mathcal{G}} \right] \\ &= \mathbb{E} \left[\mathbb{E} \left[W_{n,i}(X) W_{n,j}(X) \langle \ell(\cdot, Y_i) - \mu^*(X_i), \ell(\cdot, Y_j) - \mu^*(X_j) \rangle_{\mathcal{G}} \mid X, X_1, \dots, X_n, Y_i \right] \right] \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 &= \mathbb{E} \left[W_{n,i}(X) W_{n,j}(X) \left\langle \ell(\cdot, Y_i) - \mu^*(X_i), \mathbb{E} \left[\ell(\cdot, Y_j) \mid X, X_1, \dots, X_n, Y_i \right] - \mu^*(X_j) \right\rangle_{\mathcal{G}} \right] \\
 &= \mathbb{E} \left[W_{n,i}(X) W_{n,j}(X) \left\langle \ell(\cdot, Y_i) - \mu^*(X_i), \mathbb{E} \left[\ell(\cdot, Y_j) \mid X_j \right] - \mu^*(X_j) \right\rangle_{\mathcal{G}} \right] = 0. \quad (5.33)
 \end{aligned}$$

Furthermore, by $\mathbb{E}[\ell(Y, Y)] < \infty$ we have $\mathbb{E}[\sigma^2(X)] < \infty$ for

$$\sigma^2(X) \doteq \mathbb{E} \left[\|\ell(\cdot, Y) - \mu^*(X)\|_{\mathcal{G}}^2 \mid X \right]. \quad (5.34)$$

By (5.33) we have

$$\begin{aligned}
 I_n &= \mathbb{E} \left[\sum_{i=1}^n W_{n,i}^2(X) \|\ell(\cdot, Y_i) - \mu^*(X_i)\|_{\mathcal{G}}^2 \right] \\
 &= \mathbb{E} \left[\mathbb{E} \left[\sum_{i=1}^n W_{n,i}^2(X) \|\ell(\cdot, Y_i) - \mu^*(X_i)\|_{\mathcal{G}}^2 \mid X, X_1, \dots, X_n \right] \right] \\
 &= \mathbb{E} \left[\sum_{i=1}^n W_{n,i}^2(X) \mathbb{E} \left[\|\ell(\cdot, Y_i) - \mu^*(X_i)\|_{\mathcal{G}}^2 \mid X, X_1, \dots, X_n \right] \right] \quad (5.35) \\
 &= \mathbb{E} \left[\sum_{i=1}^n W_{n,i}^2(X) \mathbb{E} \left[\|\ell(\cdot, Y_i) - \mu^*(X_i)\|_{\mathcal{G}}^2 \mid X_i \right] \right] \\
 &= \mathbb{E} \left[\sum_{i=1}^n W_{n,i}^2(X) \sigma^2(X_i) \right].
 \end{aligned}$$

If σ^2 is bounded, then I_n tends to zero almost surely by condition (iv). Otherwise let $\tilde{\sigma}^2 \leq L$ be such that

$$\mathbb{E} \left[|\tilde{\sigma}^2(X) - \sigma^2(X)| \right] < \varepsilon, \quad (5.36)$$

see (Györfi et al., 2002, Theorem A.1). Then

$$\begin{aligned}
 I_n &\leq \mathbb{E} \left[\sum_{i=1}^n W_{n,i}^2(X) \tilde{\sigma}^2(X_i) \right] + \mathbb{E} \left[\sum_{i=1}^n W_{n,i}^2(X) \left| \sigma^2(X_i) - \tilde{\sigma}^2(X_i) \right| \right] \\
 &\leq L \mathbb{E} \left[\sum_{i=1}^n W_{n,i}^2(X) \right] + \mathbb{E} \left[\sum_{i=1}^n W_{n,i}(X) \left| \sigma^2(X_i) - \tilde{\sigma}^2(X_i) \right| \right], \quad (5.37)
 \end{aligned}$$

where the first term tends to zero by condition (iv) and for the second term we have

$$\mathbb{E} \left[\sum_{i=1}^n W_{n,i}(X) \left| \sigma^2(X_i) - \tilde{\sigma}^2(X_i) \right| \right] \leq c \mathbb{E} \left[\left| \sigma^2(X) - \tilde{\sigma}^2(X) \right| \right] \leq c \varepsilon \quad (5.38)$$

by condition (ii). In conclusion, I_n converges to 0. \square

5.3.3 Recursive Estimation of CKMEs

Let (\mathbb{X}, ϱ) be a locally compact Polish space, as before. In this section, we apply local averaging “kernels” on the input space. These “kernels” are not necessarily positive

definite, therefore, to avoid misunderstanding, we call them smoothers. Nevertheless, many positive definite functions are covered with the definition that follow.

Definition 5.3.2 (smoother). *A function $k : \mathbb{X} \times \mathbb{X} \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$ is called a smoother, if it is measurable, nonnegative, symmetric, and bounded.*

Here, a novel recursive local averaging estimator is introduced. Let (k_n) be a smoother sequence and (a_n) be a stepsize (learning rate) sequence of nonnegative numbers. We construct a recursive algorithm by the rule that follows:

$$\begin{aligned} \mu_1(x) &\doteq \ell(\cdot, Y_1), \quad \text{and} \\ \mu_{n+1}(x) &\doteq \left(1 - a_{n+1}k_{n+1}(x, X_{n+1})\right)\mu_n(x) + a_{n+1}k_{n+1}(x, X_{n+1})\ell(\cdot, Y_{n+1}), \end{aligned} \tag{5.39}$$

for $n \in \mathbb{N}$. By induction, one can see that μ_n is of the form defined in (5.15). It is clear that one only needs to store μ_n , because in each iteration, when a new observation pair is available, one can immediately update μ_n by the recursion defined in (5.39).

In practice, we often need to evaluate $\mu^*(x)$ on a function $g \in \mathcal{G}$, i.e., the conditional expectation $\mathbb{E}[g(Y) | X = x]$ is sought. Then, our recursion simplifies to

$$\begin{aligned} \langle \mu_1(x), g \rangle_{\mathcal{G}} &= \langle \ell(\cdot, Y_1), g \rangle_{\mathcal{G}} = g(Y_1), \\ \langle \mu_{n+1}(x), g \rangle_{\mathcal{G}} &= \langle (1 - a_{n+1}k_{n+1}(x, X_{n+1}))\mu_n(x) + a_{n+1}k_{n+1}(x, X_{n+1})\ell(\cdot, Y_{n+1}), g \rangle_{\mathcal{G}} \\ &= \left(1 - a_{n+1}k_{n+1}(x, X_{n+1})\right)\langle \mu_n(x), g \rangle_{\mathcal{G}} + a_{n+1}k_{n+1}(x, X_{n+1})g(Y_{n+1}), \end{aligned} \tag{5.40}$$

which can be computed in linear time with constant memory. The real-valued consistency of this method can be established, e.g., by (Györfi et al., 2002, Theorem 25.1), however, we usually do not know in advance which function $g \in \mathcal{G}$ is of our interest, hence estimating the conditional kernel mean map is very useful. Moreover, knowing the whole conditional distribution could also be used for various inference tasks, e.g., conditional distribution estimation, hypothesis testing or building prediction regions.

Theorem 5.3.6 presents sufficient conditions for the weak and strong consistency of our recursive scheme. Its proof is presented in (Tamás and Csáji, 2024). It is a generalization of Theorem 25.1 of Györfi et al. (2002). There are two novelties w.r.t. that results. We prove consistency for Hilbert space valued regression and we cover locally compact Polish input spaces. The smoother functions do not need to admit a particular form or be monotonous. Intuitively the smoother functions should shrink around the observed input points as n goes to infinity. The rate of this decrease is controlled by stepsizes (h_n) and (r_n) . The proposed conditions are w.r.t. a general majorant function H .

Theorem 5.3.6. *Let (\mathbb{X}, ϱ) be a locally compact Polish space. Assume that C1, C2 and the conditions that follow are satisfied.*

- (i) *There exist (h_n) and (r_n) positive sequences tending to 0 and a nonnegative, nonincreasing function H on $[0, \infty)$ with $1/r_n \cdot H(s/h_n) \rightarrow 0$ ($n \rightarrow \infty$) for all $s \in (0, \infty)$.*

(ii) For all $n \in \mathbb{N}^+$ it holds that

$$k_n(x, z) \leq \frac{1}{r_n} H(\varrho(x, z)/h_n). \quad (5.41)$$

(iii) The supremum of additive weights is bounded by 1, i.e.,

$$\sup_{x, z \in \mathbb{X}, n \in \mathbb{N}^+} a_n k_n(x, z) \leq 1. \quad (5.42)$$

(iv) Measure Q_x does not diminish w.r.t. the smoother functions, that is,

$$\liminf_{n \rightarrow \infty} \int_{\mathbb{X}} k_n(x, t) dQ_x(t) > 0 \quad \text{for } Q_x\text{-almost all } x. \quad (5.43)$$

(v) The positive learning rates satisfy

$$\sum_{n=1}^{\infty} a_n = \infty, \quad \text{and} \quad \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} \frac{a_n^2}{r_n^2} < \infty. \quad (5.44)$$

Then, the estimate sequence (μ_n) defined by (5.39) is weakly and strongly consistent.

Conditions (i) and (ii) ensure that $k_n(x, z)$ vanishes for $x \neq z$ as $n \rightarrow \infty$. The weight functions are probability weights because of assumption (iii). Condition (iv) is the strongest technical assumption in a general metric measure space, however, in several cases it is easy to verify. Condition (v) can be guaranteed usually by the choice of stepsizes.

We presented our recursive algorithm in a general framework. It remains to construct smoother sequences and stepsizes that satisfy the proposed conditions. In the theorem that follows we generate the smoothers with the help of an $\mathbb{R} \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$ type mother smoother K . In the next section we present several corollaries of this theorem to design consistent algorithms for three important ML applications.

Theorem 5.3.7. *Let (\mathbb{X}, ϱ) be a locally compact Polish space and $K : \mathbb{R} \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$ be a measurable, nonnegative and bounded function. Assume C1 and C2. Let (h_n) and (r_n) be positive sequences with zero limit. Let us define the smoothers as*

$$k_n(x, z) \doteq \frac{1}{r_n} K\left(\frac{\varrho(x, z)}{h_n}\right), \quad (5.45)$$

for $n \in \mathbb{N}^+$. Let (μ_n) be defined as in (5.39). Assume that:

- (i) There are positive constants R and b such that $K(t) \geq b \mathbb{I}(t \in [-R, R])$ for all $t \in \mathbb{R}$.
- (ii) There is a measurable, nonnegative and nonincreasing function H on $[0, \infty)$ such that $1/r_n \cdot H(s/h_n) \rightarrow 0$ as $n \rightarrow \infty$ and $K(s) \leq H(s)$ for all $s \in (0, \infty)$.

(iii) The nonnegative learning rates satisfy

$$\sum_{n=1}^{\infty} a_n = \infty, \quad \text{and} \quad \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} \frac{a_n^2}{r_n^2} < \infty. \quad (5.46)$$

(iv) The weights of the update term is bounded by 1, i.e.,

$$\sup_{t \in \mathbb{R}} K(t) \sup_{n \in \mathbb{N}^+} \frac{a_n}{r_n} \leq 1. \quad (5.47)$$

(v) The probability of small balls is bounded from below by

$$\liminf_{n \rightarrow \infty} \frac{Q_x(B(x, R h_n))}{r_n} > 0 \quad Q_x - a.s. \quad (5.48)$$

Then, (μ_n) is weakly and strongly consistent.

Proof. It is sufficient to verify the conditions of Theorem 5.3.6. We assumed that

$$1/r_n \cdot H(s/h_n) \rightarrow 0, \quad (5.49)$$

for all $s \in (0, \infty)$. From (5.45) and condition (ii) it follows that

$$r_n k_n(x, z) = K(\varrho(x, z)/h_n) \leq H(\varrho(x, z)/h_n). \quad (5.50)$$

Condition (iv) implies that

$$\sup_{x, z \in \mathbb{X}, n \in \mathbb{N}^+} a_n k_n(x, z) = \sup_{x, z \in \mathbb{X}, n \in \mathbb{N}^+} \frac{a_n}{r_n} K\left(\frac{\varrho(x, z)}{h_n}\right) \leq \sup_{t \in \mathbb{R}} K(t) \sup_{n \in \mathbb{N}^+} \frac{a_n}{r_n} \leq 1 \quad (5.51)$$

holds. Finally by condition (i) we have

$$\begin{aligned} \int_{\mathbb{X}} k_n(x, t) dQ_x(t) &= \int_{\mathbb{X}} \frac{1}{r_n} K\left(\frac{\varrho(x, t)}{h_n}\right) dQ_x(t) \\ &\geq \int_{\mathbb{X}} \frac{b}{r_n} \mathbb{I}\left(\frac{\varrho(x, t)}{h_n} \in [-R, R]\right) dQ_x(t) \\ &= \int_{\mathbb{X}} \frac{b}{r_n} \mathbb{I}\left(t \in B(x, R h_n)\right) dQ_x(t) = \frac{b Q_x(B(x, R h_n))}{r_n}. \end{aligned} \quad (5.52)$$

Taking the lim inf on both sides and applying condition (v) yield (5.43). The conditions on the stepsize sequence are assumed. Thus, (μ_n) is weakly and strongly consistent. \square

5.4 Demonstrative Applications

In this section we demonstrate the applicability of Theorem 5.3.7 through some characteristic model classes important for statistical learning. We consider three general setups. The main difference of these applications lies in the input spaces. We show that the requirement on the probability of small balls is satisfied in these cases and provide learning rates (a_n) , (r_n) and (h_n) , such that they satisfy the conditions of Theorem 5.3.7.

First, Euclidean input spaces are considered, for which we prove the weak and strong universal consistency of the recursive estimator of the conditional kernel mean map. The main novelty of this corollary compared to the results of (Györfi et al., 2002) is that our method is applicable for special Hilbert space valued regression problems.

Second, we study abstract Riemannian manifolds as input spaces for which an embedding into an “ambient” Euclidean space may not be explicitly given. One of the motivations of this example comes from manifold learning (Tenenbaum et al., 2000; Lin and Zha, 2008), which is an actively studied area in ML, whose theoretical study is full of challenges. The presented recursive framework can offer a new technical tool for this direction.

Finally, we investigate the case of functional inputs (Ferraty and Vieu, 2006). This example is motivated by signal processing methods for continuous-time systems in time-series analysis. We consider a wavelet-like approach leading to an input space that is a locally compact subset of $L_2(\mathbb{R})$ induced by translations of a suitable mother function.

5.4.1 Euclidean Spaces

For a Euclidean space the weak and strong universal consistency of the recursive estimator of the conditional kernel mean map is a consequence of Theorem 5.3.7.

Theorem 5.4.1. *Let $\mathbb{X} = \mathbb{R}^p$, with the Euclidean metric, and $K : \mathbb{R} \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$ be a measurable, nonnegative and bounded function. Let the stepsizes be defined as $a_n \doteq 1/n$, and let $r_n \doteq 1/n^{(1-\varepsilon)/2}$, where $\varepsilon \in (0, 1)$, and $h_n \doteq \sqrt[p]{r_n}$ and k_n be as in (5.45) for $n \in \mathbb{N}^+$. Let (μ_n) be defined as in (5.39). Assume C1, C2 and conditions (i) and (ii) from Theorem 5.3.7, then (μ_n) is weakly and strongly universally consistent.*

Proof. We can assume (w.l.o.g.) that K is bounded by 1. A Euclidean space is a locally compact Polish space, therefore, we can apply Theorem 5.3.7. Conditions (i) and (ii) are assumed. Our choice of stepsizes clearly satisfies (5.46) and (5.47). For (5.48) we use (Devroye, 1981, Lemma 2.2) which proves that for every probability measure Q_x on \mathbb{R}^p there exists a nonnegative function g satisfying $g(x) < \infty$ Q_x -almost surely, such that

$$\frac{h_n^p}{Q_x(B(x, R h_n))} \rightarrow g(x) \quad Q_x\text{-a.s.} \quad (5.53)$$

for all $R > 0$. Therefore

$$\liminf_{n \rightarrow \infty} \frac{Q_x(B(x, R h_n))}{r_n} = \frac{1}{g(x)} > 0 \quad Q_x\text{-a.s.} \quad (5.54)$$

and then the statement of corollary is proved by applying Theorem 5.3.7. \square

Mother kernel K can be chosen based on prior knowledge. In the table that follows we list a set of the possible candidates. One can easily verify that all of these functions are measurable, nonnegative and bounded by 1. They also satisfy conditions (i) and (ii) from Theorem 5.3.7 with $H = K|_{[0,\infty)}$.

Name	Formula
Box kernel	$\mathbb{I}(x < B)$, with $B > 0$
Gaussian kernel	$\exp\left(-\frac{x^2}{\sigma}\right)$, with $\sigma > 0$
Laplace kernel	$\exp\left(-\frac{ x }{\sigma}\right)$, with $\sigma > 0$
Epanechnikov kernel	$3/4(1 - x^2) \mathbb{I}(x < 1)$

5.4.2 Riemannian Manifolds

In our recursive scheme the power of h_n w.r.t. r_n is (at least) p for a p -dimensional Euclidean space. Manifolds can often be embedded in a high-dimensional Euclidean space, however, they are locally isomorphic to a lower dimensional one. This local isometry allows us to use the lower manifold dimension as the power of h_n w.r.t. r_n . Moreover, we also cover abstract p -dimensional manifolds, where an ambient Euclidean space is not required. The proof of Theorem 5.4.2 can be found in (Tamás and Csáji, 2024).

Theorem 5.4.2. *Let \mathbb{X} be a p -dimensional connected, geodesically complete Riemannian manifold, with geodesical distance ϱ and $K : \mathbb{R} \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$ be a measurable, nonnegative and bounded function. Let $a_n \doteq 1/n$, $r_n \doteq 1/n^{(1-\varepsilon)/2}$, where $\varepsilon \in (0, 1)$, and $h_n = \sqrt[p]{r_n}$ and k_n be as in (5.45) for $n \in \mathbb{N}^+$. Let (μ_n) be defined by (5.39). Assume that C1, C2 and conditions (i) and (ii) from Theorem 5.3.7 hold, then (μ_n) is weakly and strongly universally consistent.*

5.4.3 Locally Compact Subset of a Hilbert Space

Finally, we consider functional inputs. The analyzed function set is motivated by wavelets. Our model class can be seen as how a signal is encoded in a computer by storing a finite number of coefficients for some basis functions at given knots, where the locations of these knots are flexible and part of the representation.

Let us consider the Hilbert space $L_2(\mathbb{R})$. Let ψ be a function in a Sobolev space $W^{1,2}(\mathbb{R})$ (Berlinet and Thomas-Agnan, 2004), and τ_x be the translation operator on $L_2(\mathbb{R})$ defined pointwise by $\tau_x f(t) \doteq f(t - x)$. For given (constant) hyperparameters $m \in \mathbb{N}$, $M > 0$, let

$$\mathcal{M} \doteq \left\{ f : \mathbb{R} \rightarrow \mathbb{R} \mid f = \sum_{i=1}^m \lambda_i \tau_{x_i} \psi \text{ for some } \lambda_1, \dots, \lambda_m, x_1, \dots, x_m \in [-M, M] \right\}. \quad (5.55)$$

Consider the canonical (measurable) mapping ϕ from $[-M, M]^{2m}$ to \mathcal{M} given by

$$\phi : \begin{bmatrix} \lambda \\ x \end{bmatrix} \mapsto \sum_{i=1}^m \lambda_i \tau_{x_i} \psi, \quad (5.56)$$

where $\lambda = [\lambda_1, \dots, \lambda_m]^T$ and $x = [x_1, \dots, x_m]^T$. Clearly, ϕ is surjective, however, it is not injective. We consider probability measures of the form $Q_x \doteq P_x \circ \phi^{-1}$ for some P_x on $[-M, M]^{2m}$, i.e., we assume that Q_x is the pushforward of some measure on the bounded (locally compact) Polish space $[-M, M]^{2m}$ with the Euclidean metric. The proof of the theorem that follows can be found in (Tamás and Csáji, 2024).

Theorem 5.4.3. *Let $\psi \in W^{1,2}(\mathbb{R})$, $\mathbb{X} = \mathcal{M}$ with the L_2 metric, $K : \mathbb{R} \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$ be a measurable, nonnegative and bounded function. Let $a_n \doteq 1/n$, $r_n \doteq 1/n^{(1-\varepsilon)/2}$, for an $\varepsilon \in (0, 1)$, and $h_n = \sqrt[2m]{r_n}$ and k_n be as in (5.45) for $n \in \mathbb{N}^+$. Let (μ_n) be defined as in (5.39). Assume (i)-(ii) from Theorem 5.3.7, then (μ_n) is weakly and strongly consistent for measures of the form $Q_x \doteq P_x \circ \phi^{-1}$ for any distribution P_x on $[-M, M]^{2m}$.*

5.5 Discussion

In this chapter, we have introduced a new recursive estimator for the conditional kernel mean map, which is a key object to represent conditional distributions in Hilbert spaces. We have proved the weak and strong L_2 consistency of the new method in the Bochner sense, under general structural conditions. We have considered a locally compact Polish input space and assumed only the knowledge of a kernel on the (measurable) output space. Our recursive algorithm uses a smoother sequence on the metric input space and three learning sequences, each of these having a particular role in the iterative settings. Learning rate (a_n) adjusts the weights of the current estimate term and the update term in each step. Sequences (h_n) and (r_n) are used to adaptively shrink the smoother functions w.r.t. the intrinsic measuretic structure of the metric space. Our main assumption concerns the probabilities of small balls, i.e., we assume that the measure of small balls with radius h_n are comparable to r_n when n goes to infinity. We have generalized a result of Györfi et al. (2002, Theorem 25.1) for locally compact Polish input spaces and Hilbert space valued regressions. We have considered three important application domains of our recursive estimation scheme. Our consistency results are universal in case of Euclidean input spaces and complete Riemannian manifolds, because the small ball probability assumption can be satisfied by (h_n) and (r_n) for all probability distributions. A Hilbert space valued input set (containing functions) was also considered to illustrate the generality of the framework.

Chapter 6

Independence Tests with Finite Sample Guarantees

This chapter is based on our journal paper ([Tamás et al., 2023](#)). These results were also presented at the 62nd IEEE Conference on Decision and Control, Marina Bay, Singapore. We introduce a robust statistical test for the independence of stochastic (time-invariant) linear systems that are synchronous. Our method was implemented in Python by my co-author Dániel Á. Bálint with whom I jointly run the numerical experiments and created the illustrations of this chapter including Figure 6.1a, Figure 6.1b, Figure 6.1c, Figure 6.1d, Figure 6.1e, Figure 6.1f, Figure 6.1g and Figure 6.1h.

6.1 Introduction

Statistical independence is a key notion in several areas of statistics and probability theory, including time series analysis ([Box et al., 2015](#)), system identification ([Ljung, 1999](#)), signal processing ([Moon and Stirling, 2000](#)) and ML. In this chapter we present a resampling hypothesis test with finite sample guarantees for the independence of two simultaneous, stochastic linear systems. Our setup is distribution-free, i.e., the driving noises of the observed processes can follow any probability law. Potential applications of the hypothesis test include identifying (conditionally) dependent price returns in the stock market or discovering connections between two systems on a network.

Given an i.i.d. sample of random pairs with some joint distribution, there already exists several hypothesis tests for independence, e.g., the celebrated χ^2 test ([Pearson, 1900](#)), Hoeffding’s test based on the factorization of the joint distribution function ([Hoeffding, 1948](#)), HSIC-based tests ([Gretton et al., 2008](#)) and L_1 distance and log-likelihood based tests ([Gretton and Györfi, 2010](#)). These methods typically use the limiting distribution of some test statistic to determine the critical values for a given sample size. Usually it is not tractable to compute the exact distribution of these test statistics, however, permutation tests and Monte Carlo tests offer viable solutions. For stochastic processes it is even more challenging to test independence. For this, HSIC and distance correlation based

approaches were proposed in the literature (Chwialkowski and Gretton, 2014; Székely and Rizzo, 2009), which are supported by asymptotic guarantees.

6.2 Problem Setting

We construct robust permutation based independence tests (Pfister et al., 2018; Rindt et al., 2021) with finite sample guarantees, for stochastic, time-invariant linear systems (Ljung, 1999), that are given by

$$\begin{aligned} Y_t &= G_1(q^{-1}; \theta^*)U_t + H_1(q^{-1}; \theta^*)E_t, \\ Z_t &= G_2(q^{-1}; \varphi^*)V_t + H_2(q^{-1}; \varphi^*)N_t, \end{aligned} \tag{6.1}$$

where U_t and V_t are observable system inputs, Y_t and Z_t are observable outputs for $t \in \mathbb{Z}$; q^{-1} is the backshift operator; E_t and N_t are possibly dependent process noises; G_1, H_1 , and G_2, H_2 are rational transfer functions on finite dimensional parameter spaces Θ and Φ , respectively. The unknown true system parameters are θ^* and φ^* . Our main assumptions are as follows, cf. (Ljung, 1999):

- D1.** *The true systems generating outputs (Y_t) and (Z_t) are in the model classes, i.e., $\theta^* \in \Theta$ and $\varphi^* \in \Phi$.*
- D2.** *Rational (causal) transfer functions G_1, G_2, H_1 and H_2 have known orders.*
- D3.** *H_1 and H_2 are invertible for all $\theta \in \Theta$ and $\varphi \in \Phi$.*
- D4.** *The systems are initialized in zero, i.e., $Y_t = Z_t = U_t = V_t = E_t = N_t = 0$, for $t \leq 0$.*
- D5.** *The systems are driven by an i.i.d. innovation sequence $\{(E_t, N_t)\}_{t=1}^{\infty}$ from the (unknown) joint distribution of (E, N) .*
- D6.** *The systems operate in open-loop: (U_t) and (V_t) are independent of (E_t) and (N_t) .*

For example, autoregressive moving average systems with exogenous inputs (ARMAX) can satisfy these conditions. To simplify the analysis, we treat the inputs $(U_t), (V_t)$ as deterministic. This is w.l.o.g. as we can always condition on the inputs, because they are independent of the innovations. In case the inputs are stochastic, the obtained results should be interpreted as conditional to the inputs, i.e., we test whether (Y_t) and (Z_t) are conditionally independent given $(U_t), (V_t)$. Also, we can assume that the parameterization is unique, e.g., by assuming that $H_1(0; \theta) = 1$ and $H_2(0; \varphi) = 1$ for all $\theta \in \Theta, \varphi \in \Phi$.

In this chapter our main goal is to construct consistent rank tests with non-asymptotic stochastic guarantees for the null hypothesis that (Y_t) and (Z_t) are independent. One of our key observations is that under the presented assumptions the independence of (Y_t) and (Z_t) conditional on the inputs is equivalent to the independence of (E_t) and (N_t) . Therefore, it is sufficient to test the null hypothesis

$$H_0 : Q_{E,N} = Q_E \otimes Q_N \quad \text{vs} \quad H_1 : Q_{E,N} \neq Q_E \otimes Q_N. \quad (6.2)$$

The true parameters, θ^* and φ^* , are unknown, henceforth the noise terms are not observable. This is what makes the hypothesis testing challenging. For simplicity, we assume that the finite sample of inputs, (U_t) , (V_t) , and outputs, (Y_t) , (Z_t) , available is large enough to compute n prediction errors $\{(E_t(\theta), N_t(\varphi))\}_{t=1}^n$ for any values of θ and φ .

We construct independence tests in several steps. First, we estimate the system parameters with non-asymptotic confidence regions, then we reconstruct the residuals on the set of accepted parameters and finally apply a permutation test on the residuals based on dependence measure estimates. We use the notion of HSIC to detect any nonlinear dependence between the driving noise terms. We accept the null hypothesis if we find at least one pair of parameters in the confidence region where the permutation test accepts the hypothesis of independence. Our main assumption is that the linear systems are driven synchronously and that the noise terms could be recovered if the system parameters were known. We only rely on the i.i.d. assumption to quantify the user-chosen probability of type I error and prove that the probability of type II error vanishes asymptotically under mild statistical assumptions.

6.3 Permutation Tests for the I.I.D. Case

First, for simplicity, assume that the parameters are known. In this case we can recover the noise terms from the observations as

$$\begin{aligned} E_t &= E_t(\theta^*) = H_1^{-1}(q^{-1}; \theta^*)(Y_t - G_1(q^{-1}; \theta^*)U_t), \\ N_t &= N_t(\varphi^*) = H_2^{-1}(q^{-1}; \varphi^*)(Z_t - G_1(q^{-1}; \varphi^*)V_t), \end{aligned} \quad (6.3)$$

using D3, D4 and D6. Then the independence of E and N can be tested based on the i.i.d. sample $\{(E_t, N_t)\}_{t=1}^n$.

6.3.1 Resampling

Let $\mathcal{D}_0 \doteq \{(E_t, N_t)\}_{t=1}^n$ denote the recovered noise terms. We propose a rank test which is based on empirical HSIC estimates computed from perturbed samples. One of the main ideas of this chapter is to generate perturbed datasets which have the same distributional properties as the original observations if and only if the null hypothesis is true.

We apply the permutation test of (Pfister et al., 2018), which was refined and proved to be consistent by (Rindt et al., 2021). As in Chapter 3 and Chapter 4 we choose an arbitrary (rational) significance level δ and integer hyperparameters $1 \leq r \leq m$ such that $\delta = r/m$. Let S_n be the set of permutations on $[n]$ and $\{\pi_j\}_{j=1}^{m-1}$ be uniformly randomly generated from S_n . We construct $m - 1$ alternative samples by

$$\mathcal{D}_j = \pi_j \mathcal{D}_0 \doteq \{(E_i, N_{\pi_j(i)})\}_{i=1}^n \quad (6.4)$$

for $j = 1, \dots, m-1$. Ultimately, we end up with a total of m datasets to compare. Observe that if H_0 holds true then $\mathcal{D}_0 = ((E_1, N_1), \dots, (E_n, N_n))$ has the same distribution as $\mathcal{D}_j = ((E_1, N_{\pi_j(1)}), \dots, (E_n, N_{\pi_j(n)}))$ for any permutation π_j , whereas if H_1 holds, then the distribution of \mathcal{D}_j is different from that of \mathcal{D}_0 . Our goal is to detect this difference whenever the null hypothesis does not hold.

6.3.2 Exact Coverage

The comparison of the datasets is carried out with the help of ranking functions, cf. Definition 3.2.1. Our main tool for quantifying the probability of type I error is Lemma 3.2.1. A technical challenge is posed by identical datasets. We use a random permutation σ on $[m-1]_0$ independently generated from \mathcal{D}_0 and $\{\pi_j\}_{j=1}^{m-1}$ to resolve this problem as before, i.e., let $\mathcal{D}_j^\sigma \doteq (\mathcal{D}_j, \sigma(j))$ denote the extended datasets for $j \in [m-1]_0$.

Theorem 6.3.1. *Assume D1-D6 and that θ^* , φ^* and ψ are given. If H_0 holds true then for every integers $1 \leq r \leq m$ and sample size $n \in \mathbb{N}^+$ we have*

$$\mathbb{P}\left(\psi(\mathcal{D}_0^\sigma, \dots, \mathcal{D}_{m-1}^\sigma) \leq r\right) = \frac{r}{m}. \quad (6.5)$$

Proof. Notice that $\{\mathcal{D}_j^\sigma\}_{j=0}^{m-1}$ are almost surely pairwise different exchangeable vectors under H_0 , therefore Theorem 6.3.1 follows from Lemma 3.2.1. \square

Observe that Theorem 6.3.1 is completely distribution-free and provides us finite sample guarantees for the type I error probability; the significance level of the proposed resampling scheme is exact and user-chosen (rational). In the sections that follow we construct ranking functions that ensure the consistency of the proposed test.

The HSIC is used for assessing the statistical dependency between E and N with joint distribution $Q_{E,N}$. The theoretical HSIC is needed to be estimated from the i.i.d. sample, $\mathcal{D}_0 = \{(E_i, N_i)\}_{i=1}^n$, of $Q_{E,N}$. Our hypothesis test uses HSIC_n , the consistent estimator of HSIC defined in (2.60), with a characteristic product kernel.

6.3.3 Hypothesis Test for Independence

Our resampling test compares empirical dependence measure estimates via a ranking function ψ . To resolve (the unlikely event of) ties during comparison, we amend the order function \prec_σ , cf. (3.9). Let $\widehat{\Delta}_n^{(j)} = |\text{HSIC}_n(\mathcal{D}_j)|$ for $j = 0, \dots, m-1$ and

$$\psi(\mathcal{D}_0^\sigma, \dots, \mathcal{D}_{m-1}^\sigma) \doteq 1 + \sum_{j=1}^{m-1} \mathbb{I}\left(\widehat{\Delta}_n^{(0)} \prec_\sigma \widehat{\Delta}_n^{(j)}\right). \quad (6.6)$$

We reject H_0 if and only if $\psi(\mathcal{D}_0^\sigma, \dots, \mathcal{D}_{m-1}^\sigma) \leq r$. If H_0 holds then $\{\mathcal{D}_j^\sigma\}_{j=0}^{m-1}$ are exchangeable, hence the rank statistic is uniformly distributed. If H_0 does not hold, then

Algorithm 6 Independence Test for an I.I.D. Sample

Inputs: i.i.d. sample \mathcal{D}_0 , desired significance level δ , product kernel $k \otimes \ell$, tiebreaking permutation σ on $[m-1]_0$

- 1: Choose integers $1 \leq r \leq m$ such that $\delta = r/m$.
- 2: Generate $m-1$ random permutation $\{\pi_j\}_{j=1}^{m-1}$ uniformly from S_n .
- 3: Construct $m-1$ new alternative sample by $\mathcal{D}_j = \{(E_i, N_{\pi_j(i)})\}_{i=1}^n$ for $j \in [m-1]$ and let $\mathcal{D}_j^\sigma \doteq (\mathcal{D}_j, \sigma(j))$ for $j \in [m-1]_0$.
- 4: Compute the HSIC estimates $\widehat{\Delta}_n^{(j)} = |\text{HSIC}_n(\mathcal{D}_j)|$ for $j = 0, 1, \dots, m-1$.
- 5: Compute the rank statistic:

$$\psi(\mathcal{D}_0^\sigma, \dots, \mathcal{D}_{m-1}^\sigma) = 1 + \sum_{j=1}^{m-1} \mathbb{I} \left(\widehat{\Delta}_n^{(0)} \prec_\sigma \widehat{\Delta}_n^{(j)} \right). \quad (6.7)$$

- 6: Reject H_0 if and only if

$$\psi(\mathcal{D}_0^\sigma, \dots, \mathcal{D}_{m-1}^\sigma) \leq r.$$

$\text{HSIC}(E, N) \neq 0$ and by [Pfister et al. \(2018\)](#), variable $\text{HSIC}_n(\mathcal{D}_0)$ tends to a positive number. The pairs are shuffled, therefore, the perturbed samples $\{\mathcal{D}_j^\sigma\}_{j=1}^{m-1}$ are almost i.i.d. Thus, one expects that $\text{HSIC}_n(\mathcal{D}_j)$ tends to 0 for $j \in [m-1]$. In conclusion, under H_1 asymptotically $\text{HSIC}_n(\mathcal{D}_0)$ dominates $\text{HSIC}_n(\mathcal{D}_j)$ for every $j \in [m-1]$. The pseudocode of the hypothesis test for the i.i.d. case is presented in Algorithm 6. Our independence test admits an exact confidence level, which is a direct consequence of Theorem 6.3.1:

Corollary 6.3.1. *Assume D1-D6. Let ψ be the HSIC-based ranking function defined in (6.6). If H_0 holds, then for every integers $1 \leq r \leq m$ and sample size $n \in \mathbb{N}^+$ we have*

$$\mathbb{P} \left(\psi(\mathcal{D}_0^\sigma, \dots, \mathcal{D}_{m-1}^\sigma) \leq r \right) = \frac{r}{m}. \quad (6.8)$$

6.3.4 Strong Consistency

In this section we provide asymptotic guarantees for the type II error probability. [Rindt et al. \(2021, Lemma 1\)](#) showed that the HSIC-based ranking is stable in the following sense:

$$\widehat{\Delta}_n^{(0)} \xrightarrow{p} |\text{HSIC}(E, N)| \quad \text{and} \quad \widehat{\Delta}_n^{(j)} \xrightarrow{p} 0 \quad \text{for } j \in [m-1]. \quad (6.9)$$

This property ensures that the empirical estimates of HSIC stochastically vanish for the permuted samples. Let us assume that:

D7. *Kernel $k \otimes \ell$ is characteristic.*

Theorem 6.3.2. *Assume that D1-D7 hold and θ^*, φ^* are given. If H_1 holds, then for any integers $1 \leq r < m$:*

$$\mathbb{P} \left(\psi(\mathcal{D}_0^\sigma, \dots, \mathcal{D}_{m-1}^\sigma) \leq r \right) \xrightarrow{n \rightarrow \infty} 1. \quad (6.10)$$

Proof. One can bound the probability in (6.10) as

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbb{P}(\psi \leq r) &\geq \mathbb{P}(\psi = 1) \geq \mathbb{P}(\forall j \in [m-1] : \widehat{\Delta}_n^{(0)} > \widehat{\Delta}_n^{(j)}) \\ &= 1 - \mathbb{P}(\exists j \in [m-1] : \widehat{\Delta}_n^{(0)} \leq \widehat{\Delta}_n^{(j)}) \\ &\geq 1 - \sum_{j=1}^{m-1} \mathbb{P}(\widehat{\Delta}_n^{(0)} \leq \widehat{\Delta}_n^{(j)}) \geq 1 - m \cdot \mathbb{P}(\widehat{\Delta}_n^{(0)} \leq \widehat{\Delta}_n^{(1)}), \end{aligned}$$

where $\mathbb{P}(\widehat{\Delta}_n^{(0)} \leq \widehat{\Delta}_n^{(1)})$ goes to zero, because of (6.9). □

By Theorem 6.3.2 the probability of type II error tends to zero as the sample size goes to infinity, assuming that the HSIC is characteristic.

6.4 Robust Independence Tests

Let us consider the general problem where the true parameters are unknown constant vectors. In this case, the exact noise terms cannot be recovered, but only estimated. We assume that we can build non-asymptotically guaranteed confidence sets for the true parameters. Then, the idea is to use a two-step algorithm: first, we construct (distribution-free) confidence regions, then apply a parameter dependent version of the above hypothesis test on each parameter pair in the confidence region.

6.4.1 Parameter Dependent Hypothesis Test

We present a meta algorithm that works with any confidence regions for θ^* and φ^* , i.e., we assume that for all $\beta > 0$ we can build confidence sets $\widehat{\Theta}_n$ and $\widehat{\Phi}_n$ such that both

$$\mathbb{P}(\theta^* \in \widehat{\Theta}_n) \geq 1 - \beta \quad \text{and} \quad \mathbb{P}(\varphi^* \in \widehat{\Phi}_n) \geq 1 - \beta \tag{6.11}$$

hold for all sample size $n \in \mathbb{N}^+$. For simplicity, we will omit n from the notation. By D3 we obtain $E_t(\theta)$ and $N_t(\varphi)$ for any parameter-pair candidate $(\theta, \varphi) \in \widehat{\Theta} \times \widehat{\Phi}$ by

$$\begin{aligned} E_t(\theta) &\doteq H_1^{-1}(q^{-1}, \theta)(Y_t - G_1(q^{-1}, \theta)U_t), \\ N_t(\varphi) &\doteq H_2^{-1}(q^{-1}, \varphi)(Z_t - G_2(q^{-1}, \varphi)V_t), \end{aligned} \tag{6.12}$$

for $t = 1, \dots, n$. These quantities can be perturbed as before to construct parameterized alternative datasets

$$\mathcal{D}_j(\theta, \varphi) = \{(E_i(\theta), N_{\pi_j(i)}(\varphi))\}_{i=1}^n \tag{6.13}$$

for $j = 1, \dots, m-1$ and extended by σ to create $\mathcal{D}_j^\sigma(\theta, \varphi)$ for $j = 0, \dots, m-1$. Finally, for any ranking function ψ one can define parameter dependent ranks as

$$\psi(\theta, \varphi) \doteq \psi(\mathcal{D}_0^\sigma(\theta, \varphi), \dots, \mathcal{D}_{m-1}^\sigma(\theta, \varphi)). \tag{6.14}$$

Theorem 6.4.1. *Assume D1-D6. Let ψ be a ranking function, $\widehat{\Theta}$ and $\widehat{\Phi}$ conservative confidence sets with significance level at most β . If H_0 holds true then*

$$\mathbb{P}\left(\max_{(\theta, \varphi) \in \widehat{\Theta} \times \widehat{\Phi}} \psi(\theta, \varphi) \leq r\right) \leq \frac{r}{m} + 2\beta. \quad (6.15)$$

Proof. Using the union bound and (6.11), one can show that $\widehat{\Theta} \times \widehat{\Phi}$ is a confidence region for (θ^*, φ^*) , i.e.,

$$\mathbb{P}\left((\theta^*, \varphi^*) \notin \widehat{\Theta} \times \widehat{\Phi}\right) \leq \mathbb{P}\left(\theta^* \notin \widehat{\Theta}\right) + \mathbb{P}\left(\varphi^* \notin \widehat{\Phi}\right) \leq 2\beta.$$

Then, under H_0 , we have

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbb{P}\left(\max_{\theta \in \widehat{\Theta}, \varphi \in \widehat{\Phi}} \psi(\theta, \varphi) \leq r\right) &= \mathbb{P}\left(\{(\theta^*, \varphi^*) \notin \widehat{\Theta} \times \widehat{\Phi}\} \cap \left\{\max_{\theta \in \widehat{\Theta}, \varphi \in \widehat{\Phi}} \psi(\theta, \varphi) \leq r\right\}\right) \\ &\quad + \mathbb{P}\left(\{(\theta^*, \varphi^*) \in \widehat{\Theta} \times \widehat{\Phi}\} \cap \left\{\max_{\theta \in \widehat{\Theta}, \varphi \in \widehat{\Phi}} \psi(\theta, \varphi) \leq r\right\}\right) \quad (6.16) \\ &\leq \mathbb{P}\left((\theta^*, \varphi^*) \notin \widehat{\Theta} \times \widehat{\Phi}\right) + \mathbb{P}\left(\psi(\theta^*, \varphi^*) \leq r\right), \end{aligned}$$

where the first term is less than 2β because of (6.15) and the second term is r/m because of Theorem 6.3.1. □

6.4.2 Robust HSIC-Based Ranking

Ranking functions can be defined similarly to the i.i.d. case via the HSIC. The idea is to compute dependence measure estimates w.r.t. plausible parameters. Let us consider HSIC estimate functions $\widehat{\Delta}_n^{(j)}(\theta, \varphi) \doteq |\text{HSIC}_n(\mathcal{D}_j(\theta, \varphi))|$, for $j = 0, 1, \dots, m-1$ and define the ranking function as

$$\psi(\theta, \varphi) \doteq 1 + \sum_{j=1}^{m-1} \mathbb{I}\left(\widehat{\Delta}_n^{(0)}(\theta, \varphi) \prec_{\sigma} \widehat{\Delta}_n^{(j)}(\theta, \varphi)\right). \quad (6.17)$$

If H_0 does not hold, then $\widehat{\Delta}_n^{(0)}(\theta, \varphi)$ tends to be the greatest around (θ^*, φ^*) , henceforth, we reject the null hypothesis if $\psi(\theta, \varphi)$ is at most some user-chosen rank value r on $\widehat{\Theta} \times \widehat{\Phi}$. The step-by-step method is presented in Algorithm 7. Note that the test exhibits finite sample guarantees for the significance level, as it is showed by Theorem 6.4.1.

6.4.3 Strong Consistency of the Robust Test

In this section we quantify the asymptotic behaviour of rejection probability when H_0 is false, thus let us consider the case when E and N are dependent. We prove that the power of the suggested test tends to 1 as the sample size goes to infinity. We assume that:

D8. *Control inputs (U_t) , (V_t) and driving noises (E_t) , (N_t) are a.s. included in a Cesàro*

Algorithm 7 Independence Test for Synchronous Systems

Inputs: observations (U_t) , (Y_t) , (V_t) and (Z_t) , transfer functions G_1 , G_2 , H_1 and H_2 parameterized by $\theta \in \Theta$ and $\varphi \in \Phi$, user-chosen (rational) significance level $\alpha \in (0, 1)$, confidence sets $\hat{\Theta}$ and $\hat{\Phi}$ for θ^* and φ^* respectively with (rational) significance level at most β for $2\beta \leq \alpha$, tiebreaking permutation σ on $[m-1]_0$

- 1: Choose integers $1 \leq r \leq m$ such that $r/m \leq \alpha - 2\beta$.
- 2: Generate $m-1$ random permutation $\{\pi_j\}_{j=1}^{m-1}$ uniformly from S_n .
- 3: Construct noise term functions for $t = 1, \dots, n$ by

$$\begin{aligned} E_t(\theta) &\doteq H_1^{-1}(q^{-1}, \theta) \left(Y_t - G_1(q^{-1}, \theta) U_t \right), \\ N_t(\varphi) &\doteq H_2^{-1}(q^{-1}, \varphi) \left(Z_t - G_2(q^{-1}, \varphi) V_t \right). \end{aligned} \tag{6.18}$$

- 4: Build $m-1$ alternative sample functions by $\mathcal{D}_j(\theta, \varphi) = \{(E_i(\theta), N_{\pi_j(i)}(\varphi))\}_{i=1}^n$ for $j \in [m-1]$ and let $\mathcal{D}_j^\sigma(\theta, \varphi) = (\mathcal{D}_j(\theta, \varphi), \sigma(j))$ for $j \in [m-1]_0$.
- 5: Compute $\hat{\Delta}_n^{(j)}(\theta, \varphi) = |\text{HSIC}_n(\mathcal{D}_j(\theta, \varphi))|$ for $j = 0, 1, \dots, m-1$.
- 6: Construct the parameter dependent ranking function

$$\begin{aligned} \psi(\theta, \varphi) &\doteq \psi\left(\mathcal{D}_0^\sigma(\theta, \varphi), \dots, \mathcal{D}_{m-1}^\sigma(\theta, \varphi)\right) \\ &= 1 + \sum_{j=1}^{m-1} \mathbb{I}\left(\hat{\Delta}_n^{(0)}(\theta, \varphi) \prec_\sigma \hat{\Delta}_n^{(j)}(\theta, \varphi)\right). \end{aligned} \tag{6.19}$$

- 7: Reject the null hypothesis if and only if $\max_{\theta \in \hat{\Theta}, \varphi \in \hat{\Phi}} \psi(\theta, \varphi) \leq r$.
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space for $p = \infty$, i.e., for $(W_t) \in \{(U_t), (V_t), (E_t), (N_t)\}$ we have

$$\|W\|_{c(\infty)} \doteq \sup_{n \in \mathbb{N}} \frac{1}{n} \sum_{t=1}^n |W_t| < \infty. \tag{6.20}$$

D9. There a.s. exist $K, \tilde{\varepsilon} > 0$ such that for $\theta \in B(\theta^*, \tilde{\varepsilon})$:

$$\|E(\theta^*) - E(\theta)\|_{c(\infty)} \leq K \cdot \|\theta^* - \theta\|, \tag{6.21}$$

and respectively for $N(\varphi)$, where $\varphi \in B(\varphi^*, \tilde{\varepsilon})$.

D10. The confidence sets are uniformly consistent, i.e., for all $\varepsilon > 0$ there a.s. exists an $N_0 \in \mathbb{N}$ such that for all $n > N_0$ both $\hat{\Theta}_n \subseteq B(\theta^*, \varepsilon)$ and $\hat{\Phi}_n \subseteq B(\varphi^*, \varepsilon)$.

D11. HSIC_n is Lipschitz continuous around (θ^*, φ^*) , i.e., $\exists C, \tilde{\varepsilon} > 0$ such that

$$\begin{aligned} &\left| \text{HSIC}_n(\mathcal{D}_j(\theta^*, \varphi^*)) - \text{HSIC}_n(\mathcal{D}_j(\theta, \varphi)) \right| \\ &\leq C \cdot \left(\|E(\theta^*) - E(\theta)\|_{c(\infty)} + \|N(\varphi^*) - N(\varphi)\|_{c(\infty)} \right) \end{aligned} \tag{6.22}$$

for $\theta \in B(\theta^*, \tilde{\varepsilon}), \varphi \in B(\varphi^*, \tilde{\varepsilon})$ and $j = 0, \dots, m-1$.

Theorem 6.4.2. *Assume D1-D11. If H_1 holds true, then*

$$\mathbb{P}\left(\max_{(\theta, \varphi) \in \widehat{\Theta}_n \times \widehat{\Phi}_n} \psi(\theta, \varphi) \leq r\right) \xrightarrow{n \rightarrow \infty} 1. \quad (6.23)$$

Proof. We use a characteristic HSIC, thus under H_1 we have $\widehat{\Delta}_n^{(0)}(\theta^*, \varphi^*) \xrightarrow{p} \kappa \doteq |\text{HSIC}(E, N)| > 0$. In addition, $\widehat{\Delta}_n^{(j)}(\theta^*, \varphi^*) \xrightarrow{p} 0$ for $j \in [m-1]$ because of (6.9). Let us fix a positive ε that is smaller than $\tilde{\varepsilon}$ and $\tilde{\tilde{\varepsilon}}$. By D10, there exists almost surely an $N_0 \in \mathbb{N}$ such that $\widehat{\Theta}_n \in B(\theta^*, \varepsilon)$ and $\widehat{\Phi}_n \in B(\varphi^*, \varepsilon)$ for all $n > N_0$. We prove that for n large enough the rank values equal to 1 uniformly on $B(\theta^*, \varepsilon) \times B(\varphi^*, \varepsilon)$ with large probability. We know that $\widehat{\Delta}_n^{(j)}(\theta^*, \varphi^*)$ is closer than ε to κ with large probability if n is large enough. Then, condition D9 and D10 yield

$$\begin{aligned} |\widehat{\Delta}_n^{(0)}(\theta^*, \varphi^*) - \widehat{\Delta}_n^{(0)}(\theta, \varphi)| &\leq C \cdot \left(\|E(\theta^*) - E(\theta)\|_{c(\infty)} + \|N(\varphi^*) - N(\varphi)\|_{c(\infty)} \right) \\ &\leq C \cdot K \cdot \left(\|\theta^* - \theta\| + \|\varphi^* - \varphi\| \right), \end{aligned}$$

which proves that there exists $C_1 > 0$ such that a.s.

$$\sup_{\theta \in B(\theta^*, \varepsilon), \varphi \in B(\varphi^*, \varepsilon)} \left| \widehat{\Delta}_n^{(0)}(\theta^*, \varphi^*) - \widehat{\Delta}_n^{(0)}(\theta, \varphi) \right| \leq C_1 \cdot \varepsilon.$$

Thus, the infimum of $\widehat{\Delta}_n^{(0)}(\theta, \varphi)$ on confidence set $\widehat{\Theta}_n \times \widehat{\Phi}_n$ tends to κ in probability. Similarly one can prove that $\sup \widehat{\Delta}_n^{(j)}(\theta, \varphi)$ on $\widehat{\Theta}_n \times \widehat{\Phi}_n$ tends to 0 for $j = 1, \dots, m-1$, implying that the probability of rejection goes to 1. \square

6.5 Demonstrative Example

We consider two autoregressive (AR) systems: $Y_t = \alpha_* Y_{t-1} + E_t$, and $Z_t = \beta_* Z_{t-1} + N_t$ with $\alpha_* = 0.5$ and $\beta_* = 0.3$. For parameters (α, β) the residuals $(E_t(\alpha))$ and $(N_t(\beta))$ can be computed from $(Y_t), (Z_t)$ as $E_t(\alpha) = Y_t - \alpha Y_{t-1}$ and similarly for $(N_t(\beta))$. For AR systems, the required Lipschitz continuity can be easily satisfied. If $|\alpha| < 1$, then under D8 one can prove $\|Y\|_{c(\infty)} < \infty$ and D9. If $k \otimes \ell$ is Lipschitz and characteristic, then D11 is also satisfied for HSIC estimates.

6.5.1 Sign-Perturbed Sums

For autoregressive systems with exogenous inputs (ARX) systems, confidence regions satisfying D10 can be constructed, e.g., by using the SPS method (Csáji et al., 2014). SPS can build exact confidence regions with user-chosen confidence levels for the true parameters of the ARX systems (Csáji et al., 2012; Csáji and Weyer, 2015). Originally, the symmetricity of the noise terms was required to apply SPS, and the noises were allowed to change over time. Under the i.i.d. assumption, symmetry is no more required, if we apply a slight modifications of the core algorithm (Kolumbán et al., 2015). Non-asymptotically exact confidence levels are reached by ranking the perturbed gradient of

Algorithm 8 Sign-Perturbed Sums for ARX Systems

Inputs: observations (U_t) , (Y_t) , system orders p and q , tiebreaking permutation σ , user-chosen (rational) significance level $\beta \in [0, 1]$

- 1: Choose integers $1 \leq r \leq m$ such that $r/m = \beta$.
- 2: Compute the prediction errors for $\theta = (a^T, b^T)^T \in \mathbb{R}^{p+q}$:

$$E_t(\theta) \doteq Y_t - \varphi_t^T \theta \text{ for } t \in [n], \quad (6.24)$$

where $\varphi_t \doteq [Y_t, \dots, Y_{t-p}, U_{t-1}, \dots, U_{t-q}]^T$.

- 3: Generate $m - 1$ independent Rademacher vectors, $\alpha_j \doteq (\alpha_{j,t})_{t=1}^n$ for $j \in [m - 1]$.
- 4: Construct perturbed outputs and regressors with $\bar{Y}_t(\theta, \alpha_j) = 0$ for $t \leq 0$, and for $t \in [n]$ and $j \in [m - 1]$ by

$$\begin{aligned} \bar{Y}_t(\theta, \alpha_j) &\doteq \sum_{i=1}^p b_i U_{t-i} + \sum_{i=1}^q a_i \bar{Y}_{t-i}(\theta, \alpha_j) + \alpha_{j,t} E_t(\theta), \\ \bar{\varphi}_t(\theta, \alpha_j) &\doteq [\bar{Y}_{t-1}(\theta, \alpha_j), \dots, \bar{Y}_{t-p}(\theta, \alpha_j), U_{t-1}, \dots, U_{t-q}]^T. \end{aligned} \quad (6.25)$$

- 5: Compute the reference variables that follow for $j \in [m - 1]_0$:

$$\begin{aligned} S_0(\theta) &\doteq \Phi_n^{-1/2} \sum_{t=1}^n \varphi_t (Y_t - \varphi_t^T \theta), \\ S_j(\theta) &\doteq \Phi_n^{-1/2}(\theta, \alpha_j) \sum_{t=1}^n \bar{\varphi}_t(\theta, \alpha_j) \alpha_{j,t} (Y_t - \varphi_t^T \theta), \end{aligned} \quad (6.26)$$

where $\Phi_n \doteq \frac{1}{n} \sum_{t=1}^n \varphi_t \varphi_t^T$ and $\bar{\Phi}_n(\theta, \alpha_j)$ is constructed similarly from $\bar{\varphi}_t(\theta, \alpha_j)$.

- 6: Construct the ranking function by

$$\psi(\theta) \doteq 1 + \sum_{j=1}^{m-1} \mathbb{I} \left(\|S_0(\theta)\| \succ_{\sigma} \|S_j(\theta)\| \right). \quad (6.27)$$

- 7: Let $\hat{\Theta}_n \doteq \{\theta \in \mathbb{R}^{p+q} : \psi(\theta) \leq m - r\}$.
-

the square error criterion. The uniform consistency of SPS was proved in (Weyer et al., 2017); later an instrumental variable-based extension was proposed by Volpe et al. (2015), which is uniformly consistent, even in case of ARX systems under feedback control, i.e., it satisfies D10 even in closed-loop setups, where computationally efficient ellipsoidal outer approximations are also presented. The pseudocode of the SPS method for ARX systems is included in Algorithm 8 for the sake of completeness.

6.5.2 Numerical Simulations

We simulated two AR systems with nonlinearly dependent i.i.d. innovations $\{(E_t, N_t)\}_{i=1}^n$. The processes were initialized in zero, cf. D4. First, a rotated mixture of Gaussian distributions (Gretton et al., 2008) was considered for innovations, see Figure 6.1e. We generated a sample with $n = 50$ elements from a zero mean two-dimensional

Figure 6.1: Reference functions, ranking functions, innovation data and power functions for AR systems.

Gaussian distribution with covariance matrix $\frac{1}{4} \cdot \mathbb{I}$, then we shifted each data-point with a pair of random signs and rotated the obtained points around the origin with an angle of 0.1 (radian). We used SPS to construct confidence sets for α_* and β_* with significance level $1/80$ and tested independence with $m = 40$ datasets. We maximized the ranking function on a fine grid of the confidence region.

Reference value function $\hat{\Delta}_n^{(0)}$ and ranking function ψ is plotted on Figure 6.1a and 6.1b. We compared our HSIC-based ranking to a distance covariance based method which is introduced in (Tamás et al., 2023). The distance covariance based method is showed on Figure 6.1c and 6.1d. At significance level 0.15 based on Figure 6.1b we reject the null hypothesis, but we accept H_0 at this level based on Figure 6.1d, because the ranking function exceeds 5 for some parameters. The (estimated) power functions, i.e., the rejection probability functions, are plotted for $n = 200$ and significance level 0.15 on Figure 6.1f w.r.t. the rotation angle, which served as a dependence factor. Second, a sample from an extinct version of Gaussian vector variable with covariance $\frac{1}{4} \cdot \mathbb{I}$ was used to generate innovations, see Figure 6.1g. We induced dependence between E and N by throwing away the pairs that lied in a circle around the origin with radius r . Figure 6.1h shows the (estimated) power functions w.r.t. the distinction rate increasing with r for $n = 500$ using HSIC and distance covariance with significance level 0.15.

6.6 Discussion

In this chapter we introduced a hypothesis test for the independence of synchronous linear systems with non-asymptotically guaranteed significance levels. The main idea was to apply permutation tests over a confidence region for the system parameters. We combined these methods with HSIC to detect any nonlinear dependence between the innovations of the systems. We proved consistency under mild distributional and structural assumptions and demonstrated the method on AR systems.

Chapter 7

Conclusions

In recent decades ML “glorified” statistics by propelling the revolution of AI. Uncertainty quantification became an intrinsic task in ML for most real world applications, especially for the ones that need to meet strict safety, stability or quality criteria. We presented stochastic guarantees for statistical learning methods in a data-driven, distribution-free framework. Our methods provide theoretical background for robust, reliable and trustworthy ML applications by quantifying uncertainty under very mild structural and distributional assumptions. Four fundamental statistical problems were considered from distribution-free and non-asymptotic viewpoints: heavy-tailed mean estimation, binary classification, CKME estimation and independence testing. In the last chapter we summarize our main contributions and highlight possible future research directions.

7.1 Confidence Regions for Supervised Learning

First, the fundamental problem of mean estimation was considered. The RMM method was introduced for constructing exact confidence intervals for the mean of a symmetric distribution based on a finite set of i.i.d. sample. We proved that our hyperparameter-free method builds exact confidence intervals that shrink with optimal rates. Second, we presented a distribution-free resampling framework to build exact confidence regions for the regression function of binary classification for any finite sample size. We proved strong uniform bounds for a novel ERM based method for model classes with finite pseudo-dimension and inverse Lipschitz parameterization and provided PAC bounds on the \mathcal{L}_2 size of the confidence sets. Additionally, we introduced a kNN based and two variants of a CKME based methods and proved strong pointwise bounds under mild statistical assumptions. Our algorithms were demonstrated on a logistic model class and compared to asymptotic ellipsoids around the MLE.

7.2 Uncertainty Quantification for Kernel Methods

Kernel methods are popular nonparametric tools to deal with abstract sets and non-linear structures. They provide a neat framework to handle probability distributions by mapping them to a RKHS. In supervised learning problems where input-output pairs are modelled, the conditional distribution of the output given the input is often of interest. CKMEs can be used to encode the conditional distribution of an output. In Chapter 5 a new recursive algorithm was introduced to estimate the conditional kernel mean map in an RKHS valued Bochner space. Our results present sufficient conditions for the weak and strong L_2 consistency of the recursive estimator based on the generalization of Stone’s theorem. We demonstrated our results on three arch-typical input spaces including Euclidean spaces, Riemannian manifolds and locally compact subsets of function spaces.

7.3 Independence Testing with Finite Sample Guarantees

Independence testing is a key task in several fields including finance, industry, health care and sociology. In Chapter 6 robust independence tests with finite sample guarantees were introduced for stochastic linear time-invariant systems, assuming that the systems are driven by jointly i.i.d. innovations. Our method provides distribution-free bounds for the significance level, thus the innovations can have arbitrary joint distribution. The algorithm combines confidence regions with permutation tests and the Hilbert–Schmidt independence criterion to detect any nonlinear dependence between the observed systems. We proved the consistency of our hypothesis tests under mild structural assumptions and demonstrated the method with numerical experiments.

7.4 Future Research Directions

Our confidence regions offer data-driven solutions to several ML tasks such as prediction and decision-making. The RMM method have already been applied to stochastic multi-armed bandits, which is a fundamental reinforcement learning problem for the famous exploration-exploitation dilemma. We proved near-optimal regret bounds for the parameter-free RMM upper confidence bounds algorithm (Tamás et al., 2025). Additional applications of the confidence regions might cover contextual bandits (e.g., linear bandits) and robust control problems. Another interesting research direction is to construct point estimators based on our resampling framework admitting guaranteed performance. Proving convergence rates for the presented conditional kernel mean map estimator for a broad class of distributions is also an open problem of high importance. Building prediction regions based on CKME estimates is a promising direction to pursue, as well.

Appendix A

Appendix A contains the proofs which were left out from Chapter 3. Some additional details of the main proofs are also included. Finally, supplementary experiments are presented comparing the sizes of the RMM and SPS confidence intervals to nonparametric tests such as the sign test and Wilcoxon signed-rank test and illustrating the distribution of the confidence interval endpoints, and the empirical coverage probabilities of the tests based on the asymptotic theory, SPS and RMM.

A.1 Proofs for Heavy-Tailed Mean Estimation

This section contains the proofs of Theorems 3.2.5, Theorem 3.3.2 and Theorem 3.5.2; as well as additional details for Theorem 3.2.4.

Theorem 3.2.5. *Assume A1, A2 and A3. Let $\varrho > 0$, $k = \lceil 8 \log((m-r+1)/\varrho) \rceil$, $1 \leq r < m$ be user-chosen integers and \mathcal{R} be defined by (3.8). If*

$$4(\sigma^2 + d(\theta)^2) \frac{32 \log((m-r+1)/\varrho)}{n} \leq d(\theta)^2 \quad (\text{A.1})$$

holds for $d(\theta) = |\mu - \theta|$, then we have

$$\mathbb{P}(\mathcal{R}(\theta) \leq m-r) \leq \varrho. \quad (\text{A.2})$$

Proof. Let us fix $\theta \neq \mu$, integers $1 \leq r < m$ and use notation $\hat{\mu}^j \doteq \hat{\mu}(\mathcal{D}_j(\theta))$ for $j = 0, \dots, m-1$. The following lower bound holds

$$\mathbb{P}(\mathcal{R}(\theta) > m-r) \geq \mathbb{P}\left(|\hat{\mu}^0 - \mu| < d/2, |\hat{\mu}^j - \theta| < d/2 \text{ for } j = 1, \dots, m-r\right), \quad (\text{A.3})$$

because from $|\hat{\mu}^0 - \mu| < d/2$ it follows that $|\hat{\mu}^0 - \theta| \geq d/2$. Let us define events

$$\begin{aligned} B_0 &\doteq \{|\hat{\mu} - \mu| < d/2\}, \\ B_j &\doteq \{|\hat{\mu}^j - \theta| < d/2\} \text{ for } j = 1, \dots, m-1. \end{aligned} \quad (\text{A.4})$$

By the union bound we have

$$\mathbb{P}\left(\bigcup_{j=0}^{m-r} \bar{B}_j\right) \leq \sum_{j=0}^{m-r} \mathbb{P}(\bar{B}_j) \leq \mathbb{P}\left(|\hat{\mu}^0 - \mu| \geq d/2\right) + \sum_{j=1}^{m-r} \mathbb{P}\left(|\hat{\mu}^j - \theta| \geq d/2\right). \quad (\text{A.5})$$

and henceforth if

$$4(\sigma^2 + d^2) \frac{32 \log((m-r+1)/\varrho)}{n} < d^2, \quad (\text{A.6})$$

then we have

$$\mathbb{P}\left(|\hat{\mu}^j - \theta| \geq d/2\right) \leq \mathbb{P}\left(|\hat{\mu}^j - \theta| > \sqrt{\frac{(\sigma^2 + d^2)32 \log((m-r+1)/\varrho)}{n}}\right) \leq \frac{\varrho}{m-r+1}. \quad (\text{A.7})$$

In addition, because of

$$4\sigma^2 \frac{32 \log((m-r+1)/\varrho)}{n} \leq 4(\sigma^2 + d^2) \frac{32 \log((m-r+1)/\varrho)}{n} < d^2, \quad (\text{A.8})$$

we also have

$$\mathbb{P}\left(|\hat{\mu}^0 - \theta| \geq d/2\right) \leq \mathbb{P}\left(|\hat{\mu}^j - \theta| > \sigma \sqrt{\frac{32 \log((m-r+1)/\varrho)}{n}}\right) \leq \frac{\varrho}{m-r+1}. \quad (\text{A.9})$$

In conclusion,

$$\mathbb{P}\left(\mathcal{R}(\theta) > m-r\right) \geq \mathbb{P}\left(\bigcap_{j=0}^{m-r} B_j\right) \geq 1 - \sum_{j=0}^{m-1} \mathbb{P}(\bar{B}_j) \geq 1 - \varrho. \quad (\text{A.10})$$

Note that for any $\theta \neq \mu$ for n large enough (A.6) is satisfied. \square

Equality 45 for Theorem 3.2.4

$$\begin{aligned} \nu^+ &= \text{med}_{\ell \in [k]} \nu_\ell^+ = \text{med}_{\ell \in [k]} \left(\frac{\hat{\mu}(\mathcal{D}_0) + \frac{1}{\tilde{n}} \sum_{i=(\ell-1)\tilde{n}}^{\ell\tilde{n}} \alpha_{i,1} Y_i}{1 + \frac{1}{\tilde{n}} \sum_{i=(\ell-1)\tilde{n}}^{\ell\tilde{n}} \alpha_{i,1}} \right) \\ &= \text{med}_{\ell \in [k]} \left(\mu + \frac{\hat{\mu}(\mathcal{W}_0) + \frac{1}{\tilde{n}} \sum_{i=(\ell-1)\tilde{n}}^{\ell\tilde{n}} \alpha_{i,1} W_i}{\frac{1}{\tilde{n}} \sum_{i=(\ell-1)\tilde{n}}^{\ell\tilde{n}} (1 + \alpha_{i,1})} \right) \\ &= \mu + \text{med}_{\ell \in [k]} \left(\frac{\hat{\mu}(\mathcal{W}_0) + \frac{1}{\tilde{n}} \sum_{i=(\ell-1)\tilde{n}}^{\ell\tilde{n}} \alpha_{i,1} W_i}{\frac{2}{\tilde{n}} (\tilde{n} - Z_\ell)} \right) = \mu + V^+. \end{aligned} \quad (\text{A.11})$$

Inequality 51 for Theorem 3.2.4.

$$\begin{aligned}
\mathbb{P}(B \cap A) &\leq \mathbb{P}(\tilde{B} \cap A) \leq \mathbb{P}\left(\text{med}_{\ell \in [k]} \left(\hat{\mu}(\mathcal{W}_0) - \frac{1}{\tilde{n}} \sum_{i=(\ell-1)\tilde{n}}^{\ell\tilde{n}} \alpha_{i,1} W_i \right) > \varepsilon/4 \right) \\
&= \mathbb{P}\left(\hat{\mu}(\mathcal{W}_0) - \text{med}_{\ell \in [k]} \left(\frac{1}{\tilde{n}} \sum_{i=(\ell-1)\tilde{n}}^{\ell\tilde{n}} \alpha_{i,1} W_i \right) > \varepsilon/4 \right) \\
&\leq \mathbb{P}\left(\left\{ \hat{\mu}(\mathcal{W}_0) > \varepsilon/8 \right\} \cup \left\{ -\text{med}_{\ell \in [k]} \frac{1}{\tilde{n}} \sum_{i=(\ell-1)\tilde{n}}^{\ell\tilde{n}} \alpha_{i,1} W_i > \varepsilon/8 \right\} \right) \\
&\leq \mathbb{P}(\hat{\mu}(\mathcal{W}_0) > \varepsilon/8) + \mathbb{P}\left(\text{med}_{\ell \in [k]} \frac{1}{\tilde{n}} \sum_{i=(\ell-1)\tilde{n}}^{\ell\tilde{n}} -\alpha_{i,1} W_i > \varepsilon/8 \right) \leq 2 \cdot \mathbb{P}(\hat{\mu}(\mathcal{W}_0) > \varepsilon/8).
\end{aligned} \tag{A.12}$$

Theorem 3.3.2. *For $m \geq 2$ we have*

$$\Theta_n = \bigcup_{\substack{J \subseteq [m-1], j \in J \\ |J|=m-r}} \bigcap \left\{ \theta : S_0(\theta) \prec_\pi S_j(\theta) \right\}, \tag{A.13}$$

thus Θ_n is an interval that contains $\hat{\mu}(\mathcal{D}_0)$, if $\Theta_n \neq \emptyset$.

Proof. Equation (A.13) follows from the observation that

$$\begin{aligned}
\left\{ \theta : S_0(\theta) \prec_\pi S_j(\theta) \right\} &= \left\{ \theta : \mathbb{I}(S_0(\theta) \prec_j S_j(\theta)) = 1 \right\} \quad \text{and} \\
\bigcup_{\substack{J \subseteq [m-1], j \in J \\ |J|=m-r}} \bigcap \left\{ \theta : S_0(\theta) \prec_\pi S_j(\theta) \right\} &= \left\{ \theta : \mathcal{R}(\theta) \leq m-r \right\}.
\end{aligned} \tag{A.14}$$

We show that Θ_n is an interval in three steps. First, we prove that for all $j \in [m-1]$ $I_j \doteq \{\theta : S_0(\theta) \prec_\pi S_j(\theta)\}$ is an interval. Second, we show that if I_j is nonempty, then $\hat{\mu} = \hat{\mu}(\mathcal{D}_0)$ is included. Finally, we use (A.14) to conclude that Θ_n is an interval, because it is the union of intervals that have a common element or empty.

Clearly $\hat{\mu}$ is a parameter that should be included in I_j , because $S_0(\hat{\mu}) = 0$. More precisely if $\nu \in I_j$ and $\nu > \hat{\mu}$, then we prove that $[\hat{\mu}, \nu] \subseteq I_j$ (similarly for $\nu < \hat{\mu}$ if $\nu \in I_j$, then we have $[\nu, \hat{\mu}] \subseteq I_j$). Assume by contradiction that there exists $\bar{\theta} \in [\hat{\mu}, \nu]$ such that $S_j(\bar{\theta}) \prec_\pi S_0(\bar{\theta})$. We know that S_j is a piecewise linear function, of which slopes are included in $[-1, 1]$. We have $S_j(\theta) \leq \theta + S_j(\bar{\theta}) - \bar{\theta}$ for all $\theta > \bar{\theta}$, because the left derivative of S_j is at most 1. In addition for all $\theta < \nu$ we have $S_j(\theta) \geq \theta + S_j(\nu) - \nu$. If $\pi(0) < \pi(j)$, then $S_0(\nu) \prec_\pi S_0(\nu)$ implies $S_0(\nu) \leq S_j(\nu)$ and $S_j(\bar{\theta}) \prec_\pi S_0(\bar{\theta})$ implies $S_j(\bar{\theta}) < S_0(\bar{\theta})$. Thus, the contradiction follows by

$$\begin{aligned}
-\hat{\mu} &= \nu - \hat{\mu} - \nu = S_0(\nu) - \nu \leq S_j(\nu) - \nu \leq S_j(\theta) - \theta \\
&\leq S_j(\bar{\theta}) - \bar{\theta} < S_0(\bar{\theta}) - \bar{\theta} = \bar{\theta} - \hat{\mu} - \bar{\theta} = -\hat{\mu}.
\end{aligned} \tag{A.15}$$

One can proceed similarly for $\pi(0) > \pi(j)$. In conclusion we proved that I_j is an interval

and if there is at least one element in I_j , then $\hat{\mu}$ is also included. Henceforth, $\cap_{j \in J} I_j$ is also an interval for all $J \subseteq [m-1]$, which includes $\hat{\mu}$ or is empty. Finally, the same can be said about the union of these. \square

An auxiliary lemma for Theorem 3.5.2.

In this section, we present an auxiliary lemma for Theorem 4.2 and its detailed proof.

Lemma A.1.1. *Let Y be a random vector in \mathbb{R}^p such that $\mu \doteq \mathbb{E}[Y]$, $\Sigma_Y \doteq \text{var}(Y)$, and $\lambda^* \doteq \lambda_{\max}(\Sigma_Y)$, the greatest eigenvalue of Σ_Y . Let $\theta \in \mathbb{R}^p$ and α be a Rademacher variable independent of Y , then for $Z = \alpha \mathbb{1} \odot (Y - \theta) + \theta$, we have $\mathbb{E}[Z] = \theta$ and*

$$\text{Tr}(\text{var}(Z)) = \text{Tr}(\Sigma_Y) + \|\mu - \theta\|^2, \quad (\text{A.16})$$

$$\lambda_{\max}(\text{var}(Z)) \leq \lambda_{\max}(\Sigma_Y) + \|\mu - \theta\|^2. \quad (\text{A.17})$$

Proof. Because of independence we have $\mathbb{E}[\alpha \odot (Y - \theta) + \theta] = \mathbb{E}[\alpha] \odot \mathbb{E}[(Y - \theta)] + \theta = \theta$. We can show (A.16) by

$$\begin{aligned} \text{Tr}(\text{var}(Z)) &= \text{Tr}(\mathbb{E}[(\alpha \mathbb{1} \odot (Y - \theta) + \theta - \mathbb{E}Z)(\alpha \mathbb{1} \odot (Y - \theta) + \theta - \mathbb{E}Z)^T]) \\ &= \text{Tr}(\mathbb{E}[(\alpha \mathbb{1} \odot (Y - \theta))(\alpha \mathbb{1} \odot (Y - \theta))^T]) \\ &= \text{Tr}(\mathbb{E}[(Y - \mu + \mu - \theta)(Y - \mu + \mu - \theta)^T]) \\ &= \text{Tr}(\Sigma_Y + (\mu - \theta)(\mu - \theta)^T) = \text{Tr}(\Sigma_Y) + \|\mu - \theta\|^2, \end{aligned} \quad (\text{A.18})$$

where we also proved that $\text{var}(Z) = \Sigma_Y + (\mu - \theta)(\mu - \theta)^T$. For (A.17) we use the well-known fact that for a symmetric real matrix A we have

$$\lambda_{\max}(A) = \max_{x: \|x\|=1} x^T A x. \quad (\text{A.19})$$

Therefore

$$\begin{aligned} \lambda_{\max}(\text{var}(Z)) &= \max_{x: \|x\|=1} x^T \text{var}(Z) x = \max_{x: \|x\|=1} x^T (\Sigma_Y + (\mu - \theta)(\mu - \theta)^T) x \\ &= \max_{x: \|x\|=1} (x^T \Sigma_Y x + x^T (\mu - \theta)(\mu - \theta)^T x) \leq \lambda^* + \|\mu - \theta\|^2, \end{aligned} \quad (\text{A.20})$$

where we used that the largest eigenvalue of vv^T equals to $\|v\|^2$. \square

Theorem 3.5.2. *Assume A1, A4, A5 and A6. Let $\varrho > 0$ and $1 \leq r < m$ be user-chosen integers. For $\theta \neq \mu$ if*

$$\sqrt{\frac{c_1(\text{Tr}(\Sigma) + \Delta(\theta)^2)}{n}} + \sqrt{\frac{c_2(\lambda^* + \Delta(\theta)^2) \log\left(\frac{c_3(m-r)}{\varrho}\right)}{n}} < \frac{\Delta(\theta)}{2}, \quad (\text{A.21})$$

holds, where $\Delta(\theta) = \|\theta - \mu\|$, then we have

$$\mathbb{P}(\mathcal{R}(\theta) \leq m - r) \leq \varrho. \quad (\text{A.22})$$

Proof. Let us fix $\theta \neq \mu$, integers $1 \leq r \leq m$ and use notation $\hat{\mu}^j \doteq \hat{\mu}(\mathcal{D}_j(\theta))$ for $j = 0, \dots, m - 1$. The following lower bound holds

$$\mathbb{P}(\mathcal{R}(\theta) > m - r) \geq \mathbb{P}\left(\|\hat{\mu}^0 - \mu\| < \Delta/2, \|\hat{\mu}^j - \theta\| < \Delta/2 \text{ for } j = 1, \dots, m - r\right), \quad (\text{A.23})$$

because from $\|\hat{\mu}^0 - \mu\| < \Delta/2$ it follows that $\|\hat{\mu}^0 - \theta\| \geq \Delta/2$. Let us define events

$$\begin{aligned} B_0 &\doteq \{\|\hat{\mu}^0 - \mu\| < \Delta/2\}, \\ B_j &\doteq \{\|\hat{\mu}^j - \theta\| < \Delta/2\} \text{ for } j = 1, \dots, m - 1. \end{aligned} \quad (\text{A.24})$$

Then, by the union bound we have

$$\mathbb{P}\left(\bigcup_{j=0}^{m-r} \bar{B}_j\right) \leq \sum_{j=0}^{m-r} \mathbb{P}(\bar{B}_j) \leq \mathbb{P}\left(\|\hat{\mu}^0 - \mu\| \geq \Delta/2\right) + \sum_{j=1}^{m-r} \mathbb{P}\left(\|\hat{\mu}^j - \theta\| \geq \Delta/2\right). \quad (\text{A.25})$$

Because of A6 the first term can be bounded by

$$\mathbb{P}\left(\|\hat{\mu}^0 - \mu\| \geq \Delta/2\right) \leq \mathbb{P}\left(\|\hat{\mu}^0 - \mu\| > \sqrt{\frac{c_1 \text{Tr}(\Sigma)}{n}} + \sqrt{\frac{c_2 \lambda^* \log(c_3(m-r)/\varrho)}{n}}\right) \leq \tilde{\varrho}, \quad (\text{A.26})$$

where $\varrho = (m - r + 1)\tilde{\varrho}$. The other terms can be bounded similarly by

$$\mathbb{P}\left(\|\hat{\mu}^j - \theta\| \geq \Delta/2\right) \leq \mathbb{P}\left(\|\hat{\mu}^j - \theta\| > \sqrt{\frac{c_1(\text{Tr}(\Sigma) + \Delta^2)}{n}} + \sqrt{\frac{c_2(\lambda^* + \Delta^2) \log(c_3(m-r)/\varrho)}{n}}\right). \quad (\text{A.27})$$

In conclusion, under the required conditions we have

$$\mathbb{P}(\mathcal{R}(\theta) \leq m - r) \leq (m - r + 1)\tilde{\varrho} = \varrho, \quad (\text{A.28})$$

which proves the desired bound. \square

A.2 Supplementary Numerical Experiments

A.2.1 Confidence Interval Size Experiment

In this experiment we compare the empirical sizes of several confidence regions for different sample distributions. We consider the mean estimation problems, where Y is sampled from a (a) symmetrized Pareto II distribution with shape parameter $a = 1.6$ and scale parameter 1, (b) zero-mean Laplace distribution with scale parameter $\lambda = 1$, (c) standard normal distribution and (d) uniform distribution on interval $(-10, 10)$. The

Figure A.1: Comparison of confidence interval sizes

sizes of the RMM and SPS confidence regions are compared to the sizes of the sign test-based and Wilcoxon signed-rank test-based confidence intervals. For the Wilcoxon signed-rank test we used the statistical package of R with approximate confidence levels. Throughout our experiments we considered 0.5-level confidence regions, with $m = 20$ and $r = 10$ in case of the RMM and SPS, a sample size of $n = 5000$ and $s = 10000$ independently simulated trajectories. For the Wilcoxon signed-rank test we used fewer independent simulations ($s' = 100$), because constructing the confidence intervals based on this test is computationally intensive and there was a very small variance regarding the sizes. The difference between the 0.9-quantiles of the confidence interval sizes for the different sample distributions are shown in Figure A.1. It can be observed that in case of the heavy-tailed Pareto II distribution the sizes of the confidence regions based on the sign test and the Wilcoxon signed-rank test are smaller than those based on the RMM and SPS. Recall that despite their smaller sizes, these order-based tests have no guarantees for their shrinking rates, also the Wilcoxon signed-rank test has high computational burden and admits only approximate guarantees for the coverage probability. These experiments

Figure A.2: Comparison of confidence interval end point distributions.

also indicate that as the sample distribution becomes less heavy-tailed, the RMM and SPS methods build confidence intervals with smaller sizes than the sign and Wilcoxon signed-rank tests. We can conclude that the RMM method can be a robust solution, because it achieves a significant improvement for heavy-tailed distributions w.r.t. the SPS method and is more efficient than the tested nonparametric methods for light-tailed distributions.

A.2.2 Experiment: Distribution of Intersections

We present an empirical comparison between the SPS and the RMM methods for sample distributions with different tail probabilities. In these simulations the empirical distributions of the random variables that determine the confidence intervals (the end point of the intervals) are investigated. In case of the SPS algorithm these points can be computed as in (Szentpéteri and Csáji, 2023), while in case of the RMM method these points are ν^+ and ν^- . In the experiments the observations were (symmetrically) Pareto-distributed with scale parameter 1 and shape parameter β . We set $k = 5$, considered a sample size of $n = 125$ and $s = 100000$ independently generated end points. Our results are shown for different β parameters in Figure A.2. The empirical distributions indicate that for heavy-tailed noises the end points (that determine the confidence interval) are more concentrated about 0 in case of the RMM method, while for less heavy-tailed noises they are more concentrated in case of the the SPS method.

A.2.3 Experiment: Coverage Probability

We studied the empirical coverage probabilities of asymptotic CLT-based confidence intervals, the SPS algorithm and the RMM method. In this experiment we considered $n = 30$, $k = 3$ and $s = 100000$ independently generated confidence intervals and computed the empirical probabilities \hat{p} that the true parameter is in the region. The observations were (symmetrically) Pareto-distributed with scale parameter 1 and shape parameter β as before. Our results are summarized in Table A.1. We can observe that the confidence levels are always exact for the RMM and SPS methods, however, the asymptotic confidence intervals can perform poorly. On the one hand for $\beta \leq 2$ the true variance of the unknown

Table A.1: Empirical coverage probabilities for $n = 30$, $k = 3$ and $s = 100000$.

	\hat{P}_A	\hat{P}_{SPS}	\hat{P}_{RMM}
$\beta = 1.1$	0.999	0.899	0.898
$\beta = 1.5$	0.987	0.901	0.901
$\beta = 2$	0.938	0.901	0.900
$\beta = 3$	0.748	0.901	0.900

distribution is infinite, thus the asymptotic intervals constructed based on the sample variance are too large. On the other hand for $\beta = 3$ and $n = 30$ the limit distribution is a poor approximation of the distribution of the mean and the asymptotic method underestimates the uncertainty of the sample mean.

Appendix B

Appendix B contains the proofs of Theorem 4.3.1, Theorem 4.4.1, Theorem 4.4.2 and Theorem 4.6.1. Additionally, we included several model classes that can be used with the ERM-based approach. Finally, we present the theoretical background of asymptotic confidence ellipsoids around the MLE for logistic regression and some fundamental results that are applied in the proofs.

B.1 Proof of Theorem 4.3.1

Theorem 4.3.1. *Assume that B1, B2 and B3 hold. Then, for any ranking function ψ , integers $1 \leq q_1 \leq q_2 \leq m$ and sample size $n \in \mathbb{N}^+$ we have*

$$\mathbb{P}(\theta^* \in \Theta_n^\psi) = \frac{q_2 - q_1 + 1}{m}. \quad (\text{B.1})$$

Proof. We observed that $\mathcal{D}_0, \mathcal{D}_1(\theta^*), \dots, \mathcal{D}_{m-1}(\theta^*)$ are conditionally i.i.d. with respect to the inputs, $\{X_i\}_{i=1}^n$, hence their extended versions are exchangeable, and also (a.s.) pairwise different due to their constructions. Thus, Lemma 3.2.1 implies that $\psi(\mathcal{D}_0^\pi(\theta), \{\mathcal{D}_k^\pi(\theta)\}_{k \neq 0}) = k$ with exact probability $1/m$ for all $k \in [m]$. \square

B.2 Proofs of Theorem 4.4.1 and Theorem 4.4.2

The proof of strong uniform consistency relies on the ULLN, in particular on the concepts of packing and covering numbers and three auxiliary lemmas. First, we present these concepts and the lemmas. Then, we apply the lemmas to prove the theorems.

Condition B6 bounds the pseudo-dimension of \mathcal{F}_0 which is sufficient for the ULLN to hold on \mathcal{F}_0 (Györfi et al., 2002, Theorem 9.6), however, we need to apply the ULLN on the transformation of \mathcal{F}_0 , thus let us consider the set of $\mathbb{X} \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$ type functions given by

$$\mathcal{G} \doteq \{h = (f - g)^2 \mid f, g \in \mathcal{F}_0\}. \quad (\text{B.2})$$

The first step in the proof is to show that condition B6 is sufficient for $V_{\mathcal{G}^+} < \infty$ to hold. Proving this is straightforward with the help of covering and packing numbers.

Our reasoning is motivated by the arguments in (Györfi et al., 2002; Shalev-Shwartz and Ben-David, 2014; Vapnik, 1998; Wainwright, 2019).

Definition B.2.1 (ε -covering number and packing number). *Let \mathcal{F} be a class of real-valued functions and $\|\cdot\|$ be a norm on \mathcal{F} and $\varepsilon > 0$.*

1. *A set $\{f_1, \dots, f_k\}$ is an ε -cover of \mathcal{F} w.r.t. $\|\cdot\|$, if for all $f \in \mathcal{F}$ there exists an index $j \in [k]$ such that $\|f_j - f\| \leq \varepsilon$. The size of the smallest ε -cover of \mathcal{F} w.r.t. $\|\cdot\|$ is denoted by $\mathcal{N}(\varepsilon, \mathcal{F}, \|\cdot\|)$ and it is called the ε -covering number of \mathcal{F} w.r.t. $\|\cdot\|$.*
2. *A set $\{f_1, \dots, f_l\} \subseteq \mathcal{F}$ is an ε -packing of \mathcal{F} w.r.t. $\|\cdot\|$ if for all $1 \leq i < j \leq l$ we have $\|f_i - f_j\| > \varepsilon$. The size of the largest ε -packing of \mathcal{F} w.r.t. $\|\cdot\|$ is denoted by $\mathcal{M}(\varepsilon, \mathcal{F}, \|\cdot\|)$ and it is called the ε -packing number of \mathcal{F} w.r.t. $\|\cdot\|$.*

Both $\mathcal{N}(\varepsilon, \mathcal{F}, \|\cdot\|)$ and $\mathcal{M}(\varepsilon, \mathcal{F}, \|\cdot\|)$ can be infinite.

In the proof we consider random L_p covers with respect to the empirical measure, that is, for a random vector $(X_1, \dots, X_n) \in \mathbb{X}^n$ let Q_n denote the empirical measure, i.e., let $Q_n(A) \doteq \frac{1}{n} \sum_{i=1}^n \mathbb{I}(X_i \in A)$ for all measurable A and let

$$\begin{aligned} \mathcal{N}_1(\varepsilon, \mathcal{G}, \{X_1, \dots, X_n\}) &\doteq \mathcal{N}\left(\varepsilon, \mathcal{G}, \|\cdot\|_{L_1(Q_n)}\right), \\ \mathcal{M}_1(\varepsilon, \mathcal{G}, \{X_1, \dots, X_n\}) &\doteq \mathcal{M}\left(\varepsilon, \mathcal{G}, \|\cdot\|_{L_1(Q_n)}\right), \end{aligned} \tag{B.3}$$

denote the random $L_1(Q_n)$ ε -covering and packing numbers of \mathcal{G} . A sufficient condition for the ULLN can be formulated with the help of these terms, i.e., the ULLN holds if the expectations of the $L_1(Q_n)$ -covering numbers are summable (Györfi et al., 2002, Theorem 9.1). The referred theorem is included in Appendix B.6. Thus, bounding the expectation of the $L_1(Q_n)$ -covering number is a key step in the proof of Theorem 4.4.1.

Lemma B.2.1. *Let X_1, \dots, X_n be random vectors in \mathbb{R}^d . If B6 holds, then for all $\varepsilon > 0$ there exists a constant $C(\varepsilon, V_{\mathcal{F}_0^+})$, independent of X_1, \dots, X_n , such that*

$$\mathcal{N}_1(\varepsilon, \mathcal{G}, \{X_1, \dots, X_n\}) \leq C(\varepsilon, V_{\mathcal{F}_0^+}). \tag{B.4}$$

Proof. First, we show that for any $x_1, \dots, x_n \in \mathbb{X}$ we have

$$\mathcal{N}_1(\varepsilon, \mathcal{G}, \{x_1, \dots, x_n\}) \leq \left(\mathcal{N}_1(\varepsilon/8, \mathcal{F}_0, \{x_1, \dots, x_n\})\right)^2. \tag{B.5}$$

Let $\{f_1, \dots, f_k\}$ be an $\varepsilon/8$ -cover of \mathcal{F}_0 w.r.t. the $L_1(Q_n)$ norm with minimal size. It can be assumed w.l.o.g. that f_i is bounded between $[-1, 1]$ for all $i \in [k]$, otherwise the truncated versions can be used. We argue that $\{(f_i - f_j)^2 \mid i, j \in [k]\}$ is an ε -cover of \mathcal{G} including at most k^2 elements. For an arbitrary $h \in \mathcal{G}$ there exist $f, g \in \mathcal{F}_0$ such that $h = (f - g)^2$. For these functions one can find indexes $i(f), j(g) \in [k]$ such that

$$\|f - f_i\|_{L_1(Q_n)} \leq \varepsilon/8 \quad \text{and} \quad \|g - f_j\|_{L_1(Q_n)} \leq \varepsilon/8. \tag{B.6}$$

Since f, g, f_i and f_j are all bounded in $[-1, 1]$ and (B.6) holds, we obtain that

$$\begin{aligned} \int |h - (f_i - f_j)^2| dQ_n &= \int |(f - g)^2 - (f_i - f_j)^2| dQ_n \\ &\leq \int |(f - g + f_i - f_j)(f - g - f_i + f_j)| dQ_n \quad (\text{B.7}) \\ &\leq 4 \int |f - f_i| dQ_n + 4 \int |g - f_j| dQ_n \leq \varepsilon, \end{aligned}$$

thus (B.5) is proved. In the second step we consider class $\tilde{\mathcal{F}} \doteq \{1/2(f + 1) \mid f \in \mathcal{F}_0\}$ to satisfy the condition of Theorem B.6.2, requiring the boundedness of each $\tilde{f} \in \tilde{\mathcal{F}}$ in $[0, 1]$. Notice that this transformation does not affect the pseudo-dimension, that is, $V_{\mathcal{F}_0^+} = V_{\tilde{\mathcal{F}}^+}$, and for the covering numbers it holds that

$$\mathcal{N}_1(\varepsilon/8, \mathcal{F}_0, \{x_1, \dots, x_n\}) \leq \mathcal{N}_1(\varepsilon/16, \tilde{\mathcal{F}}, \{x_1, \dots, x_n\}), \quad (\text{B.8})$$

because $\{f_1, \dots, f_k\}$ is an ε -cover of \mathcal{F}_0 if and only if $\{1/2(f_1 + 1), \dots, 1/2(f_k + 1)\}$ is an $\varepsilon/2$ -cover of $\tilde{\mathcal{F}}$. In the third step we bound the covering numbers with packing numbers by Lemma B.6.1, (Györfi et al., 2002), as

$$\mathcal{N}_1(\varepsilon/16, \tilde{\mathcal{F}}, \{x_1, \dots, x_n\}) \leq \mathcal{M}_1(\varepsilon/16, \tilde{\mathcal{F}}, \{x_1, \dots, x_n\}). \quad (\text{B.9})$$

Finally, by Theorem B.6.2 we derive an upper bound depending only on pseudo-dimension $V_{\mathcal{F}_0^+}$ and $\varepsilon > 0$, cf. (Haussler, 1995)),

$$\mathcal{M}_1(\varepsilon/16, \tilde{\mathcal{F}}, \{x_1, \dots, x_n\}) \leq e(V_{\mathcal{F}_0^+} + 1) \left(\frac{32e}{\varepsilon}\right)^{V_{\mathcal{F}_0^+}}, \quad (\text{B.10})$$

where we used that $V_{\mathcal{F}_0^+} = V_{\tilde{\mathcal{F}}^+}$. Combining these inequalities yields that

$$C(\varepsilon, V_{\mathcal{F}_0^+}) \doteq e^2(V_{\mathcal{F}_0^+} + 1)^2 \left(\frac{32e}{\varepsilon}\right)^{2V_{\mathcal{F}_0^+}} \quad (\text{B.11})$$

is an almost surely valid bound on the covering number of \mathcal{G} w.r.t. the L_1 norm. \square

Lemma B.2.1 and Theorem B.6.4 are our main tools to prove Lemma B.2.2, which is a simplified version of Theorem 4.4.1.

Lemma B.2.2. *Consider the constructed confidence regions in \mathcal{F}_0 , that is, let*

$$\mathcal{F}_n^{(1)} \doteq \left\{ f_\theta \in \mathcal{F}_0 \mid \theta \in \Theta_n^{(1)} \right\}. \quad (\text{B.12})$$

Assume B1, B2, B3, B4 and B6, then for all $\varepsilon > 0$

$$\mathbb{P} \left(\bigcup_{k=1}^{\infty} \bigcap_{n=k}^{\infty} \left\{ \mathcal{F}_n^{(1)} \subseteq B(f^*, \varepsilon) \right\} \right) = 1, \quad (\text{B.13})$$

where $B(f^*, \varepsilon) \doteq \{f \in \mathcal{F}_0 \mid \|f - f^*\|_Q < \varepsilon\}$.

Proof. We are going to show that $Z_n^{(0)}(\theta)$ tends to be the greatest in the ordering, defined by \prec_π , uniformly for all $\theta \notin B(f^*, \varepsilon)$ as $n \rightarrow \infty$. For $j \in [m-1]$ the difference between the reference variables can be bounded from below as follows

$$\begin{aligned}
Z_n^{(0)}(\theta) - Z_n^{(j)}(\theta) &= \frac{1}{n} \sum_{i=1}^n (f_\theta(X_i) - f_{\theta,n}^{(0)}(X_i))^2 - \frac{1}{n} \sum_{i=1}^n (f_\theta(X_i) - f_{\theta,n}^{(j)}(X_i))^2 \\
&= \frac{1}{n} \sum_{i=1}^n (f_\theta(X_i) - f_*(X_i))^2 + \frac{1}{n} \sum_{i=1}^n (f^*(X_i) - f_{*,n}^{(0)}(X_i))^2 \\
&\quad + \frac{2}{n} \sum_{i=1}^n (f_\theta(X_i) - f_*(X_i))(f^*(X_i) - f_{*,n}^{(0)}(X_i)) - \frac{1}{n} \sum_{i=1}^n (f_\theta(X_i) - f_{\theta,n}^{(j)}(X_i))^2 \\
&\geq \mathbb{E}[(f_\theta(X) - f^*(X))^2] - \mathbb{E}[(f_\theta(X) - f^*(X))^2] \\
&\quad + \frac{1}{n} \sum_{i=1}^n (f_\theta(X_i) - f_*(X_i))^2 + \mathbb{E}[(f^*(X) - f_{*,n}^{(0)}(X))^2] \\
&\quad - \mathbb{E}[(f^*(X) - f_{*,n}^{(0)}(X))^2] + \frac{1}{n} \sum_{i=1}^n (f^*(X_i) - f_{*,n}^{(0)}(X_i))^2 \\
&\quad - \mathbb{E}[(f_\theta(X) - f_{\theta,n}^{(j)}(X))^2] + \mathbb{E}[(f_\theta(X) - f_{\theta,n}^{(j)}(X))^2] \\
&\quad - \frac{1}{n} \sum_{i=1}^n (f_\theta(X_i) - f_{\theta,n}^{(j)}(X_i))^2 - \frac{4}{n} \sum_{i=1}^n |f^*(X_i) - f_{*,n}^{(0)}(X_i)|,
\end{aligned} \tag{B.14}$$

where X is independent of \mathcal{D}_0^π and $\mathcal{D}_j^\pi(\theta)$ and the expectation is w.r.t. variables X, \mathcal{D}_0 and $\mathcal{D}_j^\pi(\theta)$. We want to bound the infimum of the left hand side for $f_\theta \in \mathcal{F}_0 \setminus B(f^*, \varepsilon)$ from below. First, notice that

$$\inf_{f_\theta \notin B(f^*, \varepsilon)} \mathbb{E}[(f_\theta(X) - f^*(X))^2] \geq \varepsilon^2. \tag{B.15}$$

Further, for the expectations of the L_2 errors we have

$$\begin{aligned}
\mathbb{E}[(f^*(X) - f_{*,n}^{(0)}(X))^2] &\geq 0, \\
\mathbb{E}[(f_\theta(X) - f_{\theta,n}^{(j)}(X))^2] &\leq \frac{c_1 + (c_2 + c_3 \log(n))V_{\mathcal{F}_0^+}}{n} \doteq a_n,
\end{aligned} \tag{B.16}$$

where we used Theorem B.6.3 from Appendix B.6 (Györfi et al., 2002, Theorem 11.5) with the observation that

$$\inf_{f \in \mathcal{F}_0} \int |f(x) - f^*(x)|^2 dQ_X(x) = 0 \tag{B.17}$$

follows from $f^* \in \mathcal{F}_0$. Additionally, Theorem B.6.3 can be applied directly without the truncation, because $|Y| \leq 1$ and $\sup_{x \in \mathbb{R}^d} |f(x)| \leq 1$ for all $f \in \mathcal{F}_0$.

The deviations from the expected values are bounded with a supremum over \mathcal{F}_0 as

$$\begin{aligned}
& \mathbb{E}[(f_\theta(X) - f^*(X))^2] - \frac{1}{n} \sum_{i=1}^n (f_\theta(X_i) - f_*(X_i))^2 \\
& + \mathbb{E}[(f^*(X) - f_{*,n}^{(0)}(X))^2] - \frac{1}{n} \sum_{i=1}^n (f^*(X_i) - f_{*,n}^{(0)}(X_i))^2 \\
& - \mathbb{E}[(f_\theta(X) - f_{\theta,n}^{(j)}(X))^2] + \frac{1}{n} \sum_{i=1}^n (f_\theta(X_i) - f_{\theta,n}^{(j)}(X_i))^2 \\
& \leq 3 \sup_{f,g \in \mathcal{F}_0} \left| \frac{1}{n} \sum_{i=1}^n (f(X_i) - g(X_i))^2 - \mathbb{E}[(f(X) - g(X))^2] \right| \\
& = 3 \sup_{h \in \mathcal{G}} \left| \frac{1}{n} \sum_{i=1}^n h(X_i) - \mathbb{E}[h(X)] \right|,
\end{aligned}$$

where \mathcal{G} is defined in (B.2). The inequality holds because f_θ , f^* and the estimates are all included in \mathcal{F}_0 . For the last term in (B.14) we apply the Cauchy–Schwartz inequality, then we bound the obtained value with the same supremum as in (B.18) plus the zero sequence a_n , defined in (B.16), as

$$\begin{aligned}
& \left(\frac{1}{n} \sum_{i=1}^n \left| f^*(X_i) - f_{*,n}^{(0)}(X_i) \right| \right)^2 \leq \frac{1}{n^2} \sum_{i=1}^n (f^*(X_i) - f_{*,n}^{(0)}(X_i))^2 \sum_{i=1}^n 1 \\
& \leq \frac{1}{n} \sum_{i=1}^n (f^*(X_i) - f_{*,n}^{(0)}(X_i))^2 - \mathbb{E}[(f^*(X) - f_{*,n}^{(0)}(X))^2] + \mathbb{E}[(f^*(X) - f_{*,n}^{(0)}(X))^2] \\
& \leq \sup_{f,g \in \mathcal{F}_0} \left| \frac{1}{n} \sum_{i=1}^n (f(X_i) - g(X_i))^2 - \mathbb{E}[(f(X) - g(X))^2] \right| + a_n \tag{B.18}
\end{aligned}$$

$$= \sup_{h \in \mathcal{G}} \left| \frac{1}{n} \sum_{i=1}^n h(X_i) - \mathbb{E}[h(X)] \right| + a_n. \tag{B.19}$$

For the sake of simplicity let

$$A_n \doteq \sup_{h \in \mathcal{G}} \left| \frac{1}{n} \sum_{i=1}^n h(X_i) - \mathbb{E}[h(X)] \right|. \tag{B.20}$$

To sum up, we can bound the infimum of (B.14) from below as

$$\inf_{f_\theta \notin B(f^*, \varepsilon)} (Z_n^{(0)}(\theta) - Z_n^{(j)}(\theta)) \geq \varepsilon^2 - a_n - 3A_n - 4\sqrt{A_n + a_n}. \tag{B.21}$$

Observe that $(a_n)_{n \in \mathbb{N}^+}$ is a deterministic sequence and tends to zero as $n \rightarrow \infty$. If $(A_n)_{n \in \mathbb{N}^+}$ converges to zero almost surely, then for all $j \in [m-1]$ a.s. there exists $n_j \in \mathbb{N}$ such that for all $n > n_j$ difference $Z_n^{(0)}(\theta) - Z_n^{(j)}(\theta)$ becomes positive for all $f_\theta \notin B(f^*, \varepsilon)$, and by the construction for all $n > \max_{j \in [m-1]} n_j$ we have $\mathcal{F}_{\varrho,n}^{(1)} \subseteq B(f^*, \varepsilon)$.

It remained to prove that $A_n \xrightarrow{a.s.} 0$. We use a uniform law of large numbers. By

Lemma B.2.1 the assumption of Theorem B.6.4 is satisfied, i.e., for all $\varepsilon > 0$ we have

$$\sum_{n=1}^{\infty} \mathbb{E} \left(\mathcal{N}_1(\varepsilon/8, \mathcal{G}, \{X_1, \dots, X_n\}) \right) e^{-n\varepsilon^2/(128B^2)} \leq C(\varepsilon, V_{\mathcal{F}_0^+}) \cdot \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} e^{-n\varepsilon^2/(128B^2)} < \infty, \quad (\text{B.22})$$

where $C(\varepsilon, V_{\mathcal{F}_0^+})$ is defined in the proof of Lemma B.2.1, $B = 4$, because $(f(x) - g(x))^2 \in [0, 4]$ for all $x \in \mathbb{X}$ and $f, g \in \mathcal{F}_0$. Consequently $A_n \xrightarrow{a.s.} 0$ holds. \square

Lemma B.2.3 formalizes the final step of proving Theorem 4.4.1.

Lemma B.2.3. *Assume B3, B5 and that (B.13) holds for all $\varepsilon' > 0$, then for all $\varepsilon > 0$:*

$$\mathbb{P} \left(\bigcup_{k=1}^{\infty} \bigcap_{n=k}^{\infty} \{ \Theta_n^{(1)} \subseteq B(\theta^*, \varepsilon) \} \right) = 1. \quad (\text{B.23})$$

Proof. If $f_{\theta} \in B(f^*, \varepsilon/L)$, then $\theta \in B(\theta_*, \varepsilon)$, because of B5. Hence, it follows that

$$\{ \Theta_{\rho, n}^{(1)} \subseteq B(\theta_*, \varepsilon) \} \supseteq \{ \mathcal{F}_{\rho, n}^{(1)} \subseteq B(f^*, \varepsilon/L) \}. \quad (\text{B.24})$$

The inclusion also holds for the lim inf of events. Finally, since (B.13) holds for ε/L by (B.24) we also have (B.23). \square

Theorem 4.4.1. *Assume B1-B6, then for all sample size $n \in \mathbb{N}^+$ and integers $1 \leq q \leq m$*

$$\mathbb{P} \left(\theta^* \in \Theta_n^{(1)} \right) = \frac{q}{m}, \quad (\text{B.25})$$

In addition, if $q < m$, then $(\Theta_n^{(1)})_{n \in \mathbb{N}^+}$ is strongly uniformly consistent.

Proof. Observe that the statement regarding the exact coverage probability follows from Theorem 4.3.1, because P1 and P2 are satisfied by the ERM-based ranking.

Under B6 we have (B.4), hence Lemma B.2.2 proves that the confidence regions are uniformly consistent in the model space. By Lemma B.2.3 in this case condition B5 is sufficient for uniform consistency in the parameter space. \square

Theorem 4.4.2. *Assume B1-B6 and $1 \leq q < m$. For all $\varepsilon > 0$ there exists N_0 such that for $n \geq N_0$ we have*

$$\mathbb{P} \left(\Theta_n^{(1)} \subseteq B(\theta^*, \varepsilon) \right) \geq 1 - C_1 e^{-n\lambda_1}, \quad (\text{B.26})$$

where C_1 depends only on ε and $V_{\mathcal{F}_0^+}$, and λ_1 depends only on ε and the Lipschitz constant.

Proof. Similarly as in the proof of Theorem 4.4.1 observe that

$$\{ \Theta_{\rho, n}^{(1)} \subseteq B(\theta_*, \varepsilon) \} \supseteq \{ \forall j \in [m-1] : \inf_{\theta \notin B(\theta_*, \varepsilon)} (Z_n^{(0)}(\theta) - Z_n^{(j)}(\theta)) > 0 \}. \quad (\text{B.27})$$

By Lemma B.2.3 and (B.21), we obtain for all $j \in [m - 1]$ that

$$\begin{aligned} \inf_{\theta \notin B(\theta_*, \varepsilon)} \left(Z_n^{(0)}(\theta) - Z_n^{(j)}(\theta) \right) &\geq \inf_{f_\theta \notin B(f^*, \varepsilon/L)} \left(Z_n^{(0)}(\theta) - Z_n^{(j)}(\theta) \right) \\ &\geq \frac{\varepsilon^2}{L^2} - a_n - 3A_n - 4\sqrt{A_n + a_n}, \end{aligned} \quad (\text{B.28})$$

where L is the Lipschitz constant, (a_n) is a deterministic zero sequence defined in (B.16) and A_n is the (measurable) supremum of the deviations defined in (B.20). Notice that the lower bound does not depend on index j , consequently by elementary manipulations

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbb{P}\left(\Theta_{\varrho, n}^{(1)} \subseteq B(\theta_*, \varepsilon)\right) &\geq \mathbb{P}\left(\forall j \in [m - 1] : \inf_{\theta \notin B(\theta_*, \varepsilon)} \left(Z_n^{(0)}(\theta) - Z_n^{(j)}(\theta) \right) > 0\right) \\ &\geq \mathbb{P}\left(\forall j \in [m - 1] : \inf_{f_\theta \notin B(f^*, \varepsilon/L)} \left(Z_n^{(0)}(\theta) - Z_n^{(j)}(\theta) \right) > 0\right) \\ &\geq \mathbb{P}\left(\frac{\varepsilon^2}{2L^2} > a_n + 3A_n + 4\sqrt{A_n + a_n}\right) \\ &\geq \mathbb{P}\left(\frac{\varepsilon^2}{6L^2} > a_n, \frac{\varepsilon^2}{6L^2} \geq 3A_n, \frac{\varepsilon^2}{6L^2} \geq 4\sqrt{A_n + a_n}\right) \\ &= \mathbb{P}\left(\frac{\varepsilon^2}{6L^2} > a_n, \frac{\varepsilon^2}{18L^2} \geq A_n, \frac{\varepsilon^4}{24^2L^4} \geq A_n + a_n\right) \\ &\geq \mathbb{P}\left(\min\left(\frac{\varepsilon^2}{6L^2}, \frac{\varepsilon^4}{2 \cdot 24^2L^4}\right) > a_n, \min\left(\frac{\varepsilon^2}{18L^2}, \frac{\varepsilon^4}{2 \cdot 24^2L^4}\right) \geq A_n\right). \end{aligned} \quad (\text{B.29})$$

Since (a_n) is deterministic and tends to zero there exists n_0 such that for all $n > n_0$:

$$\min\left(\frac{\varepsilon^2}{6L^2}, \frac{\varepsilon^4}{2 \cdot 24^2L^4}\right) > a_n \quad (\text{B.30})$$

holds. Furthermore let

$$\tau \doteq \min\left(\frac{\varepsilon^2}{18L^2}, \frac{\varepsilon^4}{2 \cdot 24^2L^4}\right) \quad (\text{B.31})$$

Then, by Theorem B.6.4 and Lemma B.2.1 for $n > n_0$ we have

$$\mathbb{P}(A_n \leq \tau) = 1 - \mathbb{P}(A_n > \tau) \geq 1 - 8C \exp\left(-\frac{n\tau^2}{128B^2}\right), \quad (\text{B.32})$$

where $B = 4$. Thus, with constants $C_1 \doteq 8C$ and $\lambda_1 \doteq \frac{\tau^2}{128B^2}$ Theorem 4.4.2 follows. \square

We can quantify the data size which is required for the PAC bound to hold. We can show that (B.30), which is the only condition that needs to be satisfied, holds if

$$n > N_0 \doteq \left(\frac{c_1 + (c_2 + c_3)V_{\mathcal{F}_0^+}}{\varepsilon'}\right)^2, \quad \text{where } \varepsilon' \doteq \min\left(\frac{\varepsilon^2}{6L^2}, \frac{\varepsilon^4}{2 \cdot 24^2L^4}\right) \quad (\text{B.33})$$

and constants c_1 , c_2 and c_3 are defined in (Györfi et al., 2002, Theorem 11.5).

B.3 Model Classes with Finite Pseudo-Dimension

The ERM-based method can be applied on a wide variety of model classes. In the dissertation we considered the perceptron, as a demonstrative example. In this section several model classes are presented where the ERM-based method constructs uniformly consistent abstract confidence regions for the true regression function.

B.3.1 Linear Models

Let \mathcal{F}_0 be a subset of a k dimensional vector space, $\tilde{\mathcal{F}}$, spanned by an orthonormal basis $\varphi_1, \dots, \varphi_k$ of $\mathbb{X} \rightarrow [-1, 1]$ type functions, i.e.,

$$f_{\theta}(x) = \sum_{i=1}^k \theta_i \varphi_i(x), \quad (\text{B.34})$$

for some $\theta \in \mathbb{R}^k$, thus $\Theta \subseteq \mathbb{R}^k$. The range of the regression function is bounded in $[-1, 1]$, therefore we consider the supremum ball with radius 1 in linear space $\tilde{\mathcal{F}}$. It is known that $V_{\tilde{\mathcal{F}}^+} \leq k + 1$, cf. (Györfi et al., 2002, Theorem 9.5), hence B6 holds. The inverse Lipschitz condition is verified for the parameterization by Lemma B.3.1, therefore in this framework our method builds exact, strongly uniformly consistent confidence regions for the true regression function.

We note that there is no explicit formula for the optimal solution of the empirical risk minimization problem over \mathcal{F}_0 when it is not the entire linear space $\tilde{\mathcal{F}}$, in which case the LS estimator provides analytical solution under mild conditions. The range of the LS estimator might include elements that are not in the desired $[-1, 1]$ interval. This problem can be resolved in several ways. Obviously, we can truncate the LS estimator into the $[-1, 1]$ interval. The advantage of this approach is that generalizing the theory to these variants of our method is fairly easy, because truncation does not increase the VC dimension of a model class. On the other hand one can argue that our estimator should be included in the given model class. Therefore, another useful approach is to restrict the parameters to enforce the boundedness of the linear combination within $[-1, 1]$, e.g., we can require the estimator to be a convex combination of the basis functions.

Lemma B.3.1. *Let \mathcal{F}_0 be a finite dimensional linear subspace of $\mathcal{L}_2(Q_x)$ spanned by an orthonormal system of vectors $\{\varphi_1, \dots, \varphi_k\}$. Then, linear parameterization is an isometry, i.e., for all $\alpha, \beta \in \mathbb{R}^k$ we have*

$$\|\alpha - \beta\|_2 = \left\| \sum_{i=1}^k \alpha_i \varphi_i(x) - \sum_{i=1}^k \beta_i \varphi_i(x) \right\|_Q, \quad (\text{B.35})$$

henceforth it is also inverse Lipschitz continuous.

Proof. The orthonormality of $\varphi_1, \dots, \varphi_k$ implies (B.35). □

B.3.2 Radial Basis Function Networks

In the second example we examine the model class of radial basis function networks of [Lowe and Broomhead \(1988\)](#) with one hidden layer on $\mathbb{X} \subseteq \mathbb{R}^d$.

Let $K : \mathbb{R}_+ \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$ be a local averaging kernel function. Popular choices include the naïve kernel $K(z) \doteq \mathbb{I}(z \in [0, 1))$ and the Gaussian kernel $K(z) \doteq e^{-z^2}$. We consider regular kernels, which are nonnegative, monotonically decreasing, left continuous and satisfy

$$\int_{\mathbb{R}^d} K(\|x\|)dx \neq 0 \quad \text{and} \quad \int_{\mathbb{R}^d} K(\|x\|)dx < \infty \quad (\text{B.36})$$

with the Euclidean norm $\|\cdot\|$. It is easy to prove that regular kernels are bounded ([Krzyzak and Linder, 1997](#); [Lei et al., 2014](#)). Let $K(z) \leq K_*$ for all $z \in \mathbb{R}^+$ and k be the number of computational units and let us consider model class

$$\mathcal{F}_0 \doteq \left\{ \sum_{i=1}^k w_i K(\|x - c_i\|_{A_i}) + w_0 \mid \right. \\ \left. w_1, \dots, w_n \in \mathbb{R}, c_1, \dots, c_k \in \mathbb{R}^d, A_1, \dots, A_k \in \mathbb{R}^{d \times d}, \sum_{i=1}^k |w_i| < B \right\}, \quad (\text{B.37})$$

where $\|x - c_i\|_{A_i} \doteq (x - c_i)^T A_i (x - c_i)$. Restriction $\sum_{i=1}^k |w_i| < B$ is made both to control the boundedness of the models and the complexity or capacity of the model class.

The verification of the inverse Lipschitz property is challenging and depends on the specific choice of the kernel, but the uniform convergence in $L_2(Q_X)$ can be guaranteed by bounding the complexity measure. We refer to the result of [Györfi et al. \(2002, Lemma 17.2\)](#), which bounds the random L_1 -cover of \mathcal{F}_0 independently from the sample as

$$\mathcal{N}_1(\varepsilon/8, \mathcal{F}_0, \{x_1, \dots, x_n\}) \leq 3^k \left(\frac{96eB(k+1)}{\varepsilon} \right)^{(2d^2+2d+3)k+1} \doteq R. \quad (\text{B.38})$$

Combining this inequality with

$$\mathcal{N}_1(\varepsilon, \mathcal{H}, \{x_1, \dots, x_n\}) \leq \left(\mathcal{N}_1(\varepsilon/8, \mathcal{F}_0, \{x_1, \dots, x_n\}) \right)^2, \quad (\text{B.39})$$

which is proved in Appendix B.2, yields that

$$\mathcal{N}_1(\varepsilon, \mathcal{H}, \{X_1, \dots, X_n\}) \leq R^2. \quad (\text{B.40})$$

This is sufficient for the uniform consistency in $L_2(Q_X)$.

The training of radial basis function networks suffers from high computational burden and effective methods for finding the global optimum are only known in special cases. Nevertheless, in practice stochastic gradient type approaches are widely used and provide estimates with good performance. These estimates can also be used as $\{f_{\theta,n}^{(j)}\}$ functions to define a ranking, and the exact coverage of the constructed region is guaranteed.

B.3.3 Neural Networks

Deep neural networks are a generalizations of the single neuron model and are widely used in many different areas including industry, economics and health care. We consider a class of feed-forward models, however, we emphasize that our method works for any fixed class of neural networks with finite pseudo-dimension. Let \mathcal{F}_0 be a class of feed-forward neural networks with a layer structure containing W parameters (weights and biased terms together), M layers and k computation units. Either the sigmoid function

$$\sigma_S(x) \doteq \frac{1}{1 + e^{-x}}, \quad (\text{B.41})$$

or the recently favored rectified linear unit (ReLU)

$$\sigma_R(x) \doteq x \cdot \mathbb{I}(x \geq 0), \quad (\text{B.42})$$

can be used as activation in each computation node.

By (Anthony and Bartlett, 2009, Theorem 14.2) for neural networks with sigmoid activation functions we have

$$V_{\mathcal{F}_0^+} \leq ((W + 2)k)^2 + 11(W + 2)k \log_2(18(W + 2)k^2). \quad (\text{B.43})$$

Similar for the ReLU activation it is proved by Bartlett et al. (2019, Theorem 7) that under general conditions the pseudo-dimension is $O(WM \log(W))$, therefore uniform convergence in $L_2(Q_X)$ is a corollary of Lemma B.2.2. For a particular example when $\mathbb{X} \subseteq \mathbb{R}^d$ we consider a network with one hidden layer, i.e., let the model class be

$$\mathcal{F}_0 \doteq \left\{ \sum_{i=1}^k c_i \sigma_S(a_i^\top x + b_i) + c_0 \mid \sum_{i=1}^k |c_i| \leq B, c_0, \dots, c_k, b_1, \dots, b_k \in \mathbb{R}, a_1, \dots, a_k \in \mathbb{R}^d \right\}, \quad (\text{B.44})$$

where condition $\sum_{i=1}^k |c_i| \leq B$ ensures the boundedness of the models. In this particular case the number of parameters is $W = (k + 1) + k + kd$, and because of (B.43), the pseudo-dimension of \mathcal{F}_0 is finite.

The training of artificial neural networks faces several computational and theoretical challenges, because in general it requires solving highly non-convex optimization problems. Nevertheless, approximate solutions (e.g., which are close to a local optimum) can be found by stochastic gradient descent type algorithms (cf. backpropagation). These solutions provide feasible estimates with decent performances, which can also be used in our UQ framework as $\{f_{\theta,n}^{(j)}\}$ functions to define the ranking, leading to exact coverage guarantees.

B.4 Confidence Ellipsoids for Logistic Regression

In the numerical experiments we compare the novel resampling methods to asymptotic confidence ellipsoids around the MLE. We consider a parametric class of models used by

logistic regression, which is a standard nonlinear technique to estimate the regression function of binary classification. In this approach the binary output values are usually denoted by 0 and 1. As above, let the i.i.d. sample be denoted by $\mathcal{D}_0 = \{(X_i, Y_i)\}_{i=1}^n$ and $X_i \in \mathbb{R}^d$ for each $i = 1, \dots, n$. Let $\theta \doteq (\beta, a)$ for some $\beta \in \mathbb{R}^d$ and $a \in \mathbb{R}$. Logistic regression models the conditional probabilities of a chosen class with a logistic function by maximizing the conditional likelihood, or equivalently the joint log-likelihood function

$$L(\theta) = L(\beta, a) \doteq \log \left(\prod_{i=1}^n p_i(\beta, a)^{Y_i} (1 - p_i(\beta, a))^{1 - Y_i} \right), \quad (\text{B.45})$$

where

$$p_i(\beta, a) \doteq \mathbb{P}(Y_i = 1 \mid X_i) = \frac{1}{1 + e^{-(X_i^T \beta + a)}}, \quad (\text{B.46})$$

for $\beta \in \mathbb{R}^d$ and $a \in \mathbb{R}$. Let the MLE be

$$\hat{\theta}_n \doteq (\hat{\beta}, \hat{a}) \in \arg \max L(\beta, a). \quad (\text{B.47})$$

By the central limit theorem it is proved that under some regularity conditions, the limit distribution of the MLE is normal, ([Lehmann and Casella, 1983](#)), i.e.,

$$\sqrt{n} (\hat{\theta}_n - \theta^*) \xrightarrow{d} \mathcal{N}_{d+1}(0, I(\theta^*)^{-1}), \quad (\text{B.48})$$

where $I(\theta^*)$ denotes the Fisher-information matrix. Because of the continuity of the Fisher-information an asymptotic confidence region, in fact an ellipsoid, for θ^* with significance level δ can be constructed by

$$\hat{\Theta}_n \doteq \left\{ \theta \in \mathbb{R}^{d+1} \mid (\theta - \hat{\theta}_n) I(\hat{\theta}_n) (\theta - \hat{\theta}_n) \leq c/n \right\}, \quad (\text{B.49})$$

where c is the $(1 - \delta)$ -quantile of the $\chi^2(d + 1)$ distribution. Under some mild regularity conditions, the Fisher-information matrix can be computed as $I(\theta) = -\mathbb{E}_\theta[\partial^2 l_i(\theta)]$, where $l_i(\theta) \doteq \log(p_i(\theta)^{Y_i} (1 - p_i(\theta))^{1 - Y_i})$ denotes the log-likelihood function of a single sample point for $i \in [n]$ and ∂^2 is the second derivative or Hessian matrix with respect to θ . By

$$L(\theta) = \sum_{i=1}^n l_i(\theta), \quad (\text{B.50})$$

the Fisher-information can be approximated by

$$I(\theta^*) \approx \frac{\partial^2 L(\hat{\theta}_n)}{n} \quad (\text{B.51})$$

and an approximate confidence ellipsoid can be constructed by

$$\hat{\Theta}_n \doteq \left\{ \theta \in \mathbb{R}^{d+1} \mid (\theta - \hat{\theta}_n) \partial^2 L(\hat{\theta}_n) (\theta - \hat{\theta}_n) \leq c \right\}. \quad (\text{B.52})$$

B.5 Proof of Theorem 4.6.1

Theorem 4.6.1. *Assume that B1-B3, B7 and B8 hold, then for all $n \in \mathbb{N}^+$ we have*

$$\mathbb{P}(\theta^* \in \Theta_n^{(3)}) = \frac{q}{m}. \quad (\text{B.53})$$

If B1-B3, B7-B9 and $1 \leq q < m$ hold, then for all $\theta \neq \theta^$ we have*

$$\mathbb{P}\left(\bigcap_{N=1}^{\infty} \bigcup_{n=N}^{\infty} \{\theta \in \Theta_n^{(3)}\}\right) = 0. \quad (\text{B.54})$$

Proof. The exact coverage follows from Lemma 3.2.1. If the alternative hypothesis holds true, i.e., $\theta \neq \theta^*$, let $S_n^{(j)}(\theta) = \sqrt{Z_j^{(1)}(\theta)}$ for $j = 0, \dots, m-1$. It is sufficient to show that $S_n^{(0)}(\theta)$ tends to be the greatest in the ordering as $n \rightarrow \infty$, because the square root function is order-preserving. For $j = 0$ by the reverse triangle inequality we have

$$\begin{aligned} S_n^{(0)}(\theta) &= \sqrt{\frac{1}{n} \sum_{i=1}^n \|\mu_\theta(X_i) - \hat{\mu}_0^{(1)}(X_i)\|_{\mathcal{G}}^2} \\ &\geq \sqrt{\frac{1}{n} \sum_{i=1}^n \|\mu_\theta(X_i) - \mu^*(X_i)\|_{\mathcal{G}}^2} - \sqrt{\frac{1}{n} \sum_{i=1}^n \|\mu^*(X_i) - \hat{\mu}_0^{(1)}(X_i)\|_{\mathcal{G}}^2}. \end{aligned} \quad (\text{B.55})$$

The first term converges to a positive number, as

$$\begin{aligned} &\frac{1}{n} \sum_{i=1}^n \|\mu_\theta(X_i) - \mu^*(X_i)\|_{\mathcal{G}}^2 \\ &= \frac{1}{n} \sum_{i=1}^n \|(\eta_\theta(X_i) - \eta^*(X_i))\ell(\cdot, 1) + (\eta^*(X_i) - \eta_\theta(X_i))\ell(\cdot, -1)\|_{\mathcal{G}}^2 \\ &= \frac{1}{n} \sum_{i=1}^n \left[(\eta_\theta(X_i) - \eta^*(X_i))^2 \ell(1, 1) + (\eta^*(X_i) - \eta_\theta(X_i))^2 \ell(-1, -1) \right] \\ &= \frac{2}{n} \sum_{i=1}^n \left[(\eta_\theta(X_i) - \eta^*(X_i))^2 \right] \rightarrow 2 \mathbb{E} \left[(\eta_\theta(X) - \eta^*(X))^2 \right], \end{aligned} \quad (\text{B.56})$$

where we used the SLLN and that $\ell(1, -1) = \ell(-1, 1) = 0$. For $f_\theta \neq f_*$ we have that $\kappa \doteq \mathbb{E}[(f_\theta(X) - f^*(X))^2] > 0$. The second term almost surely converges to zero by B9, hence we can conclude that $S_n^{(0)}(\theta) \xrightarrow{a.s.} \sqrt{2\kappa}$.

For $j \in [m-1]$ variable $Z_j^{(1)}(\theta)$ has a similar form as the second term in (B.55), thus its (a.s.) convergence to 0 follows from B9, i.e., we get $Z_j^{(1)}(\theta) \xrightarrow{a.s.} 0$ for all $\theta \in \Theta$. Hence, $Z_0^{(1)}(\theta)$ (a.s.) tends to become the greatest, implying (B.54) for $q < m$. \square

B.6 Fundamental Results Used in the Proofs

The celebrated VC dimension, which is used to define the notion of pseudo-dimension, is one of the most widely applied complexity measure in statistical learning theory. Let \mathcal{A} be a class of subsets of \mathbb{R}^d , then \mathcal{A} shatters a set $C \subseteq \mathbb{R}^d$ if for all possible subsets $C_0 \subseteq C$, there exists $A \in \mathcal{A}$ such that $A \cap C = C_0$.

Definition B.6.1 (VC dimension). *The VC dimension of \mathcal{A} , denoted by $V_{\mathcal{A}}$, is the largest number $n \in \mathbb{N}$ such that there exists a set $\{z_1, \dots, z_n\}$ of vectors in \mathbb{R}^d which is shattered by \mathcal{A} ; $V_{\mathcal{A}} \doteq \infty$ if the maximum cardinality does not exist.*

In the proof of Lemma B.2.1 we used Lemma B.6.1 and Theorem B.6.2. The lemma that follows establishes a close relationship between packing and covering numbers, see (Györfi et al., 2002, Lemma 9.2).

Lemma B.6.1. *Let \mathcal{F} be a class of functions on \mathbb{R}^d , Q_x be a probability measure on \mathbb{R}^d and $\|\cdot\| \doteq \|\cdot\|_{L_1(Q_x)}$ be the L_1 norm on \mathcal{F} . Then for all $\varepsilon > 0$:*

$$\mathcal{N}(\varepsilon, \mathcal{F}, \|\cdot\|) \leq \mathcal{M}(\varepsilon, \mathcal{F}, \|\cdot\|). \quad (\text{B.57})$$

The following theorem provides an upper bound on the packing number of \mathcal{F} w.r.t. an L_1 norm based on its VC dimension (Haussler, 1995, Corollary 3).

Theorem B.6.2. *For any set \mathbb{X} , probability distribution Q_x on \mathbb{X} , set \mathcal{F} of Q_x -measurable functions on \mathbb{X} taking values in the interval $[0, 1]$ with $V_{\mathcal{F}^+} < \infty$, and $\varepsilon > 0$*

$$\mathcal{M}\left(\varepsilon, \mathcal{F}, \|\cdot\|_{L_1(Q_x)}\right) \leq e(V_{\mathcal{F}^+} + 1) \left(\frac{2e}{\varepsilon}\right)^{V_{\mathcal{F}^+}}. \quad (\text{B.58})$$

The proof of Lemma B.2.2 applies the result of Györfi et al. (2002, Theorem 11.5).

Theorem B.6.3. *Assume that there exists $1 \leq M < \infty$ such that $|Y| \leq M$ a.s. Let f_n denote the truncated empirical risk minimizer to $[-M, M]$ over a set of functions \mathcal{F} , then*

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbb{E}\left[\int |f_n(x) - f^*(x)|^2 dQ_x(x)\right] &\leq \frac{c_1}{n} + \frac{(c_2 + c_3 \log(n))V_{\mathcal{F}^+}}{n} \\ &\quad + 2 \inf_{f \in \mathcal{F}} \int |f(x) - f^*(x)|^2 dQ_x(x), \end{aligned} \quad (\text{B.59})$$

where $c_1 = 24 \cdot 214M^4(1 + \log(42))$, $c_2 = 48 \cdot 214M^4 \log(480eM^2)$ and $c_3 = 48 \cdot 214M^4$.

In the proof of Theorem 4.4.1 we used the ULLN that follows, which is an advanced version of (Györfi et al., 2002, Theorem 9.1):

Theorem B.6.4. *Let X, X_1, \dots, X_n be i.i.d. random vectors taking values in \mathbb{R}^d and \mathcal{H} be a class of $\mathbb{R}^d \rightarrow [0, B]$ type functions. For any $n \in \mathbb{N}^+$, and any $\varepsilon > 0$*

$$\mathbb{P}\left(\sup_{h \in \mathcal{H}} \left| \frac{1}{n} \sum_{i=1}^n h(X_i) - \mathbb{E}[h(X)] \right| > \varepsilon\right) \leq 8\mathbb{E}\left[\mathcal{N}_1(\varepsilon/8, \mathcal{H}, \{X_1, \dots, X_n\})\right] e^{-n\varepsilon^2/(128B^2)}.$$
(B.60)

In addition, if for all $\varepsilon > 0$ we have

$$\sum_{n=1}^{\infty} \mathbb{E}\left[\mathcal{N}_1(\varepsilon/8, \mathcal{H}, \{X_1, \dots, X_n\})\right] e^{-n\varepsilon^2/(128B^2)} < \infty,$$
(B.61)

then the ULLN holds, that is,

$$\sup_{h \in \mathcal{H}} \left| \frac{1}{n} \sum_{i=1}^n h(X_i) - \mathbb{E}[h(X)] \right| \xrightarrow{a.s.} 0.$$
(B.62)

Appendix C

In Appendix C we present an introductory material for probability theory in Banach spaces based on the seminal works of [Pisier \(2016\)](#); [Hytönen et al. \(2016\)](#). First, Bochner integrals and Bochner spaces, which are the vector-valued generalizations of L_p spaces, are defined. Then, the notion of conditional expectation in Banach spaces is reviewed.

C.1 The Bochner Integral

The Bochner integral extends the concept of integration to functions taking values in a Banach space. Let $(\mathcal{G}, \|\cdot\|_{\mathcal{G}})$ be a Banach space with the Borel σ -field of \mathcal{G} and $(\Omega, \mathcal{A}, \mathbb{P})$ be a measure space with a finite measure \mathbb{P} . Similarly to the Lebesgue integral, the Bochner integral is first introduced for simple $\Omega \rightarrow \mathcal{G}$ type functions of the form $f(\omega) = \sum_{j=1}^n \mathbb{I}(\omega \in A_j) g_j$, where $A_j \in \mathcal{A}$ and $g_j \in \mathcal{G}$ for all $j \in [n]$, by

$$\int_{\Omega} f \, d\mathbb{P} \doteq \sum_{j=1}^n \mathbb{P}(A_j) g_j. \quad (\text{C.1})$$

Then, the integral is extended to the abstract completion of these simple functions with respect to the norm defined by the Lebesgue integral that follows:

$$\|f\|_{L_1(\mathbb{P}; \mathcal{G})} \doteq \int_{\Omega} \|f\|_{\mathcal{G}} \, d\mathbb{P}. \quad (\text{C.2})$$

Definition C.1.1. *A function $f : \Omega \rightarrow \mathcal{G}$ is called strongly measurable (Bochner-measurable) if there exists a sequence (f_n) of simple functions converging to f a.e.*

By the theorem of Pettis ([Hytönen et al., 2016](#), Theorem 1.1.20), this is equivalent to requiring the weak measurability of f and that $f(\Omega) \subseteq \mathcal{G}$ is separable.

Definition C.1.2 (Bochner-space). *Let $1 \leq p < \infty$. The vector-valued $\mathcal{L}_p(\Omega, \mathcal{A}, \mathbb{P}; \mathcal{G})$ space is defined as*

$$\mathcal{L}_p(\Omega, \mathcal{A}, \mathbb{P}; \mathcal{G}) \doteq \mathcal{L}(\mathbb{P}; \mathcal{G}) \doteq \left\{ f : \Omega \rightarrow \mathcal{G} \mid f \text{ is strongly measurable and } \int \|f\|_{\mathcal{G}}^p \, d\mathbb{P} < \infty \right\}. \quad (\text{C.3})$$

A semi-norm on $\mathcal{L}_p(\Omega, \mathcal{A}, \mathbb{P}; \mathcal{G})$ is defined by

$$\|f\|_{L_p(\mathbb{P}; \mathcal{G})} \doteq \left(\int \|f\|_{\mathcal{G}}^p d\mathbb{P} \right)^{\frac{1}{p}} \text{ for } f \in \mathcal{L}_p(\Omega, \mathcal{A}, \mathbb{P}; \mathcal{G}). \quad (\text{C.4})$$

Taking equivalence classes on $\mathcal{L}_p(\Omega, \mathcal{A}, \mathbb{P}; \mathcal{G})$ w.r.t. semi-norm $\|\cdot\|_{L_p}$ yields the vector-valued Bochner space denoted by $L_p(\Omega, \mathcal{A}, \mathbb{P}; \mathcal{G})$, simply by $L_p(\Omega, \mathbb{P}; \mathcal{G})$ or $L_p(\mathbb{P}; \mathcal{G})$.

Proposition C.1.1. *Space $(L_p(\Omega, \mathcal{A}, \mathbb{P}; \mathcal{G}), \|\cdot\|_{L_p(\mathbb{P}; \mathcal{G})})$ is a Banach space for $1 \leq p < \infty$.*

Several well-known theorems about Lebesgue integrals can be extended to Bochner integrals, see the books of (Dinculeanu, 2000; Hytönen et al., 2016; Pisier, 2016).

Proposition C.1.2 (Bochner's inequality). *For all $f \in L_1(\Omega, \mathcal{A}, \mathbb{P}; \mathcal{G})$, we have*

$$\left\| \int f d\mathbb{P} \right\|_{\mathcal{G}} \leq \int \|f\|_{\mathcal{G}} d\mathbb{P}. \quad (\text{C.5})$$

A function f is Bochner integrable if and only if the right hand side is finite, however, recall that f is required to be strongly measurable to be included in $L_1(\Omega, \mathcal{A}, \mathbb{P}; \mathcal{G})$. Observe that $\int \|f\|_{\mathcal{G}} d\mathbb{P} = \|f\|_{L_1(\mathbb{P}; \mathcal{G})}$, hence the Bochner integral is a continuous operator from $L_1(\Omega, \mathcal{A}, \mathbb{P}; \mathcal{G})$ to Banach space \mathcal{G} . By definition, the Bochner integral is also linear.

Proposition C.1.3. *Let E and F be Banach spaces and $T : E \rightarrow F$ be a bounded linear operator. Then, for all $f \in L_1(\mathbb{P}; E)$, we have that $T \circ f \in L_1(\mathbb{P}; F)$ and*

$$T\left(\int f d\mathbb{P}\right) = \int T(f) d\mathbb{P}. \quad (\text{C.6})$$

In particular, for a bounded linear functional $x^* : \mathcal{G} \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$, we have

$$\left\langle \int_{\Omega} f(\omega) d\mathbb{P}(\omega), x^* \right\rangle = \int_{\Omega} \langle f(\omega), x^* \rangle d\mathbb{P}(\omega), \quad (\text{C.7})$$

where $\langle g, x^* \rangle \doteq x^*(g)$.

Now, let $(\mathcal{G}, \langle \cdot, \cdot \rangle_{\mathcal{G}})$ be a Hilbert space. By Proposition C.1.3 for all $g \in \mathcal{G}$, we have

$$\left\langle \int_{\Omega} f(\omega) d\mathbb{P}(\omega), g \right\rangle_{\mathcal{G}} = \int_{\Omega} \langle \mu(\omega), g \rangle_{\mathcal{G}} d\mathbb{P}(\omega). \quad (\text{C.8})$$

Moreover, it can be proved that $L_2(\Omega, \mathcal{A}, \mathbb{P}; \mathcal{G})$ is also a Hilbert space with inner product

$$\langle \mu_1, \mu_2 \rangle_{L_2(\Omega, \mathbb{P}; \mathcal{G})} \doteq \int \langle \mu_1(\omega), \mu_2(\omega) \rangle_{\mathcal{G}} d\mathbb{P}(\omega). \quad (\text{C.9})$$

C.2 Conditional Expectation in Banach Spaces

Let \mathbb{P} be a probability measure and \mathcal{B} be a sub- σ -algebra of \mathcal{A} . The conditional expectation with respect to \mathcal{B} is defined for any $f \in L_1(\Omega, \mathcal{A}, \mathbb{P}; \mathcal{G})$ as the \mathbb{P} -a.s. unique element

$\mathbb{E}[f | \mathcal{B}] \doteq \nu \in L_1(\Omega, \mathcal{B}, \mathbb{P}; \mathcal{G})$ satisfying

$$\int_B \nu \, d\mathbb{P} = \int_B f \, d\mathbb{P}, \quad \text{for all } B \in \mathcal{B}. \quad (\text{C.10})$$

It can be shown that the conditional expectation is a (well-defined) bounded operator from $L_1(\Omega, \mathcal{A}, \mathbb{P}; \mathcal{G})$ to $L_1(\Omega, \mathcal{B}, \mathbb{P}; \mathcal{G})$ (Hytönen et al., 2016, Theorem 2.6.23), (Pisier, 2016, Proposition 1.4). The nonexpanding property also holds in the $L_p(\mathbb{P}; \mathcal{G})$ sense for all $1 \leq p < \infty$ (Hytönen et al., 2016, Corollary 2.6.30), that is, for all $f \in L_p(\mathbb{P}; \mathcal{G})$ we have

$$\|\mathbb{E}[f | \mathcal{B}]\|_{\mathcal{G}}^p \leq \mathbb{E}[\|f\|_{\mathcal{G}}^p | \mathcal{B}], \quad (\text{C.11})$$

and by Bochner's inequality $\|\mathbb{E}[f | \mathcal{B}]\|_{L_p(\Omega; \mathcal{G})} \leq \|f\|_{L_p(\Omega; \mathcal{G})}$. Furthermore, by Hytönen et al. (2016, Prop. 2.6.31.) we can take out the \mathcal{B} -measurable term from the conditional expectation. In particular, if \mathcal{G} is a Hilbert space, then for all $g \in \mathcal{G}$ and $f \in L_2(\Omega, \mathcal{A}, \mathbb{P}; \mathcal{G})$ we (a.s.) have that

$$\langle \mathbb{E}[\mu | \mathcal{B}], g \rangle_{\mathcal{G}} = \mathbb{E}[\langle \mu, g \rangle_{\mathcal{G}} | \mathcal{B}]. \quad (\text{C.12})$$

Appendix D

D.1 Supplementary for CKME Estimation

Appendix D contains some supplementary results for the proof of the generalized theorem of Stone. First, the generalized theorem of Stone is proved for continuous conditional kernel mean maps, then it is extended to arbitrary functions in a Bochner space. This extension is based on the denseness result that follows.

Theorem D.1.1. *Let \mathbb{X} be a locally compact Hausdorff space equipped with a Radon measure¹ Q_X and let \mathcal{G} be a separable Hilbert space. The space of compactly supported continuous functions, $\mathcal{C}_c(\mathbb{X}; \mathcal{G})$, is dense in $L_2(\mathbb{X}, Q_X; \mathcal{G})$, that is, for all $\mu \in L_2(\mathbb{X}, Q_X; \mathcal{G})$ and $\varepsilon > 0$, there exists a $\tilde{\mu} \in \mathcal{C}_c(\mathbb{X}; \mathcal{G})$ such that*

$$\int_{\mathbb{X}} \|\mu(x) - \tilde{\mu}(x)\|_{\mathcal{G}}^2 dQ_X(x) < \varepsilon. \quad (\text{D.1})$$

A similar result is proved for \mathbb{R}^d in (Hytönen et al., 2016, Lemma 1.2.31). They mention in a remark that their lemma can be generalized for locally compact spaces, but the complete proof of their claim were not found by us in the literature. Nevertheless, the presented argument has a similar flavor as the ones for scalar-valued L_p spaces.

Proof. First, we prove that we can approximate μ with simple functions in $L_2(\mathbb{X}, Q_X; \mathcal{G})$. Let $\mu \in L_2(\mathbb{X}, Q_X; \mathcal{G})$ and $\varepsilon > 0$. There exists a sequence of simple functions (μ_n) such that $\mu_n \rightarrow \mu$ a.s., i.e., $\mu_n(x) \doteq \sum_{i=1}^{k_n} g_i \mathbb{I}(x \in A_i)$ where $g_i \in \mathcal{G}$ and A_i is measurable with $Q_X(A_i) < \infty$ for all $i \in [k_n]$. Let $B_n \doteq \{x \in \mathbb{X} : \|\mu_n(x)\|_{\mathcal{G}} \leq 2 \|\mu(x)\|_{\mathcal{G}}\}$ and

$$h_n(x) \doteq \mathbb{I}(x \in B_n) \mu_n(x). \quad (\text{D.2})$$

One can see that sequence (B_n) consists of measurable sets and $h_n \rightarrow \mu$ almost everywhere. We show that $h_n \rightarrow \mu$ in $L_2(\mathbb{X}, Q_X; \mathcal{G})$. Because of

$$\|h_n\|_{L_2(\mathbb{X}; \mathcal{G})}^2 = \int_{B_n} \|\mu_n(x)\|_{\mathcal{G}}^2 dQ_X(x) \leq 2^2 \int_{\mathbb{X}} \|\mu(x)\|_{\mathcal{G}}^2 dQ_X(x), \quad (\text{D.3})$$

¹A Radon measure is a regular Borel measure.

we have $h_n \in L_2(\mathbb{X}, Q_x; \mathcal{G})$ for $n \in \mathbb{N}^+$. In addition, almost everywhere we have

$$\|\mu(x) - h_n(x)\|_{\mathcal{G}}^2 \leq (3 \|\mu(x)\|_{\mathcal{G}})^2, \quad (\text{D.4})$$

therefore, by the dominated convergence theorem

$$\begin{aligned} \lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} \|\mu - h_n\|_{L_2(\mathbb{X}, Q_x; \mathcal{G})}^2 &= \lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} \int_{\mathbb{X}} \|\mu(x) - h_n(x)\|_{\mathcal{G}}^2 dQ_x(x) \\ &= \int_{\mathbb{X}} \lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} \|\mu(x) - h_n(x)\|_{\mathcal{G}}^2 dQ_x(x) = 0. \end{aligned} \quad (\text{D.5})$$

In conclusion, for any $\varepsilon > 0$ there exists a simple function $h \in L_2(\mathbb{X}, Q_x; \mathcal{G})$ such that $\|\mu - h\|_{L_2(\mathbb{X}, Q_x; \mathcal{G})} < \varepsilon$. Therefore, it is sufficient to approximate h with a continuous function on a compact support. Let $h \in L_2(\mathbb{X}, Q_x; \mathcal{G})$ be

$$h(x) = \sum_{i=1}^N g_i \mathbb{I}(x \in A_i), \quad (\text{D.6})$$

where $g_i \in \mathcal{G}$ and $Q_x(A_i) < \infty$ for $i \in [N]$. The main idea is to approximate the indicator functions, $\{g_i \cdot \mathbb{I}(x \in A_i)\}_{i=1}^n$, separately. Let us fix $i = 1$ and $\varepsilon > 0$. Since Q_x is Radon and A_1 is measurable there exists a compact set $K \subseteq \mathbb{X}$ such that $K \subseteq A_1$ and

$$Q_x(A_1 \setminus K) < \frac{\varepsilon^2}{2N^2 \|g_1\|_{\mathcal{G}}^2}, \quad (\text{D.7})$$

and there exists an open set U such that $A_1 \subseteq U$ with

$$Q_x(U \setminus A_1) < \frac{\varepsilon^2}{2N^2 \|g_1\|_{\mathcal{G}}^2}. \quad (\text{D.8})$$

The application of Lemma D.1.3 yields that there exists an open set E such that \bar{E} is compact and $K \subseteq E \subseteq \bar{E} \subseteq U$. Because of Lemma D.1.4 there is a continuous function f_1 such that $f_1|_K = 1$ and $f_1|_{\mathbb{X} \setminus E} = 0$, from which it follows that f_1 has a compact support. For $h_1(x) \doteq g_1 \cdot \mathbb{I}(x \in A_1)$ and $\tilde{h}_1(x) \doteq g_1 \cdot f_1(x)$ we have

$$\begin{aligned} \int_{\mathbb{X}} \|h_1(x) - \tilde{h}_1(x)\|_{\mathcal{G}}^2 dQ_x(x) &= \int_{\mathbb{X}} \|g_1 \mathbb{I}(x \in A_1) - g_1 f_1(x)\|_{\mathcal{G}}^2 dQ_x(x) \\ &= \|g_1\|_{\mathcal{G}}^2 \int_{\mathbb{X}} (\mathbb{I}(x \in A_1) - f_1(x))^2 dQ_x(x) \leq \|g_1\|_{\mathcal{G}}^2 \int_{E \setminus K} 1 dQ_x(x) \\ &= \|g_1\|_{\mathcal{G}}^2 Q_x(E \setminus K) \leq \|g_1\|_{\mathcal{G}}^2 Q_x(U \setminus K) < \frac{\varepsilon^2}{N^2}. \end{aligned} \quad (\text{D.9})$$

Similarly, one can construct \tilde{h}_i which is close to h_i in $L_2(\mathbb{X}, Q_x; \mathcal{G})$ for all $i \in [N]$. Let $\tilde{\mu} \doteq \sum_{i=1}^N \tilde{h}_i$. Obviously, $\tilde{\mu}$ is continuous and has a compact support. Furthermore, by the

triangle inequality we have

$$\begin{aligned} \sqrt{\int_{\mathbb{X}} \|h(x) - \tilde{\mu}(x)\|_{\mathcal{G}}^2 dQ_x(x)} &= \sqrt{\int_{\mathbb{X}} \left\| \sum_{i=1}^N g_i(\mathbb{I}(x \in A_i) - f_i(x)) \right\|_{\mathcal{G}}^2 dQ_x(x)} \\ &\leq \sum_{i=1}^N \sqrt{\int_{\mathbb{X}} \|g_i(\mathbb{I}(x \in A_i) - f_i(x))\|_{\mathcal{G}}^2 dQ_x(x)} \leq \sum_{i=1}^N \sqrt{\frac{\varepsilon^2}{N^2}} = \varepsilon, \end{aligned} \quad (\text{D.10})$$

which finishes the proof of the theorem. \square

Lemma D.1.2. *Let $\{(\mathbb{X}_i, \mathcal{X}_i)\}_{i=1}^3$ be measurable spaces, let X_i , for $i \in \{1, 2, 3\}$, be \mathbb{X}_i -valued independent random elements on a probability space $(\Omega, \mathcal{A}, \mathbb{P})$ with push-forward measure Q_i . Let $f : \mathbb{X}_1 \times \mathbb{X}_2 \times \mathbb{X}_3 \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$ and $g : \mathbb{X}_1 \times \mathbb{X}_2 \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$ be measurable functions such that $f(X_1, X_2, X_3)$ and $g(X_1, X_2)$ are in $L_1(\Omega, \mathbb{P})$. If for Q_1 -almost all $x \in \mathbb{X}_1$ it holds that*

$$\mathbb{E}\left[f(x_1, X_2, X_3) \mid X_2\right] \leq g(x_1, X_2), \quad (\text{D.11})$$

then almost surely

$$\mathbb{E}\left[\int_{\mathbb{X}_1} f(x_1, X_2, X_3) dQ_1(x_1) \mid X_2\right] \leq \int_{\mathbb{X}_1} g(x_1, X_2) dQ_1(x_1). \quad (\text{D.12})$$

Proof. Integrating out both sides in (D.11) w.r.t. Q_1 yields

$$\int_{\mathbb{X}_1} \mathbb{E}\left[f(x_1, X_2, X_3) \mid X_2\right] dQ_1(x_1) \leq \int_{\mathbb{X}_1} g(x_1, X_2) dQ_1(x_1) = \mathbb{E}[g(X_1, X_2)]. \quad (\text{D.13})$$

In addition, the left hand side is

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbb{E}\left[\int_{\mathbb{X}} f(x_1, X_2, X_3) dQ_1(x_1) \mid X_2\right] &= \int_{\mathbb{X}_3} \int_{\mathbb{X}_1} f(x_1, X_2, x_3) dQ_1(x_1) dQ_3(x_3) \\ &= \int_{\mathbb{X}_1} \int_{\mathbb{X}_3} f(x_1, X_2, x_3) dQ_3(x_3) dQ_1(x_1) = \int_{\mathbb{X}_1} \mathbb{E}\left[f(x_1, X_2, X_3) \mid X_2\right] dQ_1(x_1), \end{aligned} \quad (\text{D.14})$$

because of Fubini's theorem. \square

For convenience, we state the main theorems that are used in the proofs of this section. We applied the following forms of the fundamental topological results from (Nagy, 2001, Lemma 5.1) and (Nagy, 2001, Theorem 5.1) to prove Theorem D.1.1.

Lemma D.1.3. *Let $(\mathbb{X}, \mathcal{T})$ be a locally compact Hausdorff space. Let K be a compact subset of \mathbb{X} , and let U be an open set, with $K \subseteq U$. Then, there exists an open set E such that \bar{E} is compact and $K \subseteq E \subseteq \bar{E} \subseteq U$.*

Lemma D.1.4 (Urysohn). *Let $(\mathbb{X}, \mathcal{T})$ be a locally compact Hausdorff space. Let K and F be disjoint subsets of \mathbb{X} , where K is compact and F is closed. Then, there exists a continuous function $f : \mathbb{X} \rightarrow [0, 1]$ such that $f|_K = 1$ and $f|_F = 0$.*

We also used the well-known results that follow from real analysis ([Dudley, 2002](#), Corollary 2.4.6) and ([Rudin, 1976](#), Theorem 4.15).

Theorem D.1.5 (Heine-Cantor). *A continuous function from a compact metric space to any metric space is uniformly continuous.*

Theorem D.1.6 (Weierstrass). *If f is a continuous mapping of a compact metric space X into \mathbb{R} , then f is bounded.*

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Summary

Machine learning is the essential component of artificial intelligence grounded on the pillars of statistical learning theory. In the dissertation we present stochastic guarantees for statistical learning methods in a data-driven framework. Our methods provide bases for robust, safe and stable practical applications by making only very mild structural and distributional assumptions. Four fundamental statistical problems are considered from distribution-free and non-asymptotic viewpoints: heavy-tailed mean estimation, binary classification, conditional kernel mean embedding estimation and independence testing.

In Chapter 3 we introduce the resampled median-of-means (RMM) method for constructing exact confidence intervals for the mean of a symmetric variable based on an i.i.d. sample without making any other distributional assumption. We prove that our method builds confidence intervals with exact coverage shrinking with optimal rates without using any hyperparameters, such as moment and range parameters.

In Chapter 4 we present a distribution-free resampling framework to build exact confidence regions for the regression function of binary classification for any finite sample size. We prove strong uniform bounds for a new empirical risk minimization (ERM) based method for model classes with finite pseudo-dimension and inverse Lipschitz parameterization and provide probably approximately correct (PAC) bounds on the \mathcal{L}_2 size of the confidence set. We also consider a k-nearest neighbors based method and two conditional kernel mean embedding based methods and prove strong pointwise consistency under mild assumptions. The presented algorithms are demonstrated on a logistic model class and compared to asymptotic ellipsoids of the maximum likelihood estimator.

Kernel mean embeddings, a widely used technique in machine learning, map probability distributions to elements of a reproducing kernel Hilbert space (RKHS). For supervised learning problems, where input-output pairs are observed, the conditional distribution of outputs given the inputs is a key object. The input dependent conditional distribution of an output can be encoded with an RKHS valued function, the conditional kernel mean map. In Chapter 5 we present a new recursive algorithm to estimate the conditional kernel mean map in an RKHS valued L_2 space. We prove the weak and strong L_2 consistency of our recursive estimator under mild structural assumptions. The theorem of Stone is generalized for Hilbert space valued regression in locally compact Polish spaces. The results are demonstrated on three application domains: for inputs coming from Euclidean spaces, Riemannian manifolds and locally compact subsets of function spaces.

In Chapter 6 we introduce robust independence tests with non-asymptotically guaranteed significance levels for synchronized, linear time-invariant stochastic systems, assuming that the systems are driven by jointly i.i.d. noises. Our method provides distribution-free bounds for the type I error probabilities, thus the innovations can have arbitrary joint distribution. The algorithm combines confidence regions with permutation tests and the Hilbert–Schmidt independence criterion to detect any nonlinear dependence between the observed systems. We also prove the consistency of our hypothesis tests under mild assumptions and demonstrate the ideas through the example of autoregressive systems.

Összefoglaló

A mesterséges intelligencia létfontosságú komponense a gépi tanulás, aminek a statisztikus tanuláselmélet biztosít háttérrel. A disszertációban statisztikus tanuláselméleti módszerekhez adunk adatvezérelt sztochasztikus garanciákat. A módszereink gyenge struktúrális és eloszlásbeli feltevésekkel élnek, ezért robusztus, stabil és biztonságos alkalmazások alapjául szolgálnak. Négy alapvető statisztikai problémát tekintünk eloszlás-független nézőpontból: vastag farkú eloszlások várható érték becslését, bináris osztályozást, feltételes kernel átlag beágyazás becslését és statisztikai függetlenség tesztelését.

A 3. fejezetben bevezetjük az újramintavételező átlagok mediánja becslést (RMM), amely egzakt konfidencia-intervallumot ad szimmetrikus eloszlások várható értékére független azonos eloszlású (i.i.d.) minta alapján további eloszlásbeli feltevések nélkül. Bebizonyítjuk, hogy a módszerünk (konstans faktoroktól eltekintve) optimális rátájú egzakt konfidencia-intervallumokat épít hiperparaméterek használata nélkül.

A 4. fejezetben eloszlás-független, egzakt konfidencia-halmazokat építünk a regressziós függvényre bináris osztályozás esetén tetszőleges minta méret esetén. Erős egyenletes korlátokat biztosítunk egy új tapasztalati kockázat minimalizálás alapú módszerhez véges pszeudo-dimenziójú és inverz-Lipschitz paraméterezésű modellosztályokra és nagy valószínűséggel megközelítőleg helyes korlátokat adunk a konfidencia-halmazok \mathcal{L}_2 méretére. Tekintünk egy k -legközelebbi szomszéd alapú módszert és két feltételes kernel átlag alapú módszert és bebizonyítjuk ezek erős pontonkénti konzisztenciáját gyenge feltevések mellett. A bemutatott módszereket egy logisztikus modellosztályon szemléltetjük és összehasonlítjuk a maximum likelihood becslés köré épített konfidencia-ellipszoidokkal.

A kernel átlag beágyazás – ami egy széles körben használt módszer a gépi tanulásban – a valószínűségi eloszlásokat egy reprodukáló magú Hilbert-térbe (RKHS) vetíti. A felügyelt tanulás esetén, ahol bemenet-kimenet párokat figyelünk meg, a kimenetek bemenetekre vett feltételes eloszlása játszik kulcs szerepet. A bemenetfüggő feltételes eloszlás egy RKHS értékű függvény segítségével, az ún. feltételes kernel átlag függvénnyel, kódolható. Az 5. fejezetben egy új rekurzív becslést vezetünk be a feltételes kernel átlag függvény becslésére egy RKHS értékű L_2 térben. Bebizonyítjuk a rekurzív becslő gyenge és erős L_2 konzisztenciáját gyenge struktúrális feltevések mellett. Általánosítjuk Stone tételét Hilbert-tér értékű regresszió esetére lokálisan kompakt lengyel terekre. Az eredményeket három alkalmazással szemléltetjük; a módszert Euklideszi-tereken, Riemann-sokaságokon és függvényterek lokálisan kompakt részalmazain demonstráljuk.

A 6. fejezetben egy robusztus függetlenségi próbát vezetünk be, ami nem-aszimptotikus garanciákat szolgáltat a szignifikancia szintre sztochasztikus, lineáris, időinvariáns rendszerek esetén, feltéve, hogy a rendszereket egy együttesen i.i.d. zaj hajtja. A módszerünk eloszlás-független korlátokat biztosít az elsőfajú hiba valószínűségére, azaz az innováció együttes eloszlása tetszőleges lehet. Az algoritmus halmazbecsléseket kombinál permutációs tesztekkel és a Hilbert-Schmidt függetlenségi kritériummal, hogy tetszőleges nemlineáris összefüggést észleljen. Bebizonyítjuk a statisztikai próba konzisztenciáját gyenge feltevések mellett és demonstráljuk a módszert autoregresszív rendszereken.